

**Strategies for dealing with large collections of
information in the workplace: A case study in personal
information management**

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Institut für Informations- und Bibliothekswissenschaft**

eingereicht von Jo Teichmann
geb. am 13.12.1994
in Hamburg

1. Gutachter/in: Prof. Dr. Jesse Dinneen
2. Gutachter/in Simon Hachmeier M.A.

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1 Introduction

In today's information-rich society, information management has become crucial daily, especially in professional settings. The sheer volume and complexity of information that individuals encounter necessitate using various tools and strategies, each with inherent limitations (Cortada, 2011). This challenge is particularly pronounced for professionals dealing with large volumes of information, where the constraints of tools and cognitive capacities are amplified. This research explores the challenges and

strategies such professionals employ to manage these challenges effectively. The focus on this aspect of Personal Information Management (PIM) is driven by the increasing importance of efficient information management in professional contexts and the potential benefits these insights can bring to improve information management skills more broadly.

William Jones, a notable scholar in the field of PIM, emphasizes that progress in this domain is about developing better tools and creating new, teachable strategies that enhance information management. Such strategies are vital for information literacy education, equipping individuals to navigate and thrive in an information-intensive environment (Jones, 2007a).

The research is anchored in the premise that better PIM leads to broader societal benefits. Within organizations, improved PIM can enhance employee productivity and understanding of their information needs, facilitating better teamwork and group information management. Beyond that, as Jones highlights, advancements in PIM are instrumental in mitigating aging challenges, such as declining working memory. They are crucial for individuals battling life-threatening illnesses as they juggle professional and personal responsibilities (Jones, 2007a).

The researchers hypothesize that those faced with large information collections are prone to develop unique strategies to mitigate the challenges. By investigating these people's PIM challenges and strategies, this thesis hopes to contribute to the broader discourse on PIM. What is even more, it aims to offer applicable and beneficial insights across a range of professional and personal scenarios, to inform educational programs in information literacy, and to prepare individuals for the demands of an information-intensive world where information management is a pivotal skill.

1.1 Signposting

The Introduction sets the stage, defining key terms and scope and laying the groundwork for the research questions. It underscores the Importance of the study in the current information landscape and segues into the Theory and Literature Review, which identifies gaps in existing research.

Our Methodology chapter details the research design and approach, describing how access was gained to the study environment and the rationale behind the chosen data collection methods. It also explains the creation of the interview guide and the steps taken during data analysis, including Qualitative Content Analysis and coding techniques. The Results section presents the heart of the research, organizing the data into a comprehensive code system that categorizes the challenges and strategies related to managing vast information collections. It evaluates the code system and evaluates challenges, strategies, and their transferability to different contexts or smaller information collections. In the

Discussion, we critically examine the implications of these findings, confronting the study's limitations and suggesting avenues for further research. The thesis culminates in the Conclusion, which synthesizes the insights gained and the impact they may have on the fields of information management and literacy. The Appendix provides an in-depth literature review of PIM terminology, a deeper analysis of the code system, and further visualization of the results.

1.2 Definition of the Basic Concepts and Scope

The following sections will define the basic concepts and how they are related in the context of this thesis. The following figure provides an overview of the relation of the concepts and a scope in the context of this thesis.

Figure 1 Concepts and relation (left), scope in the context of this thesis (right)

1.2.1 Personal Information and Personal Information Management

PIM is relatively young but “with ancient roots” compared to other research fields. In earlier times, when oral communication was dominant, human memory served as the chief means of preserving information, often assisted by mnemonics (Jones, 2007a). However, as information began to be documented and the volume of documents grew, the challenge of managing it emerged (Jones, 2007a). Similarly, Alon et al. observed more recently: “Mastery of high-level PIM strategies is essential as personal information spaces become fragmented and overloaded.” (Alon et al., 2019).

The modern discussion around PIM started post-World War II with Vannevar Bush's article “As we may think”. Bush highlighted the challenges arising from an immense quantity of information and the increasing specialization in scientific fields. He envisioned technology aiding our ability to manage the increase of information more efficiently (Jones, 2007a).

Thomas Malone is widely regarded as the father of PIM research (Bergman, 2013). Malone observed 1983 how “professional and clerical office workers organize the information in their desks and offices”.

He discovered that some workers neatly file their papers into clipboard binders. In contrast, other, more "messy" users retain their documents in piles, and, adding to Bush's vision, the "implications for designing "natural" and convenient computer-based information systems" were discussed (Malone, 1983).

The term "Personal Information Management" appeared five years later, in 1988 by the British psychologist Mark Lansdale in his paper "The psychology of personal information management" (Lansdale, 1988), when there was indeed widespread enthusiasm about how the personal computer may significantly improve people's capacity for information processing and management (Jones, 2007a; Lansdale, 1988).

Every one of us keeps information in our work and private lives. In the form of diaries, personal documents, notes, files, folders, books, emails, or bookmarks. All of this is personal information, not in the sense that it is private, but instead that we hold it for our purposes. Lansdale views the primary motivation for retaining this information (among others) in the retrieval and the desire for future use of the respective information (Lansdale, 1988).

According to his findings, further activities beyond the retrieval play a significant role within PIM. PIM includes categorizing information, handling it in general, and placing it in specific folders, for instance (Lansdale, 1988).

While Lansdale has been fundamental to the definition and the term PIM, over the years, others have introduced their definitions to the community, both for Personal Information and PIM.

William Jones offered numerous further meanings of "Personal Information," including 1) information controlled or owned by us, 2) information about us, 3) information directed at us, 4) information we send to others, 5) information we experience, and 6) information relevant to our needs (Jones, 2007b).

One of the most cited and commonly used definitions for PIM is indeed that of William Jones:

„Personal Information Management (PIM) refers to both the practice and the study of the activities a person performs in order to acquire or create, store, organize, maintain, retrieve, use and distribute the information needed to meet life's many goals (everyday or long-term, work-related or not) and to fulfill life's many roles and responsibilities (as parent, spouse, friend, employee, member of community, etc.). PIM places special emphasis on the organization and maintenance of personal information collections in which information items, such as paper documents, electronic documents,

email messages, web references, handwritten notes, etc., are stored for later use and repeated reuse
“ (Jones, 2007a).

This thesis adopts Jones's definition of PIM as its foundational framework. However, we will narrow our focus to explore the *challenges* and *strategies* (instead of activities) individuals employ to acquire, create, store, organize, maintain, retrieve, use, and distribute information. Our emphasis will be on addressing everyday and long-term, *work-related* (instead of non-work-related) objectives and the roles and responsibilities individuals uphold as *employees* (instead of parent, spouse, friend, employee, member of the community, etc.).

Within work-related objectives, we will further narrow the focus to employees who handle *vast* amounts of information, namely in the format of *files, documents, and datasets (i.e., database entries)*.

The following section aims to operationalize essential terms for this thesis. It will delve deeper into the differences and similarities between *activities, strategies, behavior, and practices*, as well as *information* and *file collections* and what *vast* or *large* refers to in the context of this thesis.

1.2.2 PIM Terminology

In the field of PIM research, the terms "activities", "practices", "strategies", and "behavior" are frequently used. However, their specific meanings and applications can often overlap, leading to potential confusion. The term "activities" is explicitly used by Jones in his definition of PIM. This section aims to distinguish it from related terms. The review in Appendix 9.2 aims to shed light on using these terms in current PIM literature. Interestingly, during the literature review, the researcher only found a few papers discussing the distinction between these terms. Often, they are used in combination without further consideration, frequently converging and interlacing, making it challenging to draw clear lines between them. Clarifying these terms is essential for fostering a more precise understanding and communication within PIM research.

1.2.3 Differentiation and Operationalization of PIM Terminology

While the literature review on PIM terminology in Appendix 9.2 has highlighted the distinct usage of PIM terms, a residue of ambiguity persists: Where exactly is the distinction between the terms?

In seeking clarity, we solicited insights from three renowned PIM researchers: Krtalić, Jones, and Bergman. Their perspectives, gathered through email correspondence, offer a deeper understanding and perhaps more questions to consider in the evolving field of PIM.

Krtalić underscores the all-encompassing nature of "behavior," emphasizing its ability to cover both intended and unintended practices. To Krtalić, behavior is shaped and influenced by an individual's attitudes, feelings, and knowledge. Furthermore, she defines "strategies" as the planned methodologies individuals deploy when dealing with specific PIM challenges, with "activities" as the actionable steps within these strategies. She stated:

"In my opinion, behaviour is an overarching term encompassing intended and unintended practices and is influenced by attitudes and feelings as well as knowledge. Strategies may refer to planned approach to dealing with a particular PIM problem, and activities could be considered as steps in the implementation of strategies."

Jones takes a different approach. He distinguishes between the terms by presenting "behavior" as something observable with an external focus. At the same time, "activity" is a term he prefers due to its internal, unobservable component, such as intent. He expands upon the term "practice" as a recurring and routine set of activities. Jones's interpretation of "strategy" is shaped by a long-term vision or objective. A prime example he provides is retaining all incoming emails in one's inbox to streamline the organization and utilize the inbox as a storage database. He shares:

"Behavior – observable with person serving, for example, as subject. I don't use this term. Activity – I prefer this term, connotes purposeful behavior with internal unobservable component (e.g., intent). Practice – activity or set of activities done repeatedly, routinely. Strategy – activities done with larger objective in mind e.g., I leave all incoming email in my inbox to avoid time in organizing and so that the inbox can serve as a kind of database for incoming personal information."

Lastly, Bergman simplifies the distinctions by offering a hierarchical understanding of the terms. In his view, "behavior" is the broadest term, succeeded by "strategies" that represent how individuals tackle their tasks and challenges. He then places "activities" and "practices" on the narrower end of the spectrum, with their application being confined to specific scenarios and technological contexts. He succinctly states: "The way I understand it is that "behavior" is the most general term, after that "strategies" which are the general way people address the tasks and problems they have, while "activities" and "practices" are more specific (e.g., limited to specific situations and technologies)."

To summarize:

- **Behavior** is perceived as the broadest term, capturing both intentional and unintentional actions and being observable.
- **Strategies** involve a more planned or goal-oriented approach to PIM challenges.
- **Activities** are the actionable steps or purposeful actions taken within the broader strategies or

behaviors, often having an internal, intent-driven component.

- **Practices** are repetitive activities or routines that may be specific to particular contexts.

While there are common threads in the perspectives of Krtalić, Jones, and Bergman, subtle distinctions arise from their understandings and usage of the terms. It becomes evident that the nuances in definitions can be shaped by personal preference, research focus, and experiential interpretations. This underscores the importance of clarity and context when employing these terms in research and practice.

For this thesis, the researcher provides a working definition of strategies in the context of PIM: “Strategies are general, intended approaches to dealing with PIM challenges, problems and needs. These Strategies may involve activities and practices to overcome a specific problem or need.”

1.3 What is an “Information Collection” in the Context of this Thesis?

In the context of this thesis, an "information collection" refers to a digital file collection stored on a person's computer or server (i.e. cloud) system. Potential file formats within these collections can range widely, encompassing documents (e.g., PDFs, Word files), multimedia (e.g., images, videos, audio recordings), data sets (e.g., Excel spreadsheets, CSV files), and other formats.

1.3.1 File Management

File Management (FM) is a subset of PIM that focuses on organizing, storing, retrieving, and manipulating *digital computer files*. As defined by Dinneen in 2023 during a presentation in the course “Human Information Behavior”: “FM is PIM regarding digital computer files”.

File Management (FM) is vital as it's an everyday task for computer users. We regularly handle files - creating, naming, moving, and more. This is central to knowledge workers and many personal hobbies in today's information society. Effective FM ensures we remain organized and productive (Dinneen, 2023).

The coming section of the thesis will cover the definition of *large* information collections to operationalize a *large* information collection from a *smaller* one.

1.4 What is a “Large” Information Collection in the Context of this Thesis?

In the context of this thesis, "large" is a multidimensional attribute that must first be considered from different dimensions before it is operationalized.

1.4.1 First: A Qualitative Perspective

Volume is the most straightforward dimension and refers to the number of documents or files within a collection (Dinneen et al., 2019; Douceur & Bolosky, 1999). Another dimension under consideration is the depth and width of file collection structures (Dinneen et al., 2019; Douceur & Bolosky, 1999; Zhang & Hu, 2014).

Beyond the volume, depth, and width of a file collection, "large" also considers the variety of storage locations. A large information collection might span multiple databases, servers, or physical storage devices, presenting additional complexities in retrieval and management (Gonçalves & Jorge, 2003). Various document types and formats can also characterize a large information space. This diversity might encompass text files, spreadsheets, images, videos, databases, etc. (Hicks et al., 2008).

Another dimension is the information density: It is not just about the number or type of documents but also the depth of information. High entropy indicates low information gain. In contrast, low entropy means a high information gain (Ye, 2022).

The overall size of a collection in terms of bytes or terabytes can also be a consideration, especially when thinking about storage solutions, backup, and retrieval times (Dinneen et al., 2019; Douceur & Bolosky, 1999).

As McDonald and Levine-Clark highlighted, "The study of PIM itself is often fragmented [...]. Many excellent studies focus, for example, on e-mail, other studies on the Web, or the management of special forms of digital information (such as digitally encoded songs or photographs). There is a need for integrative approaches in studying PIM and in designing and evaluating supporting tools." (McDonald & Levine-Clark, 2017).

This study does not integrate all sorts of information, as suggested by McDonald and Levin Clark, but to holistically understand PIM in the context of large information spaces, the researcher has decided to adopt a multi-dimensional approach, including both the size in bytes and the volume of the information collection in several documents or files.

Size, measured in terms of bytes or terabytes, provides a tangible metric that encapsulates the sheer magnitude of information and the potential challenges associated with storage, backup, version control, and retrieval. Concurrently, volume, denoted by the number of documents or files within a collection, highlights the practical aspects of managing, organizing, and accessing these pieces of information.

1.4.2 A Quantitative Definition

In defining a quantitative threshold for what constitutes a “large” information collection, this thesis references the study “The Scale and Structure of Personal File Collections” by Dinneen et al., 2019. According to their findings, typical collections contain between 29 thousand and 193 thousand files (excluding shortcuts, aliases, and symlinks) and between 4 thousand and 26 thousand folders. Regarding data size, these collections range from 33 to 232 GB (Dinneen et al., 2019).

Our primary focus for this thesis is on the outliers: collections exceeding 193 thousand files or those larger than 232 GB.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The workplace's management and organization of personal information have drawn considerable attention in current research. This literature review synthesizes the findings of multiple studies on PIM across various professional domains, focusing on the relationship between the volume of information and PIM strategies. The Discussion in Chapter 5 will review further literature connected to this thesis's results.

2.2 Information Management in the Workplace

McDonald and Levine-Clark provide a comprehensive overview of the challenges and strategies associated with managing personal information in the workplace. The challenges range from information overload and fragmentation to controlling the flow of information and social challenges like the complexities of sharing information in different settings. The authors discuss the importance of effective information management for productivity and efficiency and highlight the role of digital tools in facilitating this process. They emphasize the need for ongoing education and training to ensure employees have the skills and knowledge to manage their personal information effectively (McDonald & Levine-Clark, 2017).

Khoo et al. conducted a study to understand how users organize electronic files on their workstations. The study involved harvesting filenames, folder names, and file structures from the personal computers or notebooks that the participants use at work. The study found that users create a wide variety of file structures, ranging from simple to complex and that the nature of these structures is influenced by a variety of factors, including the nature of the user's work, the user's personal preferences, and the user's level of computer literacy (Khoo et al., 2007).

Alon et al. explored how knowledge workers manage their personal information spaces in highly overloaded work environments. The study suggested that high-level strategies are needed to cope with these challenges. The study found that knowledge workers develop innovative strategies for keeping and managing information, which could benefit a broader audience. These strategies include creating a personal taxonomy for organizing information, using search functionality to retrieve information, and using digital tools to manage information (Alon et al., 2019).

2.3 PIM Studies on Different Professions

Several studies have examined PIM practices by focusing on groups of professionals in various domains, such as private-sector employees like engineers (Chaudhry & Al-Mahmud, 2015; Yasmin et al., 2019), scholars (AL-Omar & Cox, 2016), information professionals (AlRukaibani & Chaudhry, 2019), writers and artists (Krtalić & Dinneen, 2022) and high-school students (Forkosh-Baruch & Alon, 2020). One of the most studied groups is knowledge workers, as seen in the studies by Alon et al. (Alon et al., 2017, 2019). The professions of these knowledge workers range from factory CEOs, sales and marketing managers, entrepreneurs in the administration area, senior intelligence officers, and municipal directors of education to deputy directors of elementary school and elementary school teachers. Another group studied is scientists, as seen in the study by Chaudhry and Alajmi (Chaudhry & Alajmi, 2022), which focuses on how scientists manage and share information—additionally, the study by Khoo et al. (Khoo et al., 2007) looks at how users generally organize electronic files on their workstations, which could include a variety of work groups. Lastly, the study by Zhang and Hu (Zhang & Hu, 2014) examines the file folder structures of personal computers of Ph.D. students and administrative staff in an academic environment, indicating that academic workers are also subjects of these studies.

Another research paper by Chaudhry investigates the information management behavior of Kuwaiti engineers, focusing on how they find, manage, and re-find information. The study emphasizes the importance of information literacy in the digital age, particularly in the increasing complexity of digital resources. It found that engineers use a variety of sources to collect information and often save it in folders for future use. However, using information management tools was rare, and many participants expressed a need for training in information literacy. The study suggests that companies should focus on improving information management skills among their employees (Chaudhry & Al-Mahmud, 2015).

2.4 Challenges in Personal Information Management

Chaudhry and Alajmi discussed the challenges faced in PIM among scientists, such as information anxiety and information overload. While the study did not explicitly mention the size of the information

collections, these challenges may be influenced by the size of the collections. The study found that scientists often need help managing and sharing information due to these challenges and often resort to ad hoc strategies to cope with these challenges (Chaudhry & Alajmi, 2022). In the context of information overload, Koltay discussed ways of mitigating information overload in a data-intensive world. The study argued that information overload is a significant challenge in the digital age and that individuals must develop coping strategies. The study suggested that these strategies could include developing information literacy skills, using digital tools to manage information, and adopting a mindful approach to information consumption (Koltay, 2017).

2.5 Studies on the Effect of a Collection's Size on PIM

Several studies implicitly or explicitly address the size of information collections and its implications.

Although two decades old, a study in 2002 foresaw the escalating complexity of managing vast information collections, a challenge that has only intensified in the current era of information overload. It highlighted the inadequacy of traditional information management strategies and emphasized the need for more intuitive and user-centric approaches to manage and navigate large collections of information and knowledge, especially in collaborative environments. The study advocated for multi-dimensional, associative, and context-based categorization of documents (Bookma, 2022).

Another study by Dinneen et al. titled "The Scale and Structure of Personal File Collections" (Dinneen et al., 2019) explicitly mentions the size of file collections. The study found that typical collections are growing in scale (up to nearly 200,000 files) and external structure (folder trees sized 15 x 5,000), and as a collection grows, categorization becomes necessary to keep it comprehensible, navigable and accessible (Dinneen et al., 2019). The study also noted that the observed collections typically occupied 33 to 232 GB of storage space, far larger than the largest average collection size reported a decade ago (2.5 GB). However, the study also highlighted that no coherent, detailed description of the scale and structure of typical personal file collections currently exists, leaving open questions about the nature of these collections.

The study by Alon et al. implicitly addresses the size of information collections by exploring how knowledge workers manage their personal information in *highly overloaded* work environments (Alon et al., 2019). While the study does not explicitly mention the size of the collections, the concept of information overload suggests that the size of the collections could be substantial.

Similarly, the study by Khoo et al. implicitly addresses the size of information collections by examining how users organize electronic files on their workstations. The complexity of the file structures that users

create could be influenced by the size of the collections (Khoo et al., 2007).

In the case of researchers, authors argue that PIM gains particular weight because most researchers “own” more objects than they can remember, and PIM strategies help them become aware of their information decisions and needs more explicitly (Bruce et al., 2004; Koltay, 2017), hinting at the importance of PIM as a means to manage large information collections.

2.6 Conclusion

This thesis hypothesizes that learning from individuals managing the largest information volumes could provide valuable insights into effective PIM strategies. The rationale behind this approach is that those confronted with vast amounts of information are more likely to develop efficient and innovative management strategies due to the high necessity of managing their information effectively. This perspective seeks to shift the focus within PIM research from the diversity of subjects to the scale of information they handle.

However, current literature lacks a focus on the scale of information in its analysis. This gap is significant, considering the increasing volume of information in modern work environments and the necessity for efficient management strategies. While studies have explored how various professional groups, such as knowledge workers, scientists, engineers, and academics, manage their personal information, there is a lack of research explicitly addressing the impact of collection size on PIM.

There is a need for research to identify the challenges and strategies that emerge in the context of large information collections, as this can provide insights into developing more effective and practical PIM strategies, increasingly relevant in the information-intensive landscape of contemporary work environments and beyond (McDonald & Levine-Clark, 2017).

3 Methodology

The study design and approach to the research field will be delineated in the subsequent sections. A detailed examination of this study's data collection and analysis methodologies will be undertaken. Specifically, we will consider the semi-structured guideline interviews and the content analysis proposed by Kuckartz. Additionally, the computer-assisted analysis using the software tool MAXQDA, which aided in the creation and subsequent refinement of the category system, will be elucidated.

3.1 Research Question

Building on the literature review, it becomes clear that more detailed research is needed on the challenges and strategies used by people who deal with large amounts of information. As digital information proliferates, there is a pressing need to understand these strategies better.

This gap in research leads us to the main research question: "What strategies do individuals employ to manage and handle vast amounts of information in a workplace setting?" In this context, particular attention is given to the challenges of dealing with extensive information collections. Ultimately, the discussion will consider whether these identified strategies can benefit a broader audience.

3.2 Pre-Assumptions

Since PIM is a relatively new research field, the challenges and strategies applied to large information collections have yet to be extensively researched, as shown in the previous chapter. As a result, hardly any theories can be derived from the literature to answer the research questions.

3.3 Research Design

Therefore, a qualitative research approach was chosen to address the research question. Helfferich suggests that traditional "tests" are unsuitable for studying complex learning pertaining to life experiences (such as learning to handle vast amounts of information). Gaining a more profound understanding requires engaging in conversations with participants within the research domain. Qualitative studies aim to decipher meanings or "individual perceptions", sometimes referred to as "notions of reality" or "adaptive strategies" (Helfferich, 2011).

For two weeks in October 2023, semi-structured interviews were conducted with a selected, heterogeneous group of people, handling vast amounts of information as per the definition in Chapter 1.4.2. The evaluation of the interviews was then carried out using the Qualitative Content Analysis, according to Kuckartz (see chapter 3.9).

3.4 Access to the Study Environment

The researcher's position within next Statista offers a unique vantage point for studying the management of large information volumes, owing to the company's role as a data-centric consulting firm and its affiliation with Statista, one of the world's most comprehensive statistics databases. The company's work, inherently reliant on the cumulation of large-scale data, mirrors the research focus on extensive information management, making it an exemplary setting to study the strategies deployed by professionals in real-world scenarios.

3.4.1 Description of the Samples

The criteria for participant selection were stringently outlined to ensure the research targets individuals with firsthand experience managing extensive file collections. Specifically, potential participants needed to have worked with a file collection comprising either 190 thousand files or more or a collection exceeding 230 GB or more in data volume. Preliminary interviews were conducted with individuals holding leadership roles within the companies data units to pinpoint suitable candidates for the study. The recruitment strategy was to ensure a heterogeneous sample (to enhance the content-related representativeness of the study) while adhering to the defined criteria for managing large volumes of information. This approach offers diverse perspectives on information-handling strategies and lays the groundwork for potential theory development. It was adopted to ensure the insights drawn were deeply rooted in lived experiences and were a genuine reflection of challenges and strategies in dealing with massive information collections.

Over two weeks, the researcher pinpointed ten knowledge workers from various departments across the two companies. These individuals, who vary in roles and years of experience, consistently engage with extensive information collections at differing frequencies. All subjects are working with collections larger than 190 thousand files and 230 GB in collection size. Below is a cross-table of the interview participants.

Table 1 Cross-table of interview participants

STAKEHOLDER GROUP: INFORMATION WORKER		Frequency in dealing with huge amounts of data				PARTICIPANTS (N)
Area	Experience in the field	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Rarely	
Data Science	<2 years					
	2-5 years	1	1			2
	5-10 years	1	1			2
Data Engineering	<2 years					
	2-5 years		1			1
	5-10 years					
Lead Data Science	<2 years					
	2-5 years		1			1
	5-10 years	1				1
Project Management & Team Lead	<2 years					
	2-5 years			1		1
	5-10 years		1			1
Analyst	<2 years					
	2-5 years	1				1
	5-10 years					

3.5 Data Collection Methods

The study is based on five qualitative interviews with employees from nxt Statista and another five with employees from Statista.

3.5.1 Reasons for Choosing this Method

The decision was made to conduct semi-guided interviews while examining different types of qualitative interviews. This interview format was chosen to allow open narration while ensuring the focus of the research interest.

In determining the most appropriate research method for this study, it was essential to consider methodologies previously employed in similar areas of interest, as emphasized by Kaiser (Kaiser, 2014). Notably, Kaye et al. (Kaye et al., 2006) conducted semi-structured interviews combined with tours of office spaces, engaging scholars across various disciplines. In a related vein, Chaudhry and Alajmi (Chaudhry & Alajmi, 2022) used semi-structured interviews to delve into the practices, tools, and techniques scientists and researchers utilize for PIM. Similarly, Alon et al. (Alon et al., 2019) conducted detailed interviews with knowledge workers, targeting their experiences managing personal information. Lastly, Bergman conducted 20 semi-structured 90-minute interviews to identify and map variables that characterize and account for the variety of PIM behavior (Bergman, 2013). The recurring theme of these studies is the utilization of semi-structured interviews, which highlights their effectiveness in capturing the intricacies of information management across different PIM dimensions and professional settings.

According to Myers and Newman (Myers & Newman, 2007), qualitative interviews are a powerful data-gathering technique that allows for a rich, in-depth understanding of the subject matter. The study by Chaudhry and Alajmi (Chaudhry & Alajmi, 2022) further emphasizes the value of qualitative interviews, particularly semi-structured ones, in exploring complex behaviors and practices, such as how scientists manage their personal information. They argue that qualitative interviews provide an opportunity to probe beneath the surface, offering a rich context for understanding the information behavior of scientists. Qualitative interviews allow researchers to see what is not ordinarily on view and examine what is looked at but seldom seen (Myers & Newman, 2007). Using qualitative interviews as a research method is often driven by the need for depth, flexibility, and a nuanced understanding of the research subject.

Gwizdka and Chignell write the following in their chapter on individual differences in PIM:

“The unique factors and situations of different people influence their PIM needs and practices, as well as which PIM tools might suit them best. But even people who have quite similar profiles with respect to jobs and demographics can exhibit huge observable difference in PIM-related behaviours, their choice of strategy and their preference in tools [...]” (Gwizdka & Chignell, 2007)

Gwizdka and Chignell underscore that managing personal information is a complex process shaped by personal preferences, tasks, tools, and context. Even among seemingly similar individuals, there can be stark differences in how they handle and organize their information. This is not just about what tools they use but also about their personal strategies and habits.

Given this complexity and the subtle differences between individuals, capturing the whole picture using straightforward, number-based methods is challenging. This might be why many PIM researchers lean towards qualitative approaches. By using such methods, they can delve deeper into individual experiences and practices, offering richer insights than mere statistics might provide.

This may help to understand why most PIM research takes a qualitative methodology with outcomes described in narrative terms (Bergman, 2013).

Additionally, the guided format of semi-structured interviews provides a particular structure or thematic framework, which is significant considering the context of a researcher previously inexperienced in qualitative interview techniques.

3.6 Creation of the Interview Guide

During the initial phase of the interviews, a guideline was developed. This was based on the "SPSS" method by Dr. C. Helfferich. This approach to creating a guideline is proven effective because it provides an appropriate structure for research interest while allowing participants to express themselves. "SPSS" represents four process steps: Collect, Review, Sort, and Summarize (in German, “Sammeln”, “Prüfen”, “Sortieren”, “Subsummieren”) (Helfferich, 2011). For readers interested in more detail, a comprehensive description of the process is available in Appendix 9.13. The resulting interview guide can be found in Appendix 9.14.

3.7 Pre-Test

A pre-test was conducted with one of the ten subjects (the results were excluded from the results to ensure the comparability between subjects). Questions regarding specific phenomena such as information fragmentation and information overload were excluded, and the focus was adjusted to keep the questions more open-ended, allowing for a broader answer and exploration of the topic. Each

question was weighted based on its potential impact on answering the research questions. The pre-test resulted in the final, more condensed, focused version of the interview guide.

3.8 Interviews

The interviews were conducted using the web-conference platform Microsoft Teams. The first interview was conducted on Thursday, October 17th, and the last on Friday, October 27th. The total duration of the collected interview material (excluding the pre-test interview) was 497 minutes and 44 seconds. The average duration of interviews was 55 minutes and 18 seconds. The shortest Interview was with Subject 2, with 34 minutes and 37 seconds. The most extended interview was Subject 9, with one hour, 43 minutes, and 54 seconds. Two subjects (Subjects 2 and 6) have interviews that are under 45 minutes. Five subjects (Subjects 1, 3, 4, 5, and 7) have 45 minutes to just under one hour of interviews. One Subject (Subject 8) has an interview approaching one hour but not exceeding it. One Subject (Subject 9) has an interview lasting over one hour. Nine interviews were conducted in German, while the interview with Subject 2 was in English.

The material resulted in 132 DIN A4 pages transcript of interview material. Additionally, the research has digitally collected notes on the interview guide of each participant, ranging from one to three DIN A4 pages per subject.

SUBJECT NR	INTERVIEW LENGTH IN HOURS, MINUTES, SECONDS	DIN A4 PAGES TRANSCRIPT
1	47:42	12
2	34:37	10
3	51:43	14
4	53:28	15
5	56:31	13
6	42:21	10
7	47:46	15
8	59:10	19
9	1:43:54	24

Table 2 Overview length of interviews and transcriptions

3.9 Data Analysis

The interview material was analyzed following the Content Structuring Qualitative Content Analysis according to Kuckartz (“Die inhaltlich strukturierende qualitative Inhaltsanalyse”). In the following, the researcher will provide the reasoning for the choice of method, followed by a short contrast of the different methods of analysis that can be used in the context of a qualitative content analysis following Kuckartz.

3.9.1 Reasons for this Method

Several factors were crucial in the quest for an appropriate strategy for evaluating qualitative data. The adequacy of the method for answering the work's questions was the deciding factor. At the same time, it had to be that a large amount of data had to be handled by only one person. Finally, a method appropriate for a researcher still a novice in qualitative research should be discovered; thus, a straightforward step-by-step approach was favorable. These prerequisites are met by Kuckartz Qualitative Content Analysis (Kuckartz, 2022).

3.9.2 Method of Qualitative Content Analysis

Various approaches to Qualitative Content Analysis are primarily categorized as either deductive or inductive. In the deductive approach, the researcher adopts an existing perspective from the literature (or the interview guideline). This serves as a lens through which the qualitative data is viewed, interpreted, and rated, drawing comparisons between the data and the established theories. This approach naturally requires the existence of relevant literature on the topic. On the other hand, in the inductive approach, the researcher analyzes the data without leaning on existing literature. This often happens when minimal literature is pertinent to the specific research questions. Consequently, the research question should mirror the researcher's chosen analytical approach. For instance, if there is a scarcity of related studies and an inductive approach is opted for, the research question should be explorative or descriptive, aligning with inductive reasoning.

Kuckartz describes three subtypes of Qualitative Content Analysis: content structuring, evaluative, and type-forming qualitative content analysis. The evaluative subtype should be selected for research questions that require an assessment, classification, and evaluation of content (i.e., “Do data scientists use the same strategies to handle information as librarians?”). The type-forming subtype is the most complex analysis and would be suitable for a research question that aims to detect specific subgroups within a sample. In the context of empirical research, typing means grouping cases into similar patterns or groups that can be clearly distinguished from their surroundings and other patterns and groups. This type of analysis goes beyond this work's scope and often builds upon prior content structuring or evaluative analysis. The researcher has therefore concluded that the most suitable method for this work is the content structuring subtype. This subtype allows for deductive and inductive category formation, as described below.

The seven phases of Content Structuring Qualitative Content Analysis by Kuckartz build the foundation for the following steps conducted during data analysis.

Figure 2 Kuckartz's seven step content-analysis cycle

3.10 Steps Conducted During Data Analysis

1. Tools, transcription, and types of categories
2. Initial Text work
3. Deductive code formation of main categories
4. Material coded with main categories
5. Collection of all main codes
6. Building of subcodes
7. Coding entire material
8. Analysis and visualization

3.10.1 Tools, Transcription, and Types of Categories

The recorded interview material was first loaded into the Software MAXQDA 2022. The researcher chose this software over others since it has clear documentation and many tutorials. Additionally, the affiliated university provided the researcher with a free license for the software. Within MAXQDA 2022, the researcher then transcribed each of the interviews.

Kuckartz defined several categories in Qualitative Content Analysis, namely:

Objective-based Categories: These categories revolve around concrete or perceived factual elements. They can, for example, categorize a profession, indicate a specific location, or describe an event.

Thematic Categories: These denote particular subjects, arguments, or thought patterns. In an interview, such categories highlight sections that detail these themes. Their primary role is akin to pointers, directing attention to relevant sections within the text.

Evaluative Categories: Such categories facilitate data assessment based on established standards. They often have a specified set of variations to help gauge data. For instance, a category might have ordinal levels, such as "prominent," "slightly evident," or "not evident," or even dichotomous scales like "present" and "absent."

Analytical Categories: These emerge from an in-depth engagement with the data, offering interpretations beyond mere descriptions, which thematic categories might provide. For instance, exploring the theme of "environmental behavior" might lead to the discernment of a recurring "cost-benefit rationale."

Kuckartz further defines theoretical, in-situ, and formal categories, which will not be described in further detail, as they are irrelevant to this research (Kuckartz, 2022).

3.10.2 Initial Text Work

This step was accounted for as the researcher transcribed the interviews.

3.10.3 Deductive Category Formation in Qualitative Research

Introduction

Deductive category formation is a methodology in qualitative research that primarily forms categories without immediate reference to the empirical data but rather as a derivation from “general principles” (Kuckartz, 2022).

Sources for Deductive Categories

Multiple sources can guide the development of deductive categories: theoretical framework, research literature, interview guidelines, process models, hypotheses and assumptions, everyday knowledge, personal experience, and subjective theories. For this research, the deductive foundation is based on the interview guideline (Kuckartz, 2022).

From the interview guideline, the researcher has defined the following deductive codes:

Table 3 Deductive codes from the interview guideline

QUESTION IN THE GUIDELINE	DEDUCTIVE CODE
Können Sie kurz beschreiben, was Ihre Arbeit als XXX beinhaltet?	Main Task
Können Sie Ihre Arbeit noch einmal beschreiben, aber jetzt auf die Rolle der für Ihre Arbeit benötigten Informationen eingehen?	Main Task: focus on info
Welche Informationen haben und nutzen Sie in Ihrem persönlichen Arbeitsbereich?	Info Types
Was ist die Quelle dieser Informationen (woher stammen die Dokumente)?	Info Sources
Wie sind die Dokumente in Ihrem persönlichen Arbeitsbereich gelandet?	Info Route
Wie gestalten Sie Ihren alltäglichen Umgang mit Informationen in Ihrem persönlichen Arbeitsbereich?	General Practices dealing with info
Denken Sie an einen Zeitpunkt, an dem Sie mit besonders vielen Informationen Umgehen mussten, was waren die Herausforderungen?	Challenges
Glauben Sie, dass die von Ihnen angewandten Strategien auch anderen Personen in unterschiedlichen Kontexten (zB mit weniger großen Info Mengen) helfen könnten?	Transferability of strategies
Warum ja?	Transferable (yes)
Warum nicht?	Not transferable (no)

3.10.4 Coding of Material with Main Codes

The material was looked through line-by-line and coded with the main (deductive) codes.

3.10.5 Collection of all Main Codes and Building of Subcodes using Inductive Coding

The inductive coding process in qualitative research, as outlined by Kuckartz, is a systematic approach that allows for the organic development of categories from the interview material. This method involves six key steps:

1. **Purpose Definition:** The research starts with the aim of exploring challenges and strategies in managing large information volumes. Initial deductive categories are drawn from the interview guide, allowing for more detailed inductively formed subcategories.
2. **Category Type and Abstraction Level:** Based on the research questions, objective, thematic, evaluative category types were chosen. The interview guide is initially structured to elicit

objective descriptions, with later sections probing for thematic and evaluative responses. Analytical categories may emerge in later stages of the organization of the coding system.

3. **Data Familiarization and Segment Determination:** Using MAXQDA, the analysis focuses on encoding sense units - comprehensive statements retaining meaning independently.
4. **Sequential Text Processing:** The coding is iterative, with categories assigned or formed line-by-line. On the right is the interim result of the process, showing the condensed coding system at the end of the first cycle through the material. The expanded interim result of the coding system can be found in Appendix 9.11. The number on the right indicates the codes assigned to the coding. At this point, 487 “sense units” have been encoded from the material. Blue indicates the objective-based categories, green the thematic categories, and red the evaluative categories.

Figure 3 Interim code system at stage four of the coding process

5. **Category System Organization:** Categories are then grouped and hierarchized once saturation is reached, streamlining the system into main categories and subcategories.
6. **Finalizing the Category System:** The system remains open for adjustments until no more categories emerged. Then, each category was clearly defined and exemplified by a quote from the material.

For a detailed view of the coding process and the final coding system, refer to Appendix 9.3 and 9.4 respectively.

3.10.6 Coding Entire Material

Based on the final category system, the entire material was reviewed again, and relevant text sections were coded.

3.10.7 Analysis and Visualization

The final code system was then ready for analysis and is being discussed in Chapters 4 and 5, as well as the Appendix.

4 Results

The code system was formed based on deductive categories from the interview guidelines and literature. In addition to the deductive codes, inductively formed codes were added to the system to render the code system exhaustive, as described in Chapter 3.

The following Chapter, 4.1, will present an overview of the developed code system, Chapter 4.2 contains an in-depth description of all analytical codes. Appendix 9.6 to 9.10 shows an in-depth analysis of all codes, and Appendix 9.12 shows the distribution of codes among the subjects.

4.1 *The General Structure of the Code System*

The full description of each code and an anchor example from the material can be found in Appendix 9.4.

4.1.1 *Part I: Challenges Dealing with Large Information Collections*

Table 4 Code system part I: challenges dealing with large information collections

Themes in the code	Amount of codings
<i>Total Codings in Part I</i>	82
Challenges	0
Out Of Control / External Project	8
Data Complexity And Source Management	0
Fragmentation	3
Information Flood	2
Information Storage And Access Challenges	0
Storage	9
Storage / Access	4
Archiving	2
Organisational And Collaborative Challenges	0
Clarity	5
Uncertainty And Unpredictability	2
Data Protection Concerns	4
Time-Constraints	4
Collaboration	5
Technical And Processing Challenges	0

Special Skills Needed	2
Filetype	1
Physical Challenges	2
Data-Cleaning	2
Filesystem	2
Tool Limitations	8
Time / Processing Challenges	4
Differences In Challenges Large Vs. Small Info Collections	0
Processing / Ressources	2
Overview	1
Correction	1
Organisation / Structure	3
Search	1
Structure, Planning And Preperation	5

4.1.2 Part II: Strategies when Dealing with Large Information Collections

Table 5 Code system part II: strategies when dealing with large information collections

Themes in the code	Amount of codings
<i>Total Codings in Part II</i>	<i>126</i>
Strategies	0
Strategies To Address Organisational And Collaborative Challenges	0
Mental Models	6
Information Hygiene	4
Communication And Collaboration	10
Documentation	6
Learning From Others	4
Strategies For Technical And Processing Challenges	0
Random Samples	1
Automatisation	1
Data Prioritising	2
Batches	6
Using / Developing Tools	0
General Advice Regarding Tools	2

Tools That Were Developed Externally	10
Tools That Were Developed Internally	4
Strategies For Information Storage And Access Challenges	0
Search	3
Access	6
Version Control	3
Storage And Archiving	9
Foundational Strategies	0
Structured Approach	12
Planning And Preparation	6
Strategies For Information Complexity And Source Management	0
Structure	0
File/Folder Names	0
Maschine Readability	3
Version Control	4
Flexible Adaption As Collection Grows	4
Folder Struktur	0
Context-Dependent Decision-Making	2
Data Zones / Specific Structure	7
Early On Structure	3
Personal Structure	6
Standards	2

4.1.3 Part III: Transferability of Strategies to Another Context or Smaller Information Collections

Table 6 Code system part III: transferability of strategies to another context or smaller information collections

Themes in the code	Amount of codings
<i>Total Codings in Part III</i>	20
Transferability Of Strategies	0
Transferability Of Strategies	0
Transferable (Yes)	0
Importance Of Conscious Data Management	1
Search	1

Re-Use Of Existing Set-Ups	3
Use Of Structure	3
Versioning	2
Not Transferable (No)	0
Over-Engineering	6
Threshold Not Reached To Determine If A Structure Works	2
Strategy That Emerged From Larger Collections Being Adopted	2

4.1.4 Part IV: Contextual Insights

Table 7 Code system part IV: contextual insights

Themes in the code	Amount of codings
<i>Total Codings in Part IV</i>	60
Contextual Insights	0
Info Sources	14
Info Types	7
Main Task: Focus On Info	11
Main Task	10
Info Route	12
Largest / Most Complex Projects	6

4.1.5 Part V: General Practices when Dealing with Large Information Collections

Table 8 Code system part V: general practices when dealing with large information collections

Themes in the code	Amount of codings
<i>Total Codings in Part V</i>	77
General Practices Dealing With Info	0
Learning / Collaboration	4
Lifecycle Management Of Information	0
Safety	6
Data Quality / Cleaning	2
Search / Acquisition / Retrieval / Scraping	11
Archiving / Deletion	4

Data Collection	5
Data Storage	8
Versioning	5
Backups	4
Validation	3
Information Management Fundamentals	0
Tools	12
Folder Structures	8
Meta Information / Documentation / Logging	3
File / Folder Names	2

4.2 Evaluation of the Code System

The following sections will focus on evaluating and highlighting the parts of the code system directly related to answering the research questions: parts I, II, and III. An in-depth evaluation, including Part IV and Part V, can be found in Appendix sections 9.6 to 9.10.

4.3 Part I: Challenges Dealing with Large Information Collections

4.3.1 Out of Control

The subjects share common challenges in the flow of information (in and out of their personal information spaces) that are out of their control due to client practices and internal processes: A recurring issue is the clients' limited understanding of data security, particularly with cloud storage, which results in reluctance to embrace these technologies (Subject 3). The subjects also struggle with complex and non-standard folder structures from clients and internal sources, which hampers data navigation and delays project completion (subjects three, eight, and seven). Moreover, these complex structures often lead to communication breakdowns, as subjects frequently need clarification from project managers, further stalling progress (Subject 8). Additionally, deciphering the correct file versions from numerous possibilities poses an intellectual challenge, sometimes more so than the volume of data itself (Subject 6). The difficulty in understanding the reasoning behind specific organizational data structures is another time-consuming aspect, as the logic is not always apparent (Subject 7). Finally, issues with incorrect file types or formats necessitate additional processing steps, contributing to inefficiencies in data handling (Subject 4).

Whether these challenges emerge mainly due to large information collections or the collaborative nature of project management of large information collections will be discussed in Chapter 5.

4.3.2 Data Complexity and Source Management

Subjects 3 and 8 detail the difficulties in managing and finding files within complex projects with multiple data sources, where the fragmentation of information and team dynamics can lead to inefficiencies. Subject 4 deals with organizing vast datasets, where the mentioned risk is information overload and loss without meticulous structuring.

4.3.3 Information Storage and Access Challenges

The subjects describe storage and access challenges for large information collections, including SharePoint's capacity limits (Subjects 7 and 5) that hinder collaboration. Cost is a significant concern (Subjects 7 and 1), with security measures escalating storage expenses, reflecting a balance between affordability and data protection. Data storage planning (Subject 3) is vital to avoid disruptive migrations. Subjects also face tool and format limitations (Subject 4), such as Excel's row cap and JSON's file size limit, which impose constraints on data handling. Scaling issues (Subject 1) arise as data volume grows, increasing management complexity.

"Unser Hauptproblem ist so oder so bei großen Datenmengen der Speicher. Speicher ist teuer, Speicher ist selten und da muss man immer abwägen wie wahrscheinlich ist es, dass man nach Abschluss eines Projekts noch mal irgendwann auf diese Daten zugreifen möchte?" – Subject 1

Accessing large datasets presents additional problems, such as a lack of portability and the need for specialized knowledge and parameterization to access file collections and navigate databases and file servers (Subjects 6 and 3).

„Und wenn ich mir überlege, wie einfach es ist, ChatGPT etwas zu fragen, dann frage ich mich, warum es so verdammt schwierig ist, in meinem Outlook etwas zu finden und warum ich so viel quasi umständlich Computer gerecht parametrisieren muss, wenn doch zu noch viel größeren Datenmengen der Zugang einfacher ist.“ – Subject 6

Subject 3 adds that security protocols can make data retrieval cumbersome, adding to inefficiencies. Further physical challenges are also mentioned, with Subject 2 discussing the impracticality of sharing large Excel files with clients and Subject 9 noting the necessity for specialized storage and VPN access for specific files.

Regarding archiving, Subjects 1 and 7 discuss the difficulties in retrieving data when needed, the implications of archiving strategies on data access, and the complications arising from data ownership

and physical storage locations. These insights point to the delicate balance required in archiving to ensure data remains accessible for future use.

4.3.4 Organizational and Collaborative Challenges

The subjects outline several organizational and collaborative challenges in managing large information collections. Subject 6 emphasizes the need for clarity and overview, as manual file inspection becomes impractical with large volumes, necessitating scripts for basic tasks. Subject 4 adds that the complexity of large datasets, like OpenStreetMap's extensive size (144 GB), complicates understanding the data, often requiring additional processing. Subject 8 discusses the difficulty in identifying key files within large collections for future use. Subject 3 notes the challenge of predicting all outcomes and the possibility of strategy shifts from new insights or colleague input. This unpredictability necessitates adaptable and shared organizational systems.

Data protection concerns Subject 3, who handles large amounts of sensitive data that sometimes demands physical transfer due to security concerns.

Time constraints are highlighted by 2, who illustrates that tasks like transposing rows with columns in Excel can be time-consuming without scripting. Subject 5 points out that while processing large datasets is not the issue, the time it takes is critical due to client deadlines. Subject 4 emphasizes that working with large data requires patience.

Collaboration issues include the inefficiency of sharing vast data through SharePoint (mentioned broadly), the need for strategic data sharing to avoid system overload, and managing data across various platforms. The importance of structured file organization, clear naming conventions, and avoiding characters that cause errors is also noted, affecting how, where, and by whom data is accessed and stored.

4.3.5 Technical and Processing Challenges

The subjects identify technical and processing challenges when dealing with large data sets, necessitating specialized skills for data manipulation. Subject 6 speaks of the need for expertise in scripting to handle complex data structures. Subject 2 illustrates this using Python for tasks such as manually transposing rows and columns, which would be impractical. Subject 4 notes the difficulty with specific file types like JSON or Parquet, which require special tools to access.

Data cleaning is another hurdle, as Subjects 2 and 4 emphasize the complexity of identifying and correcting errors within large data sets, especially from third-party sources.

“Data Cleaning ist gerade bei großen oder riesigen Datensätzen natürlich ein unglaublich heikles Thema. Gerade wenn wir Datensätze bekommen, die jetzt und das ist, tatsächlich auch bei Drittanbietern, wo wir Daten kaufen, dass es teilweise so ist, dass die Daten nicht vollständig sind, die Daten fehlerhaft sind, die Daten im Format falsch sind oder ein Format ein Problem gibt bei den Daten, dass die Formatierung dann nicht passt.“ - Subject 4

Subject 4 also points out the need for a filesystem hierarchy that aligns with programmatic access, where a change in structure can cause disruptions. Subject 3 adds that organizing data across multiple projects can be difficult, particularly when applying a project-based system heuristic.

Tool limitations are highlighted, with Subject 2 referencing Excel's row limitations and the need for alternative solutions such as Python or SQL databases. Subjects 5 and 4 also concur on the limitations of tools like SharePoint and Excel for handling large data volumes. Subject 4 additionally highlights the risk of information overload (as mentioned in 4.3.2).

„Wenn man zum ersten mal auf einen riesigen Datensatz blickt: Was soll ich jetzt machen? So was wie Excel kommt da ja schon sehr schnell an seine Grenzen. Wenn man dann irgendwie eine Excel Formel über 1 Million Zeilen mal ziehen will, dann kann man für eine halbe Stunde warten, bis das durchgeführt ist. Da braucht man dann auch komplett andere Tools. (...) Und selbst da: Was man sieht, sind dann immer 1000 Zeilen auf einmal, aber mehr kann kaum angezeigt oder auch vom Gehirn verarbeitet werden.“ - Subject 4

Time and processing challenges are underscored by Subject 5, which describes a data-intensive project that was time-consuming and costly to process. Subject 4 reiterates that managing large data sets is exponentially more challenging and time-consuming than smaller ones.

„Also im Endeffekt ist es die Arbeit mit großen Daten, egal ob das jetzt die Menge der, oder die Größe der Datei. Es ist ja immer noch mal sozusagen in der Verarbeitung gefühlt zehn Stufen schwieriger, als wenn man jetzt einen kleinen Datensatz hat.“ – Subject 4

Subject 9 recounts an experience where just loading data into a program took 12 hours, illustrating the scale of these challenges.

4.4 Part II: Strategies when Dealing with Large Information Collections

4.4.1 Strategies to Address Organizational and Collaborative Challenges

To tackle the challenges of handling extensive information collections, the subjects employ various strategies:

Subject 6 recommends a clear and intuitive folder structure that is mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive (MECE) for ease of adding and locating files, complemented by standardized naming conventions. For maintaining information hygiene, the subjects suggest regular organization and archiving of data in a central location to avoid clutter.

The need for a clear data structure is underscored in communication and collaboration, with best practices and expert consultations suggested to establish this structure. SharePoint and shared links are tools of choice for collaboration. A commitment to consistent file and folder organization within a team is emphasized, with the necessity of a strategic approach to data storage.

Subject 7 points to the value of proper documentation in reflecting the current state of data, while Subject 3 notes the tendency to overlook documentation due to the demand for rapid results. Subject 7 also advises newcomers to document their learning process thoroughly, and insights from developers' documentation practices, as mentioned by Subject 6, reveal the benefits of well-commented systems. Practical documentation includes describing data storage locations, using descriptive file names, as noted by Subject 3, and writing readme files in data folders, as practiced by Subject 4.

“Man kann, und das haben wir auch schon gemacht, read me's schreiben in Ordnern, dass man dann sagt okay, ich strukturiere meine verschiedenen Ordner und dann in den Ordnern mache ich so, kleine readme's damit die Leute wissen, was sie da finden. Sehr, sehr hilfreich. Das ist sehr hilfreich sogar.” – Subject 4

For learning from others, Subject 7 encourages looking for established best practices before devising new solutions:

“...man rennt, irgendwann von allein in irgendein Problem rein. Und dann würde ich immer stoppen. Und nicht versuchen selber was zu erfinden, sondern würde immer erst mal den Schritt gehen, nach Best Practices zu googeln. Ich würde immer die Annahme tätigen "Hey, das Problem hatten bestimmt schon viele und auch über Jahre hinweg".” - Subject 7.

Subject 8 advocates for professional development courses for those new to large datasets, while Subject 4 also highlights consulting online resources to tackle technical challenges, indicating the value of community knowledge in developing personal strategies for information management.

4.4.2 Strategies for Technical and Processing Challenges

The subjects adopt various strategies to overcome technical and processing challenges in handling vast information collections:

Subject 4 recommends random sampling to manage the impossibility of reviewing entire datasets. This involves examining parts of the dataset at different intervals to ensure data integrity, with checks on column uniformity and data format consistency.

Automation is highlighted by Subject 4 as a critical strategy, deeming manual processing impractical for large volumes of data. They consider automation an essential recommendation for anyone new to the field.

Subject 5 tackles SharePoint's capacity constraints by prioritizing data relevant to the research questions and variables of interest instead of attempting to process all available data. Similarly, Subject 9 suggests setting thresholds for data based on cost and quality to filter out irrelevant information, as in the case of Amazon reviews.

Batching is a multi-faceted strategy utilized by several subjects:

- Subject 6 sees the value in targeted data provision, supplying collaborators with only the necessary data subsets.
- Subject 3 finds working with data subsets functional during the initial conceptual stages to simplify development.
- 2 uses batching to work around software limitations like Excel's row limit by distributing data across multiple files.
- Subject 5 employs batch processing for handling projects with many variables, suggesting individual variable files for more focused analysis.
- Finally, Subject 4 discusses batching in data analysis, dividing millions of data points into smaller segments for sequential handling and analysis.

Collectively, these batching strategies provide a framework for efficiently managing, analyzing, and storing large datasets by breaking them down into more manageable segments.

4.4.3 The Use of Tools as a Strategy

The subjects provide a comprehensive overview of how various externally and internally developed tools help to manage large information collections.

Subject 2 advises on the importance of a balanced approach in using tools for information management and stresses the significance of human oversight in verifying information gathered by automated tools developed with languages like Python. The Subject recommends developing proficiency in Excel and learning coding languages such as Python or SQL for individuals new to managing large datasets. It underscores the essentiality of scripting skills in addressing the complexities of large data volumes.

Regarding using externally developed tools, Subject 7 employs GitHub to organize extensive volumes of code, track issues, and maintain the structure of complex development projects. Subject 4 also uses this tool, highlighting GitHub's role in systematic file storage and providing clear documentation for projects. Subject 8 utilizes Trello to aggregate large amounts of information from various sources into structured project cards, which aids in maintaining clarity and managing information overload. Subject 9 applies the tool Ray for efficiently processing large data collections and handling multiple data requests concurrently to speed up data analysis.

In the realm of internally developed tools, Subject 6 mentions a specialized self-developed document management and workflow system tailored for information annotation tasks. This system includes user-friendly interfaces allowing non-developers to interact with data without coding skills. Subject 2 has developed a Python script to transpose rows and columns in databases, restating the data for a more straightforward analysis of large datasets. Subject 5 has devised a method for saving and loading individual data variables, which enhances the speed and efficiency of data analyses by allowing focus on only the necessary segments of the dataset. Furthermore, Subject 9 supervised the development of a 'Data Aggregator' tool designed to compile data based on specific attributes across nested folder structures.

These strategies underscore adopting existing tools and developing custom solutions for efficient information management. They highlight how these tools can transform data structures and conduct targeted data aggregation, ultimately reducing the complexity and manual effort of managing large volumes of information.

4.4.4 Strategies for Information Storage and Access

The subjects offer a range of strategies to tackle challenges related to searching, accessing, version controlling, and storing and archiving large amounts of information.

Regarding search strategies, Subject 7 suggests using tools with advanced search functionalities to locate information based on keywords, file types, and other criteria while acknowledging that folder structures and names might not accurately reflect the contents. Subject 3 sees semantic search technology, which understands the meaning behind words, as the future of search. Subject 9 emphasizes a consistent folder structure to enhance the search process and avoid chaos.

Subject 6 advocates using cloud services for access strategies to enable secure and remote data access, overcoming traditional physical limitations. This Subject also practices selective data access, providing collaborators with just the necessary subsets of data. Subject 8 organizes project information using tools like Trello for efficient retrieval, and Subject 4 ensures continuous data accessibility during and after automated processes. Subject 9 implements distributed computing to drastically reduce the time required for data access and processing.

Regarding version control in tools, Subject 1 discusses how it facilitates easy modification of files while keeping a record of changes, though it can lead to duplicate files and increased storage needs. Subject 4 recommends incorporating dates or version numbers in file names to track changes and avoid the deletion of old files—Subject 5 highlights using GitHub for version control in projects with multiple collaborators.

The strategies for storage and archiving are diverse. Subjects 6, 8, and 5 discuss cloud-based solutions and server-based storage to manage large information collections and address capacity issues like those in SharePoint. Subjects 1 and 4 balance the cost of storage with accessibility, favoring archiving over deletion and emphasizing the importance of automated data handling and backup. Subject 9 prefers structured nested folders for organized storage and local server usage for faster data transfer despite the growing trend toward cloud computing. Furthermore, Subject 1 describes archiving as a strategy to transfer information from SharePoint to local drives, which, while cheaper and offering more space, presents challenges in access and collaboration.

Overall, these strategies illustrate the varied approaches adopted by the subjects to ensure that large volumes of data are securely stored, efficiently organized, and readily accessible when needed.

4.4.5 Foundational Strategies

The subjects' discussion on managing large information collections centers on the necessity of a structured approach and meticulous planning and preparation.

Subject 7 advises against the creation of overly complex systems. They suggest utilizing established solutions and maintaining straightforward and adaptable systems to evolving data handling methods.

Subject 6 emphasizes clearly defining and anticipating problems, especially when navigating different software and systems. Subject 8 underlines the significance of initiating a transparent organizational system, advocating for specific folders for each project while ensuring consistency and flexibility for potential structural enhancements.

The consistency in naming and structuring files is crucial, as highlighted by Subject 4 and Subject 1. This approach facilitates easier understanding and processing for both humans and computers. Subject 5 recommends testing systems on a small scale before scaling up, mainly when there are cost implications. Subject 1 focuses on creating reproducible structures crucial for efficient information management. Subject 3 observes that a structured approach increases productivity and minimizes the frustration of lengthy information searches. Similarly, Subject 9 agrees that a structured system is essential to prevent chaos and ensure easy navigation, especially when revisiting data.

“Auch wenn du 10.000 Files manuell checken möchtest, Du brauchst Struktur. Struktur ist das Key Schlüsselwort hier. Je mehr du dokumentierst, alles schön und so weiter. Aber Struktur und Hierarchie, sind Disziplinen, die wir haben müssen.”– Subject 9

Regarding planning and preparation, Subject 6 suggests performing dry runs before significant operations like moving large folders or merging tables. This approach helps to anticipate potential errors in resource-intensive actions.

"Und zum Start lieber erst planen und lieber einmal "dry run". Also konkretes Beispiel: Wenn ich ein Ordner von links nach rechts kopiere auf SharePoint, dann fasse ich den an und zieh den rüber. Aber wenn ich irgendwie remote Terabytes bewege oder irgendwas in der Tabelle merge oder so, dann mache ich lieber einmal einen "dry run"... Weil gerade wenn Sachen compute intensiv sind, zeitintensiv sind, sind Fehler oft nur mit manueller Arbeit unter extremem Aufwand "zurückdrehbar".“– Subject 6

Subject 3 stresses the need for a thoughtfully defined systematic structure in organizing folders, considering the nature of the data, including aspects like anonymization and temporal factors. Subject 2 recommends acquiring proficiency in Excel and scripting languages such as Python or SQL to tackle the complexities of large data sets effectively. Subject 5 emphasizes hypothesis-driven analysis, ensuring data exploration leads to significant and relevant findings. Subject 4 points out the necessity of thorough data cleaning and the development of contingency plans for any processing issues that might arise.

These strategies highlight the role of starting with simple, straightforward systems for file organization,

maintaining consistency in data handling, and preparing thoroughly with systematic structures and skills in essential data tools. They underline the importance of structured analytical approaches and backup plans to ensure reliable data analysis and workflows continue smoothly despite potential challenges.

4.4.6 Strategies for Information Complexity and Source Management

In their discussion on strategies for managing information complexity and source management, the subjects provide insights into various file and folder management aspects, emphasizing the importance of structured, adaptable, and context-dependent approaches.

Subject 3 highlights the significance of having a structured and consistent naming convention for files and folders, emphasizing that such a system facilitates automated scripts and interactions with machines by integrating metadata into the file names. This approach is echoed by Subjects 1 and 4, who focus on standardizing file names to ensure machine readability, advocating for uniform naming patterns that avoid special characters and spaces to ensure seamless processing by software.

In the realm of version control, Subject 6 discusses the shift to automated systems like SharePoint for versioning files, underscoring the need for users to ensure that final versions of files are accurately named. Subject 8 contributes to this discussion by highlighting the practice of starting file names with dates to aid in sorting and locating files within folder structures, serving as a simple yet effective versioning method. Similarly, Subject 4 emphasizes the importance of including dates or version numbers in file names to maintain a historical record of files, enabling tracking of changes over time and preserving older versions.

Subject 8 also discusses the importance of flexible adaptation as information collections grow, noting the need for regular restructuring and optimization of systems, especially as projects become more complex and standard folder structures may no longer suffice.

Further, the subjects delve into the nuances of folder structuring based on context. Subject 3, in the context of the medical field, stresses sorting data by entities and considering time components while ensuring proper anonymization. The Subject underscores the need for a systematic organization to facilitate easy information location, with the chosen folder structure dependent on the specific use case. Similarly, Subject 5 explores different approaches to structuring data, such as horizontally or vertically organizing variables, based on the intended use and the software used.

The importance of early data structuring is emphasized by Subjects 3, 9, and 8, who suggest defining formats and encouraging clients to deliver data in specific ways to avoid extensive restructuring later.

They stress the significance of having a disciplined and structured approach from the beginning for effective information management.

Subject 8 introduces the concept of data zones, discussing strategies for creating specific folder structures and sorting data by content or usage. Subject 9 further elaborates on this, introducing different zones for data, such as raw and processed data, and a golden zone for high-quality data ready for database use.

Finally, the subjects also emphasize the importance of personal folder structures and standardized approaches. Subject 3 uses a prefix-based filing system for systematic project and task management, while Subject 8 mirrors personal project folders across different storage platforms for consistency. Subject 1 outlines a standardized structure categorizing files into different areas for administrative, storage, working, and delivery purposes. Subject 4 details an organized structure for coding workflows, separating files for variables, functions, and main execution.

Subject 7 discusses a folder structure following best practices but acknowledges the lack of fixed standards for folder structures. Subject 1, meanwhile, points out that within their team, project managers can decide on individualized file naming conventions, but the overall project structure remains unchanged, emphasizing the advantages of a standardized folder structure for easy access and onboarding of new team members.

These varied strategies reflect the subjects' emphasis on creating structured, flexible, and context-dependent systems for managing large information collections, ensuring efficiency, clarity, and ease of access in information management processes.

4.5 Part III: Transferability of strategies

The subjects present divergent viewpoints on the transferability of information management strategies from large to small information collections. Some advocate for the applicability of these strategies to smaller information collections, while others raise concerns about potential inefficiencies and overcomplexity in smaller-scale contexts.

Advocates for transferability emphasize several key advantages. Subject 7 identifies version control and branching as beneficial for managing data of any size, highlighting these practices as crucial for safe experimentation and efficient tracking of edits. The same Subject also recognizes the potential of collaborative, shared spaces to enhance small-scale information management, a concept borrowed from the tech industry. This includes integrating project management with file tracking for a more cohesive approach.

Subject 6 suggests that methods for querying large databases, such as user-friendly interfaces, could be

effectively applied to smaller information systems. This replication would aim to simplify search and retrieval processes. Additionally, Subject 6 underlines the importance of being conscious of data storage, regardless of the dataset's size, to ensure proper data handling practices.

Subject 3 underscores that a systematic organizational approach benefits data volume, aiding efficient collaboration and onboarding. The principles of script reusability are also highlighted by Subjects 2 and 4, who note that scripts and automated processes developed for large datasets can save time and maintain process documentation even for smaller datasets.

„Also das, was man bei dem kleinen Datensatz macht, könnte man beim großen Datensatz wahrscheinlich nicht machen. Andersherum geht es aber super und meistens hat man dann auch noch Learnings und Automatismen, die man dann einfach mitnehmen kann und die dann auch helfen beim Verarbeiten. Ja, also es schadet nie, sozusagen diese Strategien einmal zu entwickeln und dann kann man die sozusagen für alles weiter benutzen.“ – Subject 4

Subject 5 further supports this view by suggesting that establishing structured workflows can lead to increased efficiency in project execution as repeated processes become more familiar and faster.

On the other hand, some Subjects express reservations about the direct application of these strategies to smaller datasets. Subjects 8 and 5 point out that complex organizational structures or extensive versioning systems may become unnecessary and cumbersome for smaller projects. They argue that simpler approaches might be more appropriate to avoid overcomplication. Subjects 5 and 1 caution against overengineering solutions, such as elaborate folder structures or excessive version control, which may not be justified in smaller-scale projects due to the mismatch between the effort and the benefits.

Subjects 2 and 9 emphasize that the time and resources required to implement strategies like writing scripts or setting up distributed computing environments might not be justifiable for smaller datasets. The marginal gains in efficiency may not outweigh the investment. Subjects 1 and 9 discuss non-scalability issues, arguing that strategies for managing large files, like avoiding duplication and optimizing resources, might not be as critical for smaller files.

„Das heißt ja, die Effektivität ist da. Aber wenn du das nicht richtig benötigst, das heißt, wenn die Datensätze kleiner sind, ja dann wird der Aufwand auch größer sein, dass du alle diese Sachen machst und am Ende, okay, statt zehn Sekunden brauchst du eine Sekunde zum Verarbeiten. Ja, der Zeit-Gewinn ist nicht so groß.“ – Subject 9

They also note that infrastructure designed for high-efficiency computing may not scale down

effectively for smaller datasets.

In summary, while there is agreement on the broad applicability and potential benefits of certain information management strategies, there is also a recognition that the specific context and scale of information collections should guide the decision on whether to implement these strategies. The subjects' insights suggest a nuanced approach, advocating for the adaptation of strategies from large-scale information management to smaller contexts but with careful consideration of the distinct needs and limitations of smaller datasets.

5 Discussion

5.1 Reiterating the Research Problem and Major Results

While the PIM practices, behaviors, and strategies of individuals in varied work contexts have been the subject of extensive research, there remains a noticeable gap in studies specifically targeting the PIM practices, challenges, and strategies of individuals who handle extensive information collections. Our research directly addressed this gap. This study draws upon diverse perspectives by conducting and thoroughly analyzing nine in-depth interviews with professionals from two companies. These individuals vary not only in their organizational roles but also in their educational backgrounds and years of experience in the field.

Our study's most significant finding is the identification of unique challenges and respective strategies in managing large information collections, such as the need for advanced tools and processing skills and tailored collaboration strategies.

These challenges and strategies, along with a broader view of their general practices, offer valuable insights into the field of PIM, especially in contexts dealing with large volumes of information.

Further insights into these general practices and a detailed exploration of the identified challenges and strategies are presented in the results section of this thesis, and an in-depth presentation of the results can be found in the Appendix.

5.2 Interpretation of Results and Comparison with Previous Research

This research has corroborated the initial hypothesis presented in the introduction: managing extensive information collections presents a unique set of challenges and necessitates distinct strategies, primarily due to the sheer volume of information. These challenges are qualitatively distinct from those encountered in less information-intensive settings.

The collaborative nature of working within vast information spaces introduces its own set of challenges. These challenges often exceed the capabilities of an individual and require collaborative solutions, such as seeking help from colleagues or implementing data handling plans devised by more experienced team members. This aspect underscores the importance of teamwork and collective problem-solving in managing large-scale information.

5.2.1 Challenges

This section will discuss and answer our research question regarding the challenges of dealing with extensive information collections.

We observe overlaps and noteworthy distinctions in comparing our findings with existing literature. While Alon et al. (2019) highlighted divergence of information and overloaded information spaces as general PIM challenges for knowledge workers, our study extends these concepts. We identified fragmentation, akin to divergence, and information flood, paralleling overloaded spaces. However, our research goes further, uncovering unique challenges associated with large information collections.

Thematic clustering of our results has revealed patterns in the challenges encountered. The first cluster relates predominantly to the nature of project-based consulting work in the context of working with large information collection:

Time Constraints: Highlighted by three participants, this challenge reflects the pressure of waiting for data processing in time-sensitive project environments. For example, Subject 5 described the tension between processing time and the need to present results to clients.

Data Protection: Also mentioned by three subjects, this issue becomes particularly acute with sensitive data. Subject 3 detailed the necessity of storing large data volumes on encrypted external hard drives, acknowledging the perceived risks associated with server or cloud storage, as reflected in recent literature (Alouffi et al., 2021).

Collaboration Difficulties: Encountered by four Subjects, this challenge arises when multiple individuals work on the same file, potentially losing information due to conflicting versions. This challenge has already been observed in academic institutions (Perrier et al., 2017).

Feeling Out of Control: This challenge, noted by five Subjects, involves navigating and identifying accurate and relevant information within large information collections from external sources or colleagues. This challenge is previously mentioned by McDonald and Levine-Clark as highlighted in

the Literature Review in Chapter 2 (McDonald & Levine-Clark, 2017).

In addition to the challenges related to the nature of project-based work, our research has identified several issues primarily attributed to the sheer volume of the file collections:

Tool Limitations: The constraints of commonly used tools like Excel, as expressed by our Subjects, emphasize the necessity for more robust, flexible data management solutions in large-scale settings. This result aligns with the growing acknowledgment in the field about the limitations of traditional tools when handling massive data sets, echoing the sentiments of researchers who advocate for more advanced and adaptable technologies (Raubenheimer, 2017).

Special Skills Needed: Special skills, particularly in scripting and data management, underline a crucial skill gap in the current workforce. This observation supports the argument for more targeted education and training programs in data science and analytics, as highlighted in the literature (Fajaryati et al., 2020; *Quantifying the UK Data Skill Gap - Summary Version*, o. J.; *Tech Looks to Analytics Skills to Bolster Its Workforce*, o. J.).

Time and Processing Challenges: The difficulties in processing large volumes of data highlight the need for more efficient data processing strategies and tools. This challenge, commonly faced by professionals in our study, points to an opportunity to develop new methodologies and software to handle large-scale data more effectively.

Storage Challenges: Our findings regarding storage concerns reflect a broader issue in the era of big data. The costs and logistical challenges of storing large data volumes are becoming increasingly critical, necessitating innovative data storage and retrieval approaches (Do et al., 2020; Ferguson, 2012).

Clarity and Overview: The challenge of maintaining clarity amidst large file collections underscores the importance of developing more intuitive and user-friendly data organization systems. This challenge is particularly relevant in today's context, where data overload is a common issue, and aligns with recent discussions in PIM and/or usability research on enhancing data navigability and user interface design (Iñiguez-Jarrín et al., 2020).

5.2.2 Strategies

This section will discuss and answer our main research question "What strategies do individuals employ to manage and handle vast amounts of information in a workplace setting?".

During this study, we have identified several effective strategies employed by professionals in managing extensive information collections. These strategies address the unique challenges and offer insights into managing information efficiently in high-volume contexts.

A key strategy observed aligns with Alon's 2019 concept of "Decentralizing PIM." As exemplified by Subject 6, this approach involves delegating the task of filtering information to team members. Such a strategy enables managers to avoid the intricate process of sifting through large amounts of information, instead relying on their team to properly structure and provide necessary information.

Additionally, discarding personal information, another concept drawn from Alon's 2019 research, emerged as a common theme among participants. This practice is crucial for minimizing clutter and focusing on critical information in environments where information volume is substantial.

Like Alon's findings, our study also revealed a significant inclination towards un-fragmentation of information. For instance, Subject 6 described utilizing cloud-based servers for data storage, facilitating easier and more secure access to data from various locations. This approach effectively reduces the limitations on data accessibility and is a move towards centralizing and organizing large datasets. Furthermore, the need for integrated information and knowledge management, as discussed in a 2002 study, resonates with the contemporary strategies identified in this research, underscoring a consistent need across decades (Bokma, 2002).

Moreover, new strategies were identified, such as splitting large information collections into batches, implementing nested folder structures, and maintaining detailed documentation for folder organization. These methods enhance individual efficiency and play a vital role in improving collaborative efforts, providing a clear and structured approach to information management.

5.2.3 Importance for Other Contexts

This section will discuss and answer our research question, whether these identified strategies can benefit a broader audience.

It is important to note that while certain strategies, like structured documentation, are universally applicable and beneficial even for smaller information collections, others, particularly those involving advanced technical solutions like distributed computing, may not be as suitable. When applied to less extensive information collections, these more complex strategies can lead to over-engineering, emphasizing the need to carefully consider the cost-benefit ratio in different information management scenarios.

Finally, the results of this study suggest that the insights and strategies derived from professionals managing vast information collections offer valuable lessons that extend beyond similar high-volume contexts. These strategies can inform and enhance practices across various information management scenarios, contributing significantly to PIM and information literacy.

This study's unanimous agreement among all Subjects underscored the importance of an early structured and planned approach in managing large information collections and building folder structures. This consensus highlights the foundational role of organization in effective information management.

5.2.4 Collaborative Challenges and Strategies

While Subject 6 suggests a collaborative "divide and conquer" strategy (where tasks are distributed among group members) to lessen PIM challenges, sharing information collections often has the reverse effect, as highlighted by McDonald and Levine-Clark (McDonald & Levine-Clark, 2017).

Interestingly, our analysis revealed a dichotomy between personalized and standardized approaches to folder structuring, echoing complexities identified in the literature. Subject 8, for instance, employed a personalized approach by mirroring project folders across multiple platforms like Trello, OneDrive, and local storage. In contrast, Subject 7's methodology leaned towards applying industry standards or best practices, using a generic 'Data' folder and a 'SAC' or 'Bin' folder. While less personalized, this standardized approach provides an intuitive and broadly understandable framework for different users, illustrating the trade-off between personalized efficiency and standardized accessibility. These results align with findings in the literature, that individuals can differ substantially in how they approach keeping, organizing, and managing information (Berlin et al., 1993; McDonald & Levine-Clark, 2017).

The varied strategies subjects adopt underscore the intricacies of information management in professional settings. Personalized strategies offer tailored solutions catering to individual workflows but may pose challenges in collaborative environments due to their uniqueness. On the other hand, standardized structures, though possibly less optimized for individual preferences, enhance accessibility and understanding in team-based or multi-stakeholder projects.

Indeed, collaborating to resolve these issues frequently requires a careful negotiating process (Capra et al., 2014; Wulf, 1997), since categorization affects every person in the shared space, and the tools that are employed to perform these activities don't offer pre-established conventions for tasks like organizing a project's files and folders (Mark & Prinz, 1997). Interestingly, our results introduce agents to the negotiation process that have not been yet reported in the literature, namely external clients or technical

characteristics (such as web structures) that pre-define and limit certain structures in the group information management process.

For practitioners in information management, these findings highlight the need to balance personalized efficiency with standardized structures to foster effective collaboration. Future research might explore developing flexible information management systems that accommodate individual preferences and standardization requirements and look at all the agents in the process.

Moreover, similar to the study by Khoo et al. and Alon et al., our research sheds light on various folder structure and heuristics approaches (Alon et al., 2019; Khoo et al., 2007). Subject 8, for example, discusses creating a distinct folder structure for each project and a Trello card for each task. Subjects 8 and 4 emphasize the importance of having specific structures for different data types, such as raw, processed, and classified data, sorted by content or usage. Subject 9 introduces the concept of data zones, delineating areas like raw data zones, processed data zones, and a golden zone for high-quality data ready for database use. A recurring theme among Subjects was the importance of integrity in team collaboration. Aligning on the same folder structures and rules, and providing extensive documentation, was deemed more critical than individual preferences for structure. The emphasis was on adopting and integrating a structured approach within the team rather than whose structure was adopted.

These varying strategies reflect personal preferences and influence the ease of re-finding information in shared spaces, a challenge highlighted by Bergman et al. and others (Bergman et al., 2014; Dourish et al., 1999; McDonald & Levine-Clark, 2017).

5.3 Limitations and Avenues for Further Research

This study is not without its limitations, namely the research is limited to the answers the subjects have given. The results are based on Subjects working at two separate but intellectually related companies in the information economy and may not represent all PIM contexts.

Future research could explore the applicability of identified PIM strategies in various professional domains to assess their universality. It's also important to clarify the distinctions between PIM, File Management, and Document Management for more targeted strategies. Investigating the impact of different file structures and types on PIM and extending the research to group information management could provide deeper insights into the collaborative nature of large file collection management.

Exploring different heuristics participants chose for their specific work contexts could yield valuable insights and potential blueprints for information management, literacy, and tool development. Further

research into the custom tools professionals have developed for their information management also seems promising to offer intriguing perspectives for software developers in PIM and File Management.

6 Conclusion

This thesis has explored PIM strategies and challenges among professionals managing extensive information collections. This research has offered a nuanced understanding of large-scale information management's unique challenges and strategies by conducting in-depth interviews with experts from diverse organizational backgrounds.

Subjects vary in the types of information and sources of information they deal with. Their challenges are also multi-faceted in their dimensions including storage and access difficulties, organizational and collaborative challenges, and technical and processing challenges.

Equally diverse are the strategies developed by these individuals for effective information management. The study highlights the importance of planning and structured approaches, comprehensive documentation, the deployment of internally and externally developed tools, and learning from others when working with large information collections.

The research further delved into the transferability of these strategies devised for large information collections to manage smaller collections. It points out that while some strategies are universally applicable, others need contextual adaptations, underscoring the importance of tailoring PIM approaches to specific information management environments.

This thesis contributes significantly to the academic discourse on PIM and serves as a practical guide for professionals in the field. It highlights the need for continued development and refinement of PIM strategies and tools to meet the dynamic requirements of modern information environments.

In conclusion, this thesis enriches our understanding of PIM in contexts of large information collections. It lays a foundation for future research, particularly in developing more effective and adaptable information management systems and literacy programs. The study highlights the critical role of practical, collaborative, and flexible approaches in PIM, offering insights that can significantly inform and transform the practices of information management, thereby making a substantial contribution to both the theoretical and practical realms of PIM.

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8 Statement of Independent Work

I hereby confirm that this thesis was written independently by myself without the use of any sources beyond those cited, and all passages and ideas taken from other sources are cited accordingly.

9 Appendix

9.1 Acknowledgment

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9.2 Use of PIM Terms in the Literature

9.2.1 PIM Practice, Practices, and Activities

Starting with "activities", Jones provides a framework for analyzing PIM *activities*, which he divides into three components: "keeping", "refinding", and "management activities". "Keeping" refers to the *activities* that contribute to creating and maintaining a personal information space. This could include

saving documents, organizing files, or setting up systems for future retrieval. "Refinding" refers to how people retrieve items from their personal information space, which could involve searching, browsing, or using specific retrieval methods. "Management activities" encompass people's actions to organize and update their information space, such as reorganizing files, updating stored information, or managing the overall structure of their information space. Meta-level *activities* are referred to by Jones as activities such as: "maintenance and organization, making (overall) sense of an information collection, managing privacy and security, or measuring and assessing the effectiveness of strategies and supporting tools." (Teevan et al., 2008). McDonald and Levine-Clark further elaborate that "Implicit in each of these activity types is an effort to make sense of and use the available information" (McDonald & Levine-Clark, 2017).

Sedghi et al. note that PIM refers to the tools and *activities* used to save and retrieve personal information for future use (Sedghi et al., 2015). Divya and Sudhier emphasized that PIM refers to a set of *activities* that a person performs to acquire, create, store, organize, maintain, retrieve, use, and distribute personal information for different purposes (Divya & Sudhier, 2016). Additionally, according to Bergmann, PIM refers to the *activity* of storing personal information items for later retrieval (Jones, 2007a). Bergmann defines PIM solely around the activities, while Jones also mentions the term practice in his definition of PIM.

Koltay interprets Jones's definition of PIM ("*Personal Information Management (PIM) refers to both the practice and the study of the activities...*" (Koltay, 2017)) as follows: "Accordingly (to Jones definition), PIM practices consist of the following activities: finding information, and keeping this information for future re-use." (Alon et al., 2017). It becomes apparent that the practice of PIM involves several *practices* or *activities*. Evidently, within the PIM realm, the terms "practices" and "activities" are often used synonymously, suggesting that they bear analogous meanings in this context.

9.2.2 PIM Strategies

Above, we have stated that, according to Jones, meta-level activities can be used to "assess the effectiveness of strategies". However, what are strategies in the context of PIM?

In PIM research, "strategies" often refer to individuals' broader approaches or plans to manage their personal information. They are more general than the practices and define the guidelines that help people cope with information management challenges. According to Alon et al., high-level strategies are the courses of action people develop to keep, manage, and retrieve information items. These strategies point to the capability of knowledge workers to innovate and think of new PIM solutions that may decrease information management challenges and increase efficiency. For example, one strategy could be how

individuals decide what information to keep and what to discard. Another strategy could be how to organize and store information, and yet another could be how to ensure the privacy and security of personal information. These strategies are about managing information and, for instance, managing the stress related to information overload. According to Alon et al., the mastery of high-level PIM strategies becomes more essential as personal information spaces become fragmented and overloaded. Therefore, high-level strategies should be considered an integral part of PIM literacy, alongside routine PIM practices (Alon et al., 2019).

Interestingly, Majid et al. define the whole area of PIM as “a personal strategy to acquire/create, maintain (organize/store/manage privacy and security), and use information”. Strategies could include decisions about what information to keep and what to discard, how to organize and store information, and how to ensure the privacy and security of personal information (Majid et al., 2013).

In conclusion, strategies in PIM research provide an overarching framework that guides individuals' PIM practices and activities.

9.2.3 PIM Behavior

Lastly, in the context of PIM research, "behavior" typically refers to the observable actions or patterns of actions that individuals exhibit when managing their personal information. This can encompass a wide range of actions, from how individuals search for and acquire information to how they organize, store, retrieve, and use it. For instance, in the study by Diekema and Olsen, they discuss teacher information behavior in the context of PIM, suggesting that the context of their workplace drives the behavior of teachers in managing their personal information. This implies that behavior in PIM can be influenced by external factors such as the environment or context in which the individual operates (Diekema & Olsen, 2014).

Another study states that PIM behavior can be influenced by various factors, including individuals' personality traits, education level, IT skills, familiarity with PIM tools, and the type and frequency of tasks they undertake (Greifeneder, 2023). These findings align with Professor Elke Greifeneder's teachings in the course “Human Information Behavior”; a key takeaway of the course was that Information Behavior depends on the context and situation: Time, Place, Importance, Relevance, and Availability are all dimensions that influence information behavior. Additionally, Information Behavior does change: One-time surveys can tell us little about behavior five years from now - people's lives change (Greifeneder, 2023).

In conclusion, "behavior" in PIM research refers to the observable actions and patterns of actions

individuals exhibit while managing their personal information. It is a broad term encompassing a wide range of actions. It can be influenced by various factors, including the individual's environment, tools, and personal preferences and habits.

9.3 Inductive Category Formation by Kuckartz

The process of inductive category formation in qualitative research is a methodical approach that allows researchers to derive categories directly from their data, reflecting the nuanced nature of qualitative analysis. Kuckartz proposes a detailed six-step process for inductive coding that ensures categories are systematically developed while retaining the qualitative richness of the data.

1. **Purpose Definition:** The research begins with an exploratory and descriptive aim to investigate the challenges and strategies involved in managing large volumes of information. The goal is to identify and quantify the most prominent challenges and frequently employed strategies. The initial categories are derived from the interview guide, which sets the stage for more nuanced subcategories that will emerge from the first coding run.
2. **Determining Category Type and Level of Abstraction:** Categories can be thematic, evaluative, or analytical, and they should be chosen to align with the research's objectives. The initial segments of the interview guide are designed to elicit objective responses, such as descriptions of work and information sources. In contrast, subsequent sections aim to provoke thematic responses related to organization, challenges, and strategies in information management. Evaluative responses are anticipated in discussions about the transferability of strategies, potentially leading to subcategories assessing the feasibility of transferring strategies to different contexts. As the research progresses, analytical categories may emerge, synthesizing themes into broader patterns.
3. **Familiarization with Data and Segment Determination:** A crucial decision in the coding process is determining the unit of analysis—whether it be specific terms, sentences, or paragraphs. Using MAXQDA, the researcher opts to encode sense units, which are complex statements that retain their meaning outside their original context, thus facilitating subsequent analysis.
4. **Sequential Text Processing and Category Formation:** The coding is an iterative process, with the researcher working through the texts line-by-line, assigning existing categories or forming new ones. The interim coding system developed in MAXQDA visualizes the progress, showing

a range of categorized sense units, each tagged with a code corresponding to a thematic, objective-based, or evaluative category.

5. **Systematizing and Organizing the Category System:** Reorganization is necessary when category formation reaches a saturation point. Grouping similar categories and creating a hierarchical system simplifies the process, typically refining it to ten main categories with up to ten sub-categories each. Following the initial coding, the system expanded with various inductive codes. The researcher then refined these codes, ultimately leaving the main categories as overarching titles for more detailed subcodes. Using MAXQDA 2022, the coding was streamlined by grouping similar codes, forming new superordinate categories, and ensuring coherence and relevance to the research question as recommended by Kuckartz (Kuckartz, 2022).

6. **Finalizing the Category System and Defining Categories:** After multiple iterations through steps 4 and 5, the category system will eventually reach a saturation point, with a few new categories appearing. While the system is mainly set, it remains open to adjustments based on further data analysis. Categories must be distinct and communicate clearly, with detailed definitions and illustrative excerpts prepared for presentation. Each category was then clearly defined and exemplified with representative citations for clarity in later stages. The final code system with citations can be found in Appendix 9.4.

This methodical approach to category formation ensures that the resulting coding system is comprehensive and adaptable to the evolving nature of the data. The researcher remains deeply engaged with the material, allowing for an organic yet structured analysis that can yield rich and nuanced insights into the complexities of managing large volumes of information.

9.4 List of Codes with Description and Text Examples

Code list	Description and example	Amount of codings
Code system		371
Contextual Insights	Description: This analytical category denotes interview passages that provide contextual information of a Subject. Sub-Code Examples: "Info Sources" or "Info Types"	0
Info Sources	Description: This objective category denotes interview passages that provide contextual information of a Subject's source of information	14

	<p>Example: "Das sind entweder selbst erstellte Datenbanken, also über gescrapte Daten, über eingekaufte Daten, über öffentlich verfügbare Daten oder über gelieferte Daten. Also es kann alles vom Kunden geliefert, aus öffentlichen Quellen gesammelte oder auch selbst erstellt sein." (Subject 1 , Pos. 13)</p>	
Info Types	<p>Description: This objective category denotes interview passages that provide contextual information of a Subject's used information types</p> <p>Example: "Ich habe zum Beispiel größere Sammlungen von CSV Dateien. Das ist mit das häufigste, was man eigentlich antrifft. Das sind zum Beispiel Abrechnungsdaten von Mobilfunkanbietern. Das sind AuchTechnische Logs von Mobilfunk Antennen.Das sind Datenbank Auszüge aus Verwaltungs Datenbanken. Datenbank Auszüge aus CRM Systemen. Und früher, in der Vergangenheit war es halt noch ganz viel große, Öffentlich zugängliche Bildersammlung, um Modelle zu trainieren." (Subject 7 , Pos. 12)</p>	7
Main Task: focus on info	<p>Description: This objective category denotes interview passages that provide contextual information of a Subject's main work description with a focus on the role of information.</p> <p>Example: "Es ist recht vielschichtig. Es sind an bezahlten Kunden Projekten bis hin zu kleinen internen Themen ist alles dabei. Und das bedeutet, es sind viele verschiedene Themenblöcke, Aufgabenbereiche oder Projekte, wo überall entsprechend Informationen kommen, sei es mündlich, per Teams, per Email während Calls, vielleicht sogar eine SMS oder eine WhatsApp Nachricht, je nachdem. Und dann natürlich auch zusätzlich zu Informationen noch richtige Datensätze bis hin zu Datenbanken, die dann halt alle eine Rolle spielen für die einzelnen Projekte und Aufgaben. " (Subject 8 , Pos. 47)</p>	11
Main Task	<p>Description: This objective category denotes interview passages that provide contextual information of a Subject's main work description.</p> <p>Example: "Ich bin als Partner einer Unternehmensberatung in drei Rollen unterwegs. Ich bin zum einen Verkäufer. Ich trage einen Teil des Umsatzes in dieser Firma. Ich bin zum Zweiten Teil verantwortlich für das Management dieser Firma. Begleite intern eine Rolle als HR Verantwortlicher. Und das Dritte ist, dass ich operativ in Projekten als Unternehmensberater weiter tätig bin. Das ist eine ganz grobe Aufteilung." (Subject 6 , Pos. 3)</p>	10

Info Route	<p>Description: This objective category denotes interview passages that provide contextual information on how the information ended up in a Subject's personal information space, hereby is the focus on the actual route of information (vs. the source of information).</p> <p>Example: "Aber wenn es um wirklich große Datenmengen geht, dann ist Email raus. Dann. Dann geht das von von klassisch FTP Server bis hin zu vom Kunden betriebenen Daten Drehscheiben, also dedizierten Austausch Systemen. Oft ist das dann halt auch nur irgendwie glorifiziert FTP mit mit Klimbim und ums Management rundherum. Aber wir haben auch schon ein Projekt, dass das momentan läuft. Diese Terabytes von Daten haben wir in einzelnen zwei Gigabyte Päckchen über SharePoint bekommen. " (Subject 6 , Pos. 11)</p>	12
Largest / most complex projects	<p>Description: This objective category denotes interview passages that provide contextual examples on some of the largest or most complex information projects the subjects have been involved in.</p> <p>Example: "File Numbers in den Millionen vielleicht weil also du hast 100 Elemente und pro Element hast du verschiedene sets. Und dann hast du die Reviews, dann hast du die Produkte, das heißt Tausende, 100.000, Ja, so 100 Millionen files." (Subject 9 , Pos. 65)</p>	6
General practices dealing with info	<p>Description: This analytical category denotes subcodes that provide information on general practices when dealing with large information collections</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Learning / Collaboration" or "Lifecycle management of information"</p>	0
Learning / Collaboration	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that provide general practices</p> <p>Example: "File Numbers in den Millionen vielleicht weil also du hast 100 Elemente und pro Element hast du verschiedene sets. Und dann hast du die Reviews, dann hast du die Produkte, das heißt Tausende, 100.000, Ja, so 100 Millionen files." (Subject 9 , Pos. 65)</p>	4
Lifecycle management of information	<p>Description: This analytical category denotes subcodes that provide information on Lifecycle management of information</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Safety" or "Data Quality / Cleaning"</p>	0
Safety	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages mentioning safety regarding information practices.</p>	6

	<p>Example: "Manchmal sind sie klein genug, dass sie per Email verschickt werden, auch wenn sie unkritisch sind, was Datensicherheit angeht." - Subject 8 Pos. 86</p>	
Data Quality / Cleaning	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages mentioning data quality regarding information practices.</p> <p>Example: "My only problem is definitely with company DB. We got some issue, for example, with the data quality. So for that, what I do is, first of all, to double check the data first compared to our platform, second compare to external data, for example, if you have a number for company, I need to double check that on the website on the company. " - Subject 2 Pos. 35</p>	2
Search / Acquisition / Retrieval / Scraping	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages mentioning search, retrieval, access, scraping of information.</p> <p>Example: "Normally to get access, you need, for example, access to the internal databases. And I need some tools to navigate into the internal databases. And the first tool that I use is SQL or my SQL. This language. I use it to navigate into the databases and also Python for more in-depth, let's say, analysis. So this tools serve me normally to get the data. To analyse the data." - Subject 2 Pos. 23</p>	11
Archiving/Deletion	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages mentioning archiving/deletion of information as a practice.</p> <p>Example: "Und dann gibt es noch quasi zwei Arten von Archivierung (in Trello), nämlich die eine Spalte heißt Feedback. Da kommen dann die Dateien rein, die also die die Kärtchen rein, die eigentlich erledigt sind, wo ich aber noch auf Feedback warte, ob ich den Haken runtersetzen kann oder nicht. Und wenn ich einen Haken dahinter setzen kann, dann geht es in Richtung erledigt." - Subject 8 Pos.198</p>	4
Data Collection	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages mentioning data collection of information as a practice.</p> <p>Example: "Und dann gibt es noch quasi zwei Arten von</p>	5

	<p>Archivierung (in Trello), nämlich die eine Spalte heißt Feedback. Da kommen dann die Dateien rein, die also die die Kärtchen rein, die eigentlich erledigt sind, wo ich aber noch auf Feedback warte, ob ich den Haken runtersetzen kann oder nicht. Und wenn ich einen Haken dahinter setzen kann, dann geht es in Richtung erledigt." - Subject 8 Pos.198</p>	
Data Storage	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages mentioning data storage of information as a practice.</p> <p>Example: "Genau. Also das ist dann die die Challenge, die wir dann haben. Also jetzt, Du bekommst die Daten von bestimmter Seite oder Endpoint lassen uns sagen, dieses API ist im Endeffekt diese Interface. Sie sammeln die Daten und schicken sie uns in bestimmte Formate, aber in massenhaft. Und dann ist es unsere Aufgabe, zu den Storage zu verwalten, sodass wir auch leichter die, die die Daten erst mal verteilen können und zweitens mal abrufen können." - Subject 9 Pos.17</p>	8
Versioning	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages mentioning versioning of information as a practice.</p> <p>Example: "Und drum lege ich mir dann teilweise solche Versionierung an, aber wirklich nur sehr, sehr sporadisch und unstrukturiert. Heißt einfach nur, dass jede Datei bei mir immer am Anfang das Datum hat. Wenn sechsstellig also 23 10 18 würde die heutige Datei beginnen und dann liegt halt quasi noch eine Kopie einer Datei rum mit dem aktuellen Datum und die der alte da, der wird dann weitergearbeitet und die alte Datei ist dann sozusagen dadurch archiviert. " - Subject7 Pos. 27</p>	5
Backups	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages mentioning backups as a practice.</p> <p>Example: "Und dann klar, wenn du irgendwie eine Applikation hast, die auf der Web läuft, dann macht es natürlich auch Sinn, dass die Daten die irgendwo auf dem Server sind, regelmäßig gebackuped werden, dass es da eine gute Schnittstelle gibt zwischen der Applikation und den Daten." - Subject 3 Pos. 37</p>	4
Validation	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview</p>	3

	<p>passages mentioning validation as a practice.</p> <p>Example: "Die Daten sind auch in dem Jason. Ja, aber es gibt ein Link ... dann siehst du die Google Seite, die wir dann am Ende die Daten dann gespeichert haben in dem. Also im Endeffekt könnte irgendwas sein darin, denn der Daten Validierung ist ein großes Thema bei uns." - Subject 9 Pos. 23</p>	
Information management fundamentals	<p>Description: This analytical category denotes subcodes that provide information on Information management fundamentals.</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Tools" or "Folder structures"</p>	0
Tools	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages mentioning tools as practice.</p> <p>Example: "Wenn das ganze zum Beispiel dann wirklich richtig ernst zu nehmen groß ist, benutze ich in der Regel irgendwelche Programmier Tools, die auch in der Lage sind, mit größeren Datenmengen umzugehen. Meistens Python oder R basiert." - Subject 7 Pos. 23</p>	12
Folder structures	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages mentioning practices related to folder structures</p> <p>Example: "Auch so 10.000, wenn du manuell checken möchtest, Du brauchst Struktur. Struktur ist es der Key Schlüsselwort hier. Weil auch jetzt, je mehr du dokumentiert ist, alles schön. Und so weiter. Aber Struktur und Hierarchie. Es ist ein Disziplin, die wir haben müssen " - Subject 9 Pos. 84</p>	8
Predefined structure	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that report the phenomenon that folder structures may be pre-defined by ways of retrieval.</p> <p>Example: "Ich glaube, dass (die Struktur) Großteils auch irgendwie schon so ein bisschen in Anführungszeichen vorgegeben ist, darüber wie man an die Informationen rankommt, zum Beispiel bei dem erstes Scraping hat es einfach Sinn gemacht, dass nach Postleitzahlen abzuspeichern, " (Subject 5 , Pos. 13)</p>	3
Meta information /Documentation/Logging	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages mentioning meta information, documentation and logging practices.</p> <p>Example: "Naja, und dann kann man noch Labels</p>	3

	<p>verteilen, da kommt dann auch so ein bisschen rein. Sind es jetzt payed Projekte? Sind es Pitches? Ist es next Statista internes, sind es Weiterentwicklung, Weiterbildungs-Themen oder wie auch immer. Dass ich so ein bisschen an Hand der Farbcodierung auch erkennen kann, oder auch schnell raus wiederfinden kann. Wenn ich eine Karte suche zu einem konkreten Projekt, dann bräuchten wir die gelben und die gelben sind Paid Projekte zum Beispiel" - Subject 8 Pos. 207</p>	
File/Folder names	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages mentioning practices related to File/Folder names.</p> <p>Example: "Also das ist jetzt die Folder Struktur, dann dann am Ende, also wenn du klickst auf den Folder, da siehst du einen Folder, usw. Und am Ende ist eine Datei, die hat einen Name und diese Name hat zwei oder drei Merkmale. Erst mal das Datum, den Timestamp sagt man, das ist in diese Zeit und es ist nicht die die Zahl wie jetzt 11:40 oder so, ne, es ist eine Timestamp, das ist eine Nummer, so eine große Nummer. Und dann natürlich, was ist die vom Typ zum Beispiel." - Subject 9 Pos. 21</p>	2
Challenges	<p>Description: This analytical category denotes subcodes that provide information on challenges faced by subjects when dealing with large information collections</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Data Complexity and Source Management" or "Information Storage and Access Challenges"</p>	0
Out-of-control / External Project	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that state challenges that arise when working with large information collections, due to the fact that someone is working with or dependent on external partners.</p> <p>Example: "Ich hatte schon andere Projekte, bei denen die echte Herausforderung nicht nur das schiere Volumen der Daten ist, sondern als als Externer in Daten eines Kunden, die also die richtige Version zu finden, also quasi im Unternehmen, die Wahrheit zu finden" (Subject 6 , Pos. 45)</p>	8
Data Complexity and Source Management	<p>Description: This analytical category denotes subcodes that provide information on data complexity and source management challenges faced by subjects when dealing with large information collections</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Fragmentation" or "Information</p>	0

Flood"		
Fragmentation	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that state challenges in the context of data complexity and source management, namely that of fragmentation and many information sources.</p> <p>Example: "...es klafft eine Lücke zwischen der Art und Weise, wie ich persönlich Daten verwalten würde, und dem, was passiert, wenn man in einem Team arbeitet und Informationen über verschiedene Kanäle erhält, die man dann zusammenführen muss. Ich merke gerade, dass dies bei Projektarbeiten ziemlich schwierig ist, weil wir hauptsächlich mit SharePoint arbeiten. Es gibt einen SharePoint für das Projekt, aber dann hat auch jeder sein eigenes SharePoint, wo weitere Informationen abgelegt werden. Am Ende sind die Informationen über Teams-Kanäle verstreut oder sie befinden sich auf irgendeinem Server. Die Informationen sind meistens nicht gebündelt." (Subject 3, Pos. 16)</p>	3
Information Flood	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that state challenges in the context of data complexity and source management, namely that of information overload.</p> <p>Example: "Wie schon erwähnt, haben wir riesige Datensätze, sowohl was das Volumen als auch die Anzahl betrifft. Und wie du schon sagtest, auch die Vielfalt der Dateitypen ist enorm. Wir haben alles Mögliche, von CSV- bis zu JSON-Dateien, Excel-Dateien, aber es gibt auch spezielle Formate wie Pickle und Parquet, die noch mehr Informationen speichern können. Von diesen haben wir unzählige Dateien, und auch die Größe ist sehr groß. Daher ist es für uns immer unglaublich wichtig, dass alles strukturiert ist. Wenn wir unstrukturiert mit diesen Datensätzen oder dieser Flut an Informationen und Daten umgehen würden, würde alles verloren gehen, und das wäre kritisch." (Subject 4 pt.1 , Pos. 25)</p>	2
Information Storage and Access Challenges	<p>Description: This analytical category denotes subcodes that provide information on information storage and access challenges faced by subjects when dealing with large information collections</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Storage" or "Archiving"</p>	0
Storage	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that state information storage and access challenges, with a focus on "storage", this can include challenges with filetypes regarding storage and storage solutions in general.</p> <p>Example: "Unser Hauptproblem ist so oder so bei großen</p>	9

	<p>Datenmengen der Speicher. Speicher ist teuer, Speicher ist selten und da muss man immer abwägen wie wahrscheinlich ist es, dass man nach Abschluss eines Projekts noch mal irgendwann auf diese Daten zugreifen möchte?." (Subject 1 , Pos. 23)</p>	
Storage / Access	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that state information storage and access challenges, with a focus on "storage and access", other than the sub-code on "storage" this one focuses on access issues that come with storing large amounts of information.</p> <p>Example: "Die zweite ist, dass der Datenbestand nicht portabel ist. Ich kann nicht im Flugzeug oder in der Bahn dann da mal kurz durch flötzen, weil das nicht in einer lokalen Replik eines SharePoint Ordners ist, sondern das liegt auf einem Server und ich muss mich dann halt per SSH auf den Server wählen, wenn ich da eine Datenbank Sachen suchen möchte." (Subject 6 , Pos. 29)</p>	4
Archiving	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that state information storage and access challenges, with a focus on "archiving"</p> <p>Example: "Es gibt viele Leute, die mit externen Festplatten rummachen, zum Beispiel. Das habe ich versucht, immer tunlichst zu vermeiden. Und dann hast du manchmal tatsächlich den Fall, das hatte ich tatsächlich schon öfters, dass du auf einmal ganz plötzlich und relativ zeitkritisch doch irgendwas brauchst. Und da musst du halt überlegen: Wann war das? Wie war damals meine Archivierungsstrategie? Wo finde ich das? Wie schnell kriege ich das jetzt hier wiederher? Also, da hatte ich jetzt zum Beispiel schon mal den Fall, das war aber vor diesem Job, dass ich dachte: Ach stimmt, das ist die Backup-Festplatte in dem und dem Server und das ist jetzt in dem Raum. Ich weiß, dass da ein Server steht mit der Festplatte, und da ist diese Datei, aber wie komme ich jetzt dahin? Die Zugangsdaten sind nicht mehr aktuell. Vielleicht muss ich mich über einen Account von einem Kollegen wieder eingeloggt und das dann irgendwie übers Internet zu mir transferiert? Teilweise, ja auch, das sind die Ownership-Daten. Die liegen halt nicht bei dir. Das ist dann nicht okay, das einfach bei dir zu sammeln, das muss halt irgendwo da liegen, wo es hingehört, und dann hast du da mal schnell auch ein Problem." (Subject 7 , Pos. 39)</p>	2
Organisational and collaborative challenges	<p>Description: This analytical category denotes subcodes that provide information on organizational and collaborative challenges faced by subjects when dealing with large information collections</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Clarity" or "Uncertainty and</p>	0

unpredictability"		
Clarity	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that relate to organisational and collaborative challenges, specifically around the theme of clarity and viewability.</p> <p>Example: "Aber die erste Herausforderung, die mir einfällt, ist die Übersicht zu behalten. Bei sehr großen Mengen von Dateien ist es schlichtweg nicht mehr möglich, von Hand auch nur die Dateiliste zu sehen. Und oft ist das ja ein einfacher Weg, um sich einen Überblick zu verschaffen, und das entfällt dort. Das heißt, selbst wenn ich nur gucken möchte, welche Titel die Dateien haben, welche Arten, welche Filetypen vorhanden sind, wie groß sie sind oder von wann sie sind – all die Dinge, die man in einfachen Kontexten nimmt, um einen Schnellcheck (Sanity Check) zu machen, bevor man überhaupt nur auf Metadatenebene das Ganze betrachtet. Dafür brauche ich dann schon ein Skript und dann brauche ich jemanden, der in der Lage ist, das für mich über Code auszuwerten. Es gibt sicherlich noch Mittel und Wege, die ich auch als Nicht-Techniker nutzen kann, wie viele Excel-Plugins, die mir von einem Ordner und Unterordner die Metadaten, Dateigröße und so weiter in eine Datei schreiben. Aber selbst dann muss ich anfangen, irgendwie über Pivot-Tabellen oder Power BI eine aggregierte Analyse darüberzulegen, um dann wieder mit meinen Augen und meinem Verstand in der Lage zu sein, damit etwas anzufangen. Also das ist so die erste Herausforderung." (Subject 6 , Pos. 29)</p>	5
Uncertainty and unpredictability	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that relate to organisational and collaborative challenges, specifically around the theme of uncertainty and unpredictability.</p> <p>Example: " Vielleicht noch ein Zusatz zu diesen ganzen Strategien. Ich ertappe mich selber teilweise manchmal, wenn Projekte über eine lange Zeit gehen, dass ich irgendwie Nach x Monaten mir überlege "Das war doch nicht so schlau, oder?" Ich hätte es doch gerne lieber anders gemacht. Und das ist natürlich immer ärgerlich, wenn so passiert. Man kann natürlich immer nicht alle Eventualitäten vorhersehen, wenn sich vielleicht auch Sachen ändern." (Subject 3 , Pos. 64)</p>	2
Data Protection Concerns (+)	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that relate to organisational and collaborative challenges, specifically around the theme of data protection concerns.</p> <p>Example: "Und wenn die Daten sensibel sind, gibt es auch Fälle, wo man sagt okay, dann muss man sie halt vielleicht</p>	4

	<p>auch mal, wenn es große Datenmengen sind, auf einer externen Festplatte speichern, die verschlüsselt ist. Das hatte ich jetzt in einem Projekt hier auch, dass wir große, riesengroße Datenmengen hatten vom Kunden. Die mussten wir halt ja auf einer externen Festplatte speichern, weil da war wieder das Thema: "Server, Cloud = gefährlich". Lieber auf einer Festplatte und möglichst irgendwie mit gepanzerten Wagen von einem Ort zum anderen liefern lassen." (Subject 3 , Pos. 37)</p>	
Time-Constraints	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that relate to organisational and collaborative challenges, specifically around the theme of time-constraints (given the nature of the work-context).</p> <p>Example: "Und ja, wenn man dann so will, weil also das Problem an der Stelle ist es nicht, dass es nicht funktioniert, sondern dass du, dass du dann halt einen Tag warten muss, bis bis seine Berechnung durch ist. Du hast ja aber irgendwie ein Projekt, wo und dem Kunden was vorstellen muss." (Subject 5 , Pos. 30)</p>	4
Collaboration	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that relate to organisational and collaborative challenges, specifically around the theme of collaboration.</p> <p>Example: "Wenn man zum Beispiel zusammen an einem File arbeitet und das bei vielen Files, kann es schon mal passieren, dass irgendwie zwei am gleichen File arbeiten und dann unterschiedlich abspeichern und dann geht viel Information verloren. " (Subject 4 pt1 , Pos. 33)</p>	5
Technical and Processing Challenges	<p>Description: This analytical category denotes subcodes that provide information on technical and processing challenges faced by subjects when dealing with large information collections</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Special skills needed" or "Physical challenges"</p>	0
Special Skills needed	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that relate to technical and processing challenges, around the need of special skills .</p> <p>Example: "In dem Moment, wo ich ein Script schreiben muss, um rauszufinden, wo was liegt oder wo was verteilt ist oder nicht stimmen kann, ist das ein Subset von Menschen, die die entsprechenden Skills haben." (Subject 6 , Pos. 29)</p>	3
Physical	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview</p>	2

challenges	<p>passages that relate to technical and processing challenges, around the theme of physical challenges.</p> <p>Example: "Du hast physikalische Herausforderungen, zum Beispiel: Du speicherst Daten auf einem Hard Drive, aber dieser soll nicht lokal sein, sondern auf einem Server, und dieser Server soll sicher sein. Das heißt, der erste Schritt, den die IT macht, ist sicherzustellen, dass alles intern bleibt. Das bedeutet, dass du den Hard Drive nicht einfach von deinem Haus aus erreichen kannst. Dafür brauchst du eine VPN." (Subject 9 , Pos. 50)</p>	
Data-Cleaning	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that relate to technical and processing challenges, around the theme of data-cleaning and quality.</p> <p>Example: " Data quality. Because it can be so difficult to clean, let's say an Excel sheet with, let's say, almost 1 million companies. Compared to, let's say, a sheet that would have only 10,000 companies. It's so difficult to spot the inaccurate data. It's difficult to spot. For example, the missing values and also, as I said, the data that are not accurate." (Subject 2 , Pos. 37)</p>	2
Filesystem	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that relate to technical and processing challenges, around the theme of the Filesystem.</p> <p>Example: " Manchmal hat man natürlich die Herausforderung: Wir arbeiten ja hauptsächlich in Projekten. Das heißt, es macht Sinn, sich sozusagen die die Information auch Projekt basiert, zu speichern. Aber es gibt natürlich immer wieder dieser Gedanke, auch von Information, Sharing und Knowledge Sharing, so ein bisschen, dass man sagt okay, es gibt ja aber auch Informationen, die vielleicht für andere Projekte relevant sind. Und dann ist es meistens so, wenn da ein neues Projekt das musst du erst mal überlegen, Aha, da war doch irgendwie ein Projekt mal, da haben wir doch so was Ähnliches, muss ich erst mal da suchen. Das ist jetzt auch nicht so ideal, dann, wenn man rein Projekt basiert, sich die Daten ablegt." (Subject 3 , Pos. 4)</p>	2
Tool limitations	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that relate to technical and processing challenges, around the theme of tool limitations.</p> <p>Example: "I'm limited by using Excel because sometimes you need to send results to the client via an Excel file. Excel sheets have their limits, with around 1.04 million rows. So, if we're dealing with, say, 2 million companies, we need to create additional sheets. For instance, we might use Python to generate these extra Excel sheets. This can be problematic because although the request is the same,</p>	8

	we're dealing with multiple files for a simple task. So, the data volume can become an issue when inputting data if it's too much for a single Excel file." (Subject 2 , Pos. 41)	
Time / Processing Challenges	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that relate to technical and processing challenges, around the theme of time and processing.</p> <p>Example: "Also im Endeffekt ist es die Arbeit mit großen Daten, egal ob das jetzt die Menge der, der oder die Größe der Datei ist oder die Anzahl der Dateien. Es ist ja immer noch mal sozusagen in der Verarbeitung gefühlt zehn Stufen schwieriger, als wenn man jetzt einen kleinen Datensatz hat." (Subject 4 pt2 , Pos. 6)</p>	4
Strategies	<p>Description: This analytical category denotes subcodes that provide information on strategies developed by subjects to manage the challenges faced by subjects when dealing with large information collections</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Strategies to address organisational and collaborative challenges" or "Strategies for technical and processing challenges"</p>	0
Strategies to Address Organisational and Collaborative Challenge	<p>Description: This category was formed analytically and serves as a title for sub-codes regarding general strategies within the context of collaboration and organisation.</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Communication and collaboration" or "Documentation" or "Learning from Others"</p>	0
Mental Models	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes all mental models, metaphors, train-of-thought or internal principles statements on how a Subject handles large information collections.</p> <p>Example: "Ja, also Sie können sich das tatsächlich vorstellen wie eine, wie eine kleine Fabrik. Es gibt ein Bürogebäude, das ist daneben. Da kommt dann der Vertrag, da kommt die Kommunikation hin. Wenn man die ablegt, ist nicht immer der Fall. Da kommen so SOW. Und so weiter. Das hat letztendlich natürlich nichts mit dem zu tun, was am Ende erstellt wird. Und dann hast du irgendwie Logistik-Park, wo uns angeliefert wird und also die den Produktionsbereich und ist am Ende die die Auslieferung. Also die vier Bereiche. Grob kann man das schon. Schon unterscheiden." (Subject 1 - Pos. 24)</p>	6
Information Hygiene	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes statements regarding regular information practices, necessary to keep the information space tidy.</p> <p>Example: "Am Ende sind es ja diese vielen kleinen Handgriffe, die man dann immer macht. Also noch mal</p>	4

	<p>was auszusortieren, nach einem Termin noch mal das Wichtigste zu übertragen. Aus Emails halt doch die Datei erst mal an einem zentralen Ort abzuspeichern, die Email einfach da liegen zu lassen, in der Hoffnung, ich finde die dann schon, auch wenn zehn weitere oben drauf kommen wieder. Nein, ich brauche hier bloß diese Datei, diese Powerpoint, die in der Email drin ist, die brauche ich nicht, die E Mail, also speichere ich die Powerpoint Datei. Und da sind einfach ganz viele so kleine alltägliche Handgriffe, die man halt einfach konsequent machen muss oder sich daran gewöhnen muss, die zu machen. " (Subject 8 Pos. 579)</p>	
Communication and collaboration	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes statements regardig the collaboration in the information management process. It includes sections regarding communication with clients on information structures, and the importance of integrity of structure, so that collaborative work is efficient.</p> <p>Example: "Heutzutage würde ich direkt dem Kunden zurück spiegeln und sagen das wir Hilfe brauchen bei der Strukturierung. Also wenn es einfach nur so gedumped wird sozusagen, dass man versucht mit dem Kunden zusammenzuarbeiten und zu sagen kannst du uns da mal durchführen? Kann uns dein Experte, also jemand, der diese Ordnerstruktur verwaltet, uns einmal zeigen, was da für uns wirklich das Relevante ist, Einfach um da Aufwände auch gering zu halten. Die hat der Kunde ja auch bezahlt und macht natürlich auch Sinn. So dann noch mal eine extra Runde zu gehen" - Subject 8 Pos. 390</p>	10
Documentation	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes statements regardig the importance of self-documentation for learning purposes and documentation for tracebility across different people. Statements include the wishes for documentation, even if at times a lack of time or effort prohibits the process of documenting.</p> <p>Example: "Wenn jeder Excel Business Case so gut dokumentiert wäre wie die Algorithmen von unserem gemeinsamen Kollegen Markus in-line. Ich quasi, während ich den Code lese, auch nachvollziehen kann, warum er das gemacht hat und was man. Ja, das wäre schön." Subject 6 Pos. 47</p>	6
Learning from others	<p>Description: This thematic category encaptules statements about a strategy to learn from others in the field or experts in the field, rather than trying it all on their own.</p> <p>Example: "...man rennt, irgendwann von allein in irgendein Problem rein. Und dann würde ich immer stoppen. Und nicht versuchen selber was zu erfinden, sondern würde immer erst mal den Schritt gehen, nach</p>	4

	Best Practices zu googeln. Ich würde immer die Annahme tätigen "Hey, das Problem hatte bestimmt schon viele und auch über Jahre hinweg". - Subject 7 pos. 68	
Strategies for technical and processing challenges	Description: This category was formed analytically and serves as a title for sub-codes regarding strategies for technical and processing challenges Sub-Code Examples: "Random Samples" or "Data Prioritising"	0
Random Samples		1
Automatisation	Description: This thematic category holds statements about the importance of automation regarding processing large amounts of information. Example: "Im nächsten Schritt müssen wir das Ganze noch automatisch machen. Mit manueller Arbeit wird man bei großen Datensätzen nicht weit kommen. Das macht einfach gar keinen Sinn." - Subject 4	1
Data Prioritising	Description: This thematic category denotes text segments regarding a special strategy to mitigate challenges in processing and storage they called "prioritizing" Example: "Wie anfangs schon mal erwähnt, sind wir teilweise gegen Kapazitäts Engpässe gelaufen auf dem SharePoint. Heißt wenn ich einen kleinen Datensatz habe und zehn Variablen und 100.000 Observationen, kann ich sagen, ich nehme alle mit und ich brauche vielleicht nicht alle, aber ich nehme alle mit. Wohingegen, wenn ich einen sehr großen Datensatz bekommen kann, sage ich mal, den noch nicht runtergeladen habe, muss ich mir vielleicht vorher überlegen, welche Fragestellungen ich bearbeiten und welche Variablen könnten dies? Weil ich dann halt nicht sagen kann, ich nehme die 1000 Variablen mit 10 Millionen Observationen und lad die mal runter und schauen wir mal was passiert." Subject 5 Pos 34	2
Batches	Description: This thematic category denotes text segments regarding a special strategy to mitigate challenges in processing referred to as "batches". Example: "Und gerade auch bei großen Datensätzen kann man sich das vorstellen. Wenn das jetzt Millionen über Millionen, über Millionen von Zeilen sind, dann teilen wir das in Batches auf, also in einen Unter Punkte man sagen okay, die das sind die ersten 2000 Datenpunkte und dann geht es weiter mit den nächsten 2000 Punkten usw." Subject 4 pt 1 Pos 27	6
Using / Developing Tools	Description: This analytical category was formed around subcodes regarding the use and development of tools to help with different tasks when working with large	0

	information collections.	
	Sub-Code Example: "Tools that were developed internally", "Tools that were developed externally"	
General advice regarding tools	<p>Description: This thematic category debotes text segments regarding general advice around the use of tools to help with differnt tasks when working with large information collections.</p> <p>Example: "First of all, you need to know how to use Excel very well, because sometimes they underestimate Excel. I don't know why, but it's a powerful tool and you need to know exactly, for example, how to write a VBA script, for example, that can help you to deal with many problems you have with your data of a large amount of data." Subject 2 Pos. 69</p>	2
Tools that were developed externally	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes text segments regarding the use of external tools as a strategy when working with large amounts of information.</p> <p>Example: "Da gibt es File Managementsysteme. GitHub ist zum Beispiel eins, was unglaublich gut ist, sozusagen Files abzulegen in verschiedenen Bereichen und das Ganze zu dokumentieren. Da kann man, und das haben wir auch schon gemacht read me's schreiben in Ordnern, dass man dann sagt okay, ich strukturiere meine verschiedenen Ordner und dann in den Ordnern mache ich so, kleine readme's damit die Leute wissen, was sie da finden. Sehr, sehr hilfreich. Das ist sehr hilfreich sogar." Subject 4 - pt 1 Pos 33</p>	10
Tools that were developed internally	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes text segments regarding the use and development of tools as a strategy when working with large amounts of information (compared to the use of external, existing tools)</p> <p>Example: "Das zweite ist natürlich dann wiederum sinnvolle Oberflächen zu implementieren, um die Daten zu sehen und den Überblick zu behalten. Also quasi ein modernes Äquivalent zum Datei Browser. Und das heißt, wir haben für dieses eine große Projekt ein eigenes Dokumenten Management und Workflow System gebaut, weil es ein sehr, sehr spezieller Job war, weil wir Data Annotation auf diese Daten draufgelegt haben. (...) Also Tools, die einem die Brücke bauen mit einem einfachen User Interface um, um wieder das Gefühl zu haben ich habe hier Kontrolle und ich als nicht Developer kann trotzdem diese Daten reingeben. Das ist das ist oft hilfreich." Subject 6 pos. 31</p>	4
Strategies for Information Storage	Description: This category was formed analytically and serves as a title for sub-codes regarding strategies for	0

and Access Challenges	information storage and access challenges Sub-Code Examples: "Search" or "Access"	
Search	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages regarding strategies in the context of "search".</p> <p>Example: "Das ist generell bei mir eine Strategie, die sich in den letzten Jahren immer und immer und immer mehr verbreitet hat, ist, dass ich Tools nehme, die eine Durchsuchen-Funktion haben. Dann suche ich eben. Per Schlüsselwort oder per Art der Datei oder Erstellung, Datum oder weiß der Geier irgendwie. Ich meine, Ordnerstruktur bildet ja Kontext ab. Das ist ja sehr häufig, bildet einen Kontext ab, der der Information einer Datei nicht wirklich anhaftet und wenn man Glück hat, kann man diese Kontext Information auch irgendwie anders, mit Hilfe einer Suche, So weit eingrenzen, dass man das dann auch findet." Subject 7 Pos 49</p>	3
Access	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages regarding strategies in the context of "access".</p> <p>Example: "Eine Strategie ist oder eine Basis dafür ist sicherlich die, diese Daten trotzdem in der Cloud bereitzustellen. Das heißt also, wir haben nicht einen Server im Keller, sondern wir, wir haben einen Server in der Cloud, was es ja heutzutage ja unter ähnlicher Sicherheit möglich ist, Zugriff zu haben, aber dann eben zumindest auch ortsunabhängig Zugriff zu haben über eine sichere Verbindung. Das heißt also, damit fällt eine Limitation weg, wer zugreifen kann." - Subject 6 Pos 31.</p>	6
Version Control	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages regarding strategies in the context of "Version Control".</p> <p>Example: "Was ganz wichtig ist, ist dann das Datum. Also Versionierung. Ich habe das ja schon mal angeschnitten beim Thema code. Versionierung ist auch bei Daten ganz wichtig. Also wenn man was gemacht hat von zwei Wochen und das abgespeichert hat und dann führt man den Code noch mal aus und ein paar Wochen später und hat dann irgendwie was verändert am Code ist es ganz wichtig, dass man die alte Datei nicht wegschmeißt, dass man die in einem archivieren Folder hinterlegt und dann immer ein Datum dazu hat, dass man dann weiß, okay, das File wurde an diesem Datum erstellt und dann irgendwie das nächste File muss ja ein Update dazu sein, weil es an einem späterem Datum erstellt wurde. Könnte auch eine Versionierungs Nummer sein. Also könnte jetzt auch die Version eins sein oder Version 1.1 bis 2.1. Also das ist bei der Benennung auch ganz wichtig, dass da halt jedes Mal eine Versionierung oder Datum mit dabeisteht" (Subject 4</p>	3

Storage	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages regarding strategies in the context of "Storage".</p> <p>Example: "Nie werden alle Informationen oder alle Datensätze am Ende für das Projekt eine entscheidende Rolle spielen, sondern es werden bestimmte Datensätze für bestimmte Aufgaben, Teile oder Bearbeitungen relevant sein. Und dann hilft es, die zusammenzustellen. Das kann man, das sollte man nicht machen, indem man sie kopiert und woanders hin speichert. Denn große Datenmengen noch zu kopieren, potenziert ja nur den Speicherplatz und macht auch dann alles Mögliche langsamer, zum Beispiel auch Suchen und solche Dinge. Das heißt, im Idealfall lässt man alle Daten an einem zentralen Ort liegen und verlinkt dann aber vielleicht an einem anderen Ort quasi auf die auf die finalen Unterordner Strukturen oder auf die finale Datei, die man dann für konkrete Projekte braucht. Das heißt, es könnte dann zum Beispiel eine separierte Ordnerstruktur sein und am Ende liegen dann Links auf Dateien, die dann quasi besser funktioniert für einen. Man kann dann noch mal die Dateien sozusagen neu strukturieren über links." (Subject 8 , Pos. 397)</p>	9
Foundational Strategies	<p>Description: This category was formed analytically and serves as a title for sub-codes regarding foundational strategies, that are applied to handle general challenges faced by subjects when dealing with large amounts of information</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Structured Approach" or "Planning and preparation"</p>	0
Structured Approach	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages regarding foundational, overarching strategies regarding approaching large information in a structured manner.</p> <p>Example: "Ja, ich glaube, das allererste, was ich empfehlen würde, wenn man sagt, man steigt jetzt auf große Datensätze um, ist erst mal strukturiertes Vorgehen. Weil das ist am Anfang schon erstmal das A und O. Man muss die Sachen strukturieren, man muss seine Ordner Verzeichnisse strukturieren, man muss die die Datensätze selber strukturieren, weil ganz oft sind es auch so, dass</p>	12

man unterschiedliche Datensätze hat und was weiß ich selbst auch noch gar nicht erwähnt hat. Aber man sagt, man hat teilweise auch unterschiedliche Datensätze in unterschiedlichen Files und vielleicht auch einem unterschiedlichen Format. Man hat vielleicht da mal eine Jason Datei und da mal eine CSV Datei und man will alles zusammen bekommen. Ähm, das heißt man muss da auch am Anfang schön strukturiert vorgehen, sich auf eine Sache festlegen, die Benennung immer so machen, dass man eine Versionierung drin hat und so, dass es auch maschinell lesbar ist. Und man sollte im Groben so vom Inhalt eine Übersicht haben, was du zum Beispiel wo ablegt, in welchem Verzeichnis. Und dann natürlich auch von der Verwendbarkeit der Dateien, dass es schon von außen klar ersichtlich ist. Was wurde da gemacht in diesem File, dass man Daten in den Trainings Folder und da weiß man, da sind die Trainingsdaten drin. Dann hat man eine Klasse und da sind die klassifizierten Daten und wir haben ein Model Folder, da sind die ganzen language Modelle drin. Also strukturiertes Vorgehen ist glaube ich das A und O und das wichtigste." (Subject 4 , Pos. 30)

<p>Planning and preparation</p>	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages regarding foundational, overarching strategies regarding planning and preparation before approaching large information collections. This category is similar to the category structured approach, but has a focus more on steps taken before touching the information.</p>	<p>6</p>
	<p>Example: "Und zum Start lieber erst planen und lieber einmal "dry run". Also konkretes Beispiel: Wenn ich ein Ordner von links nach rechts kopiere auf SharePoint, dann fasse ich den an und zieh den rüber. Aber wenn ich irgendwie remote Terabytes bewege oder irgendwas in der Tabelle Merge oder so, dann mache ich lieber einmal einen "dry run". Und das kann dann im Zweifel auch heißen ich hole Kollegen dazu. Und sage: Guck mal ich habe hier einen Text Dokument. Ich habe die Schritte runtergeschrieben, die ich jetzt durchführen möchte. Oder es gibt ja auch tatsächlich bei Datenbank Operationen, diese Möglichkeiten, quasi einmal ein Preview zu kriegen, das war jetzt das Ergebnis. So sieht das dann aus. Und weil, weil gerade wenn sachen compute intensiv sind, zeitintensiv sind, sind Fehler oft nur mit manueller Arbeit unter extremem Aufwand "zurückdrehbar". Dann ist so ein dry run, viel wichtiger, als wenn ich ein Word Dokument editiere und dann sage, nimm mal den letzten Stand." (Subject 6 , Pos. 43)</p>	
<p>Strategies for Information Complexity and Source Management:</p>	<p>Description: This category was formed analytically and serves as a title for sub-codes regarding strategies for information complexity and source management, namely around a structured approach.</p>	<p>0</p>

	Sub-Code Examples: "File/Folder Names" or "Folder Structure"	
Folder Struktur	<p>Description: This category was formed analytically and serves as a title for sub-codes regarding folder structure strategies for information complexity and source management</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Context-dependent decision making" or "Data Zones / specific structure"</p>	0
Context-dependent decision-making	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages regarding the dependence of right decisions regarding the folder structure based on the context.</p> <p>Example: "Aber zum Beispiel, wenn man, wie ich im Medizinbereich hatte, jetzt Daten von verschiedenen Probanden hat, dass man natürlich auch das nach Probanden auch so ein bisschen sortiert, alles natürlich auch da hat man die nächste Herausforderung, so ein bisschen diese Anonymisierung, das muss ja auch sozusagen in die Nomenklatur mit rein gedacht werden. Nicht, dass man die Anonymisierung, die vorher stattgefunden hat, so ein bisschen damit kaputtmacht. Und dann gibt es natürlich auch ja, wenn man jetzt so Daten hat, die auch so eine Zeit Komponente mit drin haben. Das muss man natürlich auch beachten. Wie strukturierst du, so strukturierst du es dann eher nach Zeitachse sozusagen oder strukturiert doch nach Entitäten. So ein bisschen. Also das hängt dann auch am Ende so ein bisschen vom Use Case ab. Wichtiger ist glaube ich, dass es systematisch ist, dass du immer weißt, okay, ich finde die Formation hier und die Zeit Komponente finde ich dann in Unterordnern oder genau andersherum. Ich finde zu einem Zeitpunkt alle Daten in diesem Unterordner zu allen Unternehmen oder zu allen Entitäten, zu dem man eben Daten hat." (Subject 3 , Pos. 45)</p>	2
Data Zones / specific structure	<p>Description: This analytical category denotes interview passages regarding a system that emerged from the interviews, namely structuring folders by zones.</p> <p>Example: "Natürlich gibt es unterschiedliche Strategien für verschiedene Rollen. Was jetzt die Daten betrifft: Wir haben beispielsweise zwei Zonen für Daten. Es gibt die Data Zones, darunter eine Rohdatenzone. Diese befindet sich meist in einem Ordner, der "Collections" genannt wird, und darin findest du verschiedene Projekte für ImmobilienScout24, für Miele usw. Die Kollegen müssen stets Verbindungen herstellen. So war es auch beim Projekt mit Miele: Wir haben Daten für einen spezifischen Kontext gesammelt. Anschließend geht man vor und liest die Dokumentation. In der Data Collection Zone sind dann</p>	7

die Rohdaten zu finden. Am Ende hat man Daten von sehr hoher Qualität – auf einem bestimmten Niveau, um wissenschaftlich korrekt zu bleiben. Diese Daten werden dann in ein anderes Repository überführt. Wir nennen es die Golden Zone. Hier befinden sich die Daten, die am besten für Datenbanken geeignet sind, sei es für SQL-Datenbanken oder NoSQL-Datenbanken, je nach Bedarf. Aber es handelt sich um Daten von guter Qualität. Alles ist geprüft und die Daten sind einsatzbereit." (Subject 9 , Pos. 43)

Early on structure

Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that stress the importance of defining a folder structure early on.

3

Example: "Versuche immer einen großen Fokus zu legen, auch relativ am Anfang, bevor man auch die Daten hoffentlich auch bekommt, ist, dass man auch den Kunden, wenn man es nicht selber sozusagen entscheiden kann, zwar auch frühzeitig den Kunden versucht dahin zu führen, dass die Daten in einem bestimmten Format geliefert werden, weil sonst hat man dann am Ende auch. Unglaublich viel Aufwand, die Daten erst mal wieder in eine schöne Struktur zu bekommen. Das heißt, meine Strategie ist natürlich immer Entweder ich schaffe es, dass der Kunde vorher die Daten so liefert, wie ich sie möchte, oder das ist sozusagen eigentlich so der erste Schritt. Und deswegen ist auch, würde ich mal sagen, ein großer Teil von Data Science Aufgaben ist weniger die schönen Machine Learning Algorithmen am Ende zu bauen, sondern es geht prinzipiell immer ganz am Anfang darum erstmal muss ich die Daten so hinbekommen, dass ich sie auch weiterverwenden kann. Das heißt, ich muss sie vernünftig irgendwo ablegen. Wenn es bei vielen Daten ist, kennen wir ja die ganzen Herausforderungen. Dann muss ich natürlich auch eine gute Nomenklatur mir überlegen." (Subject 3 , Pos. 43)

Personal Structure

Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that report on personal strategies in regards to the structure of folders

6

Example: "Ich habe dann aber meistens zusätzlich noch quasi meine eigenen Project Ordner für Dateien. Jetzt erst mal nur für mich sind quasi gespiegelt zu der Struktur, dann auf dem auf dem Server und da liegen dann auch die Datensätze, es sei denn, sie sind zu groß für OneDrive. Dann gibt es noch mal gespiegelt denselben Ordner offline sozusagen nur auf dem Laptop. Und dann sind es quasi die drei Quellen, also Trello, OneDrive oder offline entsprechend immer nach Projekten separiert." (Subject 8 , Pos. 139)

Standards	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that report on the use of standards in regards to folder structure.</p> <p>Example: "Manchmal entspricht die Struktur auch einem gewissen Standard, auch wenn es da jetzt keine festen Standards gibt. Aber es gibt so Best Practices. Häufig gibt es dann einfach einen Data Ordner und einen SAC oder Bin Ordner. Da weiß man schon sehr grob, was da eventuell drin zu erwarten ist." (Subject 7 , Pos. 47)</p>	2
File/Folder Names	<p>Description: This category was formed analytically and serves as a title for sub-codes regarding File/Folder Names strategies for information complexity and source management</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Maschine readability" or "Version control"</p>	0
Maschine Readability	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages regarding the importance of maschine readability when considering file and folder names.</p> <p>Example: "Das heißt, dass der Code muss bestmöglich auf dem, also auf dem File Path also diese, diese Ordnerstruktur, die man erstellt hat, funktionieren und muss auch bestmöglich auf den den Namen reagieren können. Das heißt, wir müssen immer daran denken, wenn wir einen Ordner erstellen oder wenn wir Files erstellen, müssen wir schon bei dem Namen darauf achten, dass es maschinenlesbar ist und keine verrückten Zeichen oder sowas einfügen und am besten auch kein Leerzeichen. Deshalb machen wir meistens den Unterstrich als um Leerzeichen zu ersetzen." (Subject 4 pt 2 , Pos. 4)</p>	3
Version control	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages regarding the importance of version control in the context of file and folder names.</p> <p>Example: "Aber dass jede Datei erst mal ein Datum vorne dran trägt, auch für die Versionierung und Sortierung innerhalb von Ordner Strukturen. Das mache ich auf jeden Fall." (Subject 8 , Pos. 279)</p>	4
Structure	<p>Description: This category was formed analytically and serves as a title for sub-codes regarding general strategies sourrounding a structured approach.</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Flexible adaption as collection grows" or "Technical structure"</p>	0
Flexible adaption as	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages regarding the importance of adapting the</p>	4

collection grows	<p>structure of a large information collection as it grows over time.</p> <p>Example: "Aber jeder hat ein anderes System, also welches System am Anfang sich zu überlegen und sie dann auch wirklich streng dann halten. Oder halt auch optimieren oder anpassen, je nachdem wann es notwendig ist. Nur dann auch komplett anpassen. Dann auch die alten Sachen noch mal neu strukturieren. Wenn das System nicht gut genug war, habe ich jetzt gerade erst gemacht, als ich meinen Laptop bekommen habe." (Subject 8 , Pos. 552)</p>	
Technical structure	<p>Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that report the phenomenon that folder structures may follow a technical structure due to the nature of the work-context.</p> <p>Example: "...auf den Projekten mit sehr großen Daten von Kunden. Das ist oft dann eine eher technische Datenstruktur. Also bei diesem Projekt mit den über 500.000 Daten, die das sind, sind ja mein geografischen Bezug diese Datensätze und die sind dann also nach grob Regionen, nach unter Regionen und nach einzelnen Standorten sortiert. Da entspricht dann also die Baumstruktur quasi der logischen Struktur." (Subject 6 , Pos. 27)</p>	2
Transferability of strategies	<p>Description: This category was formed analytically and serves as a title for sub-codes regarding the transferability of strategies.</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Transferable (yes)" or "Transferable (no)"</p>	0
Not transferable (no)	<p>Description: This category was formed analytically and serves as a title for sub-codes regarding the transferability of strategies (no)</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Over-Engineering" or "Threshold not reached to determine if a structure works"</p>	0
Over-Engineering	<p>Description: This evaluative category denotes interview passages that state that the use of strategies developed for large information collections is not beneficial for smaller information collections, because it would be inefficient aka over-engineered.</p> <p>Example: "Wenn du das (Distributed Computing) nicht wirklich benötigst, dann ist es besser, es zu lassen, das bedeutet, wenn die Datensätze kleiner sind. Dann wird der Aufwand auch größer sein, all diese Sachen zu machen und am Ende - okay, statt zehn Sekunden brauchst du nur</p>	6

	eine Sekunde. Aber der Gewinn ist nicht so groß." (Subject 9 , Pos. 78)	
Threshold not reached to determine if a structure works	<p>Description: This evaluative category denotes interview passages that state that the use of strategies developed for large information collections is not beneficial for smaller information collections, because one can only evaluate a functioning strategy once the information collection reaches a certain size.</p> <p>Example: "Also, meiner Meinung nach merkt man erst, dass eine Struktur nicht funktioniert, wenn man sehr viele Dateien hat. Also viele kleine Dateien. Bis jetzt habe ich sie einfach an einem Ort abgelegt. Jetzt merke ich aber, dass ich dort nichts mehr finde. Zum Beispiel habe ich mit 27 Zetteln angefangen, sie auf einen Stapel gelegt, und jetzt muss ich durchschauen, wo der Zettel zu einem bestimmten Meeting oder mit einer bestimmten Information ist. Also, ich muss alle 27 Zettel durchgehen. Dann wird mir klar, dass ich das irgendwie anders hätte clustern oder strukturieren müssen." (Subject 8 , Pos. 492)</p>	2
Transferable (yes)	<p>Description: This category was formed analytically and serves as a title for sub-codes regarding the transferability of strategies (yes)</p> <p>Sub-Code Examples: "Search" or "Use of structure"</p>	0
Importance of conscious data management	<p>Description: This evaluative category denotes interview passages that state that the use of strategies developed for large information collections can be beneficial for smaller information collections, with a focus on handling the information in a more conscious way.</p> <p>Example: "Und das das zweite ist, ich denke schon, dass dieser bewusste Umgang wo liegt etwas, wo habe ich Hoheit auch über den Speicherort, das Bewusstsein darüber, welche Speicherfristen. Lösch-Regeln etc. sonst wo hinterliegen, also eigentlich auch gut wären im Umgang mit kleinen Daten." (Subject 6 , Pos. 39)</p>	1
Search	<p>Description: This evaluative category denotes interview passages that state that the use of strategies developed for large information collections can be beneficial for smaller information collections, with a focus on search.</p> <p>Example: "Ein ganz prägnantes Beispiel dafür ist, wie man mit einem sehr einfachen Interface Zugang zu sehr großen Datenmengen im Hintergrund hat. Wenn ich mir überlege, wie einfach es ist, ChatGPT etwas zu fragen, dann frage ich mich, warum es so verdammt schwierig ist, etwas in meinem Outlook zu finden, und warum ich quasi umständlich computer-gerecht parametrisieren muss, obwohl der Zugang zu viel größeren Datenmengen</p>	1

	<p>einfacher ist. Wenn ich mir anschau, wie einfach, also vergleichsweise einfach, jemand im Data Team ein Skript schreiben kann, um die Datenbank nach den richtigen Sachen zu fragen, frage ich mich, ob ich nicht auch in der Lage sein sollte, als Nicht-Techie so vorzugehen und zu sagen: "Hey, lieber Datenbestand im ganzen SharePoint, ich möchte jetzt mal 'das' rausfinden." Also wirklich, das Thema Suche ist schon eklatant." (Subject 6 , Pos. 36)</p>	
Re-Use of existing set-ups	<p>Description: This evaluative category denotes interview passages that state that the use of strategies developed for large information collections can be beneficial for smaller information collections, with a focus on re-using existing information pipelines.</p> <p>Example: "Yes, it can be useful. For example, if you already have a script that can give you a specific result, you can definitely use it on a small amount of data. If you already have the script," (Subject 2 , Pos. 57)</p>	3
Use of structure	<p>Description: This evaluative category denotes interview passages that state that the use of strategies developed for large information collections can be beneficial for smaller information collections, with a focus using structures even for smaller amounts of information to strengthen the ability to collaborate on it and processing speed.</p> <p>Example: "Jeder ist anders und hat seine eigenen Strategien, aber ich glaube, unabhängig von der Größe der Daten sollte man immer versuchen, eine systematische Form zu haben, um Daten abzulegen und wiederzufinden, egal ob es wenige oder viele sind. Natürlich weiß man bei wenigen Daten meist gut Bescheid, wo was liegt. Aber man muss immer auch an das kollaborative Arbeiten denken. Wenn neue Personen auf ein Projekt stoßen und dann mit deinen Daten arbeiten sollen, müssen sie sich auch relativ schnell zurechtfinden können. Zum Beispiel sollten sie die eigene Systematik verstehen, auch wenn sie vielleicht ganz anders arbeiten. Aber wenn man selbst eine Struktur hat, dann können sich auch andere Personen darin orientieren. Ich würde sagen, unabhängig von der Datengröße sollte man immer versuchen, diese Systematik anzuwenden." (Subject 3 , Pos. 47)</p>	3
Versionierung	<p>Description: This evaluative category denotes interview passages that state that the use of strategies developed for large information collections can be beneficial for smaller information collections, with a focus using structures even for smaller amounts of information for versioning.</p> <p>Example: "Also eine Sache, die mir immer wieder auffällt, die unglaublich sinnvoll ist, wenn man damit ein bisschen umzugehen weiß ist Versionierung, insbesondere das Diff. Es ist unglaublich nützlich.... Das ist etwas, was</p>	2

eigentlich aus der Verwaltung von großen Mengen von Software kommt, was aber definitiv auch bei kleineren Sachen integriert werden könnte. Also wenn man zum Beispiel bei einem Outlook Termin auch sofort die gesamte Änderungs Historie sieht, vielleicht auch noch auf welche Email eine Änderung in einem Kalender Eintrag zurückführt und wer die gemacht hat. So solche solche Sachen sind glaube ich, könnte man sinnvoll adaptieren." (Subject 7 , Pos. 55)

Strategy that emerged from larger collections being adopted

Description: This thematic category denotes interview passages that state that strategies that can be seen in widely used tools like google docs or mail originated from a scene that handles vast amounts of information.

2

Example: "Es gibt so ein bisschen was, was zum Beispiel jetzt schon ist. Wenn du eine riesengroße Datei in Apple rein ziehst, dann sagen sie dir lass ma nicht per Email schicken, lass mal lieber bei iCloud hochladen, dann können die Leute sich das von da aus runterladen, okay. Solche Sachen, die quasi das vorher von Hand gemacht haben, werden dann jetzt automatisiert angeboten... Das ist eine Tool gestützte Strategie. Genauso eine Best Practice, die quasi durch diffundiert ist in die Allgemeinheit. Ist auch noch nicht überall drin, aber es gibt immer mehr Tools, die so was anbieten." (Subject 7 , Pos. 56)

9.5 Further Results

9.6 Part I: Contextual Insights

9.6.1 Info Sources

Customers as Data Source

Subject 7: Customers provide data directly, sometimes processed and supplied by technically skilled employees or through a contact person in the project. Subject 8: Receives data from customers, typically in the form of Excel files or SAP extracts, and often structures this information in PowerPoint slides. Subject 9: Customers provide data directly or data are collected from various websites, initially through scraping and later via APIs from other companies.

Internal Databases and Platforms

Subject 2: Mainly uses internal databases such as SMI databases and company insight databases and occasionally external databases for verification. Subject 6: Accesses data from a large platform like

Statista, which includes reports, market models, and research data.

Data Generation and Collection

Subject 1: Data are self-created, scraped, purchased, publicly collected, or delivered by the customer.

Subject 4: Pulls data via third-party APIs, uses scrapers for websites, and accesses public databases such as Google Scholar or Google Patents. Subject 5: Generates data through scraping websites and collects publicly available data from institutions like the OECD or WHO, as well as geodata and points of interest.

9.6.2 Info Types

Subject 7:

- CSV file collections, frequently encountered and containing various data such as billing data from mobile phone providers, technical logs from cell towers, database extracts from administrative databases and CRM systems.
- Previously large, publicly accessible image collections for training models.
- Source code management, including scripts for analysis or complete programs for delivery.
- Complex development environments associated with some programs.
- Output includes PowerPoint slides, finished code, and newly compiled datasets.
- Datasets in GEOJSON format and potentially other formats.

Subject 6:

- Strategic projects involving customer documents in Excel, PowerPoint, Word, and PDF formats.
- Creation of similar documents like strategic papers in PowerPoint, business plans in Excel, and occasionally papers in Word.
- Manages both small and extensive data volumes, including terabyte-scale data exchange and structuring hundreds of thousands of documents.

Subject 8:

- PowerPoint presentations and notes from communications and coordination meetings.

Subject 3:

- Primarily works with Excel files due to their convenience and client familiarity.
- Requests data dumps for Data Science tasks, especially sensitive data that must be anonymized and securely transferred.
- Uses SharePoint folders or customer servers for data uploads and downloads.
- Transfers encrypted data in CSV or ZIP files.
- Sometimes receives AWS containers with significant volumes of data for client projects.

Subject 2:

- Utilizes PDF and Excel files, with Excel being the predominant format for delivering outcomes to clients.
- Handles both qualitative and quantitative data types.

Subject 1:

- Deals with a wide range of data volumes, from small Excel files with fewer than 1,000 rows to datasets with over 1 million data points.
- Does not use programming languages, JSON files, or Python scripts, sticking mostly to readable CSV and Excel files through Office applications.

Subject 9:

- Currently, the majority of data is in JSON format, favored for its structured key-value pairing, which aids in achieving a standardized format for automation and pipeline construction

9.6.3 Main Task: Focus on Info

Handling of Information and Documentation (Subjects 7, 6, 3):

- Projects truly start with the availability of customer information, which tends to be voluminous and intricate, necessitating a profound understanding of business processes and the diverse formats in which information is received.
- Strategic documents in typical office formats (Excel, PowerPoint, Word, PDF) are created and managed, which generally involve manageable volumes of information, but larger information-intensive projects are also undertaken.

- There's a significant focus on the visualization of information, notably using tools like Power BI when Excel reaches its limitations.

Information Integration and Enhancement (Subject 7):

- Aside from working with customer information, there is the task of enhancing information with publicly available datasets, searching the free web or research databases, and possibly merging these with customer information for new insights or workflows.

Communicative Dynamics and Information Exchange (Subject 8):

- Flows of information in various forms—verbally, via digital communication tools like Teams and email, and through data sets and databases, all contributing to the projects and tasks at hand.

Importance of Contextual Information (Subject 3):

- In Data Science, the generation of insights is heavily dependent on the availability of diverse and sometimes unstructured sources of information, including project context and domain-specific knowledge.

Information Processing and Visualization (Subject 5):

- There's a comprehensive process from information generation and scraping (from the internet or specific databases like OECD, WHO) to the visualization of information, especially for insights into specific areas such as healthcare provision.

Protecting and Sharing Information (Subject 1):

- Information often needs to be protected or shared depending on internal and external requirements, with tasks involving safeguarding sensitive data or ensuring accessibility for those who need it.

Efficiency in Communication and Information Management (Subject 1):

- A significant part of the day involves handling communications efficiently, particularly managing emails and maintaining a structured file organization system.

Information Lifecycle Management (Subject 9):

- The role spans the entire information lifecycle: extraction, processing, cleaning, and visualization. This often involves handling large sets of information, such as online reviews or patent information, and applying natural language processing to extract actionable insights.

Versatility in Roles (Subject 9):

- In small teams, members often fulfill multiple roles traditionally split in larger teams, such as information engineers, DevOps, IT administration, and information scientists. This includes tasks from infrastructure management to information analysis and visualization.

Client-Centric Information Services (Subject 9):

- Providing services tailored to client needs involves collecting and processing information to a high quality level (referred to as the "Golden Zone") and addressing challenges based on client feedback, ultimately aiming for application-ready information.

In essence, these subjects describe a dynamic and multifaceted environment where information is not only processed and analyzed but is also a fundamental part of a broader communicative and project-oriented workflow. Information is gathered from diverse sources, enriched with additional details, and visualized to assist decision-making, often requiring an agile and flexible approach to handle the various tasks associated with information-centric roles.

9.6.4 Main Task

Data Science and Data Engineering Tasks (Subject 7):

- The task involves examining data sets from clients or public sources to answer targeted questions, driven by hypotheses or exploration. In the realm of Information Engineering, the focus is on providing infrastructure and workflows, often for data-driven or AI-driven projects.
- A significant part of the role involves stakeholder management, engaging closely with partners and clients to specify requirements and maintain project conditions to achieve both company and client objectives.

Multiple Roles in Management Consulting (Subject 6):

- The individual operates in three capacities: as a sales contributor to the firm's revenue, responsible for firm management and internal HR roles, and actively participating in projects as a management consultant.

Analytical and Project Management Duties (Subject 8):

- The work entails classic information analysis and preparation, including complex analyses, machine learning algorithms, and AI applications, possibly requiring cloud computing. This involves coding with languages like Python and SQL.
- Apart from technical tasks, there is a significant project management component, involving client interaction, presentation preparation, recruitment tasks, and internal company duties such as marketing.

Conceptual and Technical Support in Client Projects (Subject 3):

- The work closely involves consultants to conceptually support client inquiries, particularly what can be achieved with information and AI from a conceptual level, and then delving into the technical aspects of information analysis, processing, and machine learning model development.

Role in Information Analysis and Visualization (Subject 2):

- As an analyst, the work is information-driven, involving gathering, collecting, analyzing, and presenting results, regardless of the project. This also includes modeling for specific client requirements.

Transition to Advanced Visualization Tools (Subject 5):

- Due to the limitations of Excel, there has been a shift towards using Power BI for visualization, which allows handling larger volumes of information more efficiently and facilitates quicker analysis, including the use of JSON and large CSV files.

Technical and Strategic Support (Subject 9):

- The role is dual-leveled, offering technical support to team members and strategic guidance on technologies, policies, and solutions. The challenge is to switch between hands-on implementation and high-level strategic discussions continuously.

Monitoring Development and Providing Support (Subject 9):

- The task involves having an overview of team members' development, which is vital for potential promotions or identifying areas where development is lacking, along with daily communication to understand their challenges and progress. The role is not just to support but also to encourage colleagues to seek their solutions, ensuring that everything progresses as planned.

9.6.5 Info Route

SharePoint as a Primary Route (Subjects 7, 6 and 1):

- Information is frequently made available through SharePoint, serving as a central repository where files are stored. This is the go-to platform for both subjects, with one noting its use as a temporary parking space for information, and the other emphasizing its role in ensuring that knowledge is retained within the company even when employees depart.

Amazon EC2 and Other Cloud Services (Subject 7):

- Cloud services such as Amazon EC2 buckets have been used to provide large amounts of information. In the past, services like ownCloud and WeTransfer were employed for sharing information, highlighting a transition to cloud-based platforms for information exchange.

Dedicated Data Exchange Systems (Subject 6):

- For handling large volumes of information, conventional methods like FTP servers are used, along with customer-operated data exchange systems. These systems are described as glorified FTP setups with additional management tools. SharePoint has also been used to receive terabytes of information, demonstrating its flexibility for large-scale transfers.

Email and FTP Servers (Subject 8):

- Smaller, non-sensitive information sets are sometimes transmitted via email, while larger or sensitive information requires secured server access, usually password-protected FTP servers.

Customer-Specific Solutions (Subject 3):

- Depending on the project or customer requirements, different solutions are employed, including dedicated customer servers for uploading large amounts of information, and for smaller tasks, encrypted emails are used.

Internal Database Access and Programming Tools (Subject 2):

- Access to internal databases is gained through SQL languages, and Python is used for more in-depth analysis, indicating a technical route for information acquisition.

Web Scraping and Server Storage (Subject 5):

- Selenium, a Python library, is utilized for web scraping, indicating a method of collecting information from the internet, which is then stored as JSON files on SharePoint or departmental servers.

APIs for Information Gathering (Subjects 4, 1, and 9):

- APIs are a common method for retrieving information, either via paid access as part of an extraction pipeline or by building custom scrapers. Information from various databases is accessed through established accounts, showcasing APIs as a pivotal route for modern information gathering.
- For sharing with customers, information is often compressed into a manageable size and delivered in formats that customers can handle, such as JSON when collaborating with other data science departments.

9.6.6 Largest / most complex projects

Large Volume Document Handling (Subject 6):

- Managed a massive volume of documents, totaling approximately three terabytes, with individual files averaging around five megabytes in size, summing up to around 550,000 documents.

Complex Project Management (Subject 8):

- Oversaw a technically demanding project involving hardware solutions screening and custom software development, including programming and training algorithms. The

project required coordination within a large team, numerous consultants, and various stakeholders, resulting in a complex folder structure that was challenging to navigate.

Medical Image Data Project (Subject 3):

- Worked with a substantial volume of sensitive medical image data, where individual files were several hundred megabytes in size. The project encompassed 600 to 800 datasets, which, while not classified as 'big data', were significant in volume and required careful handling and anonymization of metadata due to privacy regulations.

Company Database Compilation (Subject 2):

- Compiled an exhaustive list of active companies in Mexico, a simple task in concept but complicated in execution, leading to the management of about 160,000 companies with approximately 2 million rows of various KPIs, necessitating meticulous verification and client coordination.

Product Review Collection (Subject 9):

- Gathered product reviews across 100 categories for the 'Home and Garden' project, involving brands like Samsung and Miele. This led to handling data files in the millions, with tens of thousands of products and potentially up to 100 million review records.

Genetic Data Metastudy (Subject 9):

- Analyzed 13 terabytes of genetic data in a postdoctoral metastudy, a significant challenge due to the immense size of the datasets, as well as the complexities of processing, coding, and encrypting such large volumes of sensitive information.

These summaries reflect the diversity and scale of information projects handled by the subjects, ranging from document management and technical project coordination to healthcare data analysis and large-scale market database creation. They showcase expertise in managing vast amounts of sensitive information under various conditions and requirements.

9.7 Part II: General Practices Dealing with Info

9.7.1 Learning / Collaboration

Subject 6 reflects on the significant shift in the importance of data-related skills, noting a mismatch

between traditional business education and the current demand for data proficiency. The use of Python scripts in Excel is highlighted as a practical example of the evolving skill set.

Subject 6 further emphasizes the need for active learning and adaptation within companies to avoid being left behind. The discussion extends to the collaborative aspect of information management, stressing the importance of distilling and transforming information to make it valuable across projects or for other users.

Subject 3 raises queries about new approaches to data processing, seeking information on programs that enhance multi-processing speed. This reflects a proactive attitude toward staying updated on the latest tools and methodologies in data processing.

In Subject 4's contribution, the challenges of knowledge transfer within teams are explored. The necessity of structured information processing is highlighted, emphasizing methods such as creating Powerpoint presentations for comprehensive documentation. The importance of a shared knowledge base for future reference and learning from past projects is underscored.

Overall, these reflections point to the dynamic nature of learning and collaboration in the context of information management, with a focus on adapting skills, fostering a collaborative environment, and efficiently sharing and documenting knowledge within teams.

9.7.2 Lifecycle Management of Information

Safety

Subject 8 covers the safe emailing of small, non-sensitive data sets, and the management of larger, sensitive data sets, emphasizing secure handling and the use of non-disclosure agreements. The subject also suggests using secure transfer methods like FTP servers or password-protected ZIP files, and storing sensitive data on encrypted laptops rather than using less secure cloud or server solutions.

Subject 3 addresses data privacy concerns, particularly the safety of cloud storage versus local storage, and the need to educate clients about the security of cloud services. This subject also discusses storing highly sensitive data on encrypted external hard drives, particularly for large datasets or sensitive information, to enhance security through physical transfer and encryption.

Finally, Subject 4 focuses on safely processing large data sets by breaking them into smaller batches for secure and efficient processing using multi-processing on servers. This includes the importance of logging sessions for tracking and managing potential errors during data processing.

Data Quality / Cleaning

Subjects 2 and 4 discuss the significant challenges of data cleaning, particularly in the context of large

datasets, highlighting issues related to data quality, completeness, accuracy, and formatting.

Subject 2 emphasizes the difficulty in maintaining data quality, especially when dealing with large Excel sheets containing nearly 1 million companies compared to smaller datasets. The challenge lies in identifying inaccurate data and spotting missing values, which becomes increasingly complex as the dataset size grows. The ability to detect and rectify these inaccuracies is crucial for ensuring the reliability and usefulness of the data.

Subject 4 addresses the intricacies of data cleaning in the context of large or massive datasets. They note that when acquiring datasets from third-party providers, there are often issues with data being incomplete, erroneous, or improperly formatted. These issues can significantly hinder the usability of the data and complicate the cleaning process. Ensuring correct data formatting is a key aspect of data cleaning, as improper formats can lead to misunderstandings and inaccuracies in data analysis.

Both subjects highlight that the challenges of data cleaning are amplified in larger datasets, where errors and inconsistencies become harder to identify and correct. This underscores the importance of robust data cleaning processes and techniques, especially when handling extensive datasets from various sources.

Search / Acquisition / Retrieval / Scraping

The interview excerpts collectively explore various methodologies and challenges associated with information search, acquisition, retrieval, and web scraping. Subject 7 focuses on obtaining information through client interactions and conducting online searches, sometimes using similar online data as a placeholder for unavailable client-specific data. Subject 6 highlights the importance of efficient information management by delegating the gathering of relevant information to team members, thus streamlining the process.

Subject 8 discusses the process of condensing extensive notes into concise, easily accessible information and also tackles the intricacies of web scraping, particularly the organization of unstructured data from diverse websites. Subject 3 emphasizes a systematic and structured approach to data organization, advocating for a balance between project-based storage and cross-project information sharing.

Subject 2 brings in the perspective of data analysis, using tools like SQL and Python, and also touches upon the use of Google Search and AI tools for aggregating external data. Meanwhile, Subject 1 underscores the significance of organized file storage, advocating for a standardized folder structure to enhance data findability and reproducibility. Lastly, Subject 9 delves into the challenges of managing and retrieving substantial data volumes from APIs, highlighting the efficiency gained from server proximity to hard drives for data transfer, an alternative to relying on cloud infrastructure.

These discussions provide a multifaceted view of the complexities and varied approaches in the field of data management and retrieval.

Archiving/Deletion

In the interview excerpts, Subjects 7, 8, and 3 share their distinct approaches to data archiving and deletion.

Subject 7 is inclined to archive almost everything, from old personal files to professional work, based on the potential future relevance of this information. They hold onto a vast array of files, believing that effective archiving can be costless and invaluable as a resource. The subject, however, acknowledges that advancements like ChatGPT might lessen the need for such extensive personal archives.

Subject 8 discusses a structured method for managing document archives, especially focusing on files awaiting feedback. These files are initially placed in a specific folder and moved to an 'accomplished' folder once finalized. The subject also mentions an unstructured approach to document versioning, where each file name begins with the date. For complex projects, an archive folder is created, but these are often deleted post-project to avoid unnecessary data storage.

Subject 3 reflects on their less frequent approach to deletion, guided by data protection regulations and client requests. They recognize the ecological impacts of excessive data storage and advocate for the deletion of non-essential data, particularly intermediate documents, to facilitate easier information retrieval and manage storage space efficiently.

These insights highlight the varied strategies employed in data management, balancing the retention of potentially useful information with practical and regulatory needs for efficient data storage and ensuring data protection.

Data Collection

In their discussions, Subjects 8, 3, 2, 4, and 9 share their approaches to data collection, highlighting diverse strategies and tools they use.

Subject 8 describes maintaining personal project folders that mirror the structure on the server. These folders house datasets, unless they are too large for OneDrive, in which case, they create an offline copy on their laptop. This multi-source system includes Trello, OneDrive, and offline storage, all organized by projects.

Subject 3 speaks about the importance of systematic and structured data storage, particularly in a project-based context. They note the challenge of balancing project-specific data storage with the need for

information sharing across projects, which sometimes requires searching for similar past projects.

Subject 2 discusses using Google Search for external databases, like IDB or the World Bank. They also mention the evolving use of AI tools to aggregate and summarize data from various sources, streamlining the process of data collection.

Subject 4 delves into the organization of different types of data within a structured directory, segregating raw data, models, training datasets, and classified datasets. They also emphasize sorting data by content and usage, such as restaurant reviews or patent datasets.

Lastly, Subject 9 talks about collecting vast amounts of data, like points of interest (POIs) across Germany. They describe using asynchronous technology to send multiple requests simultaneously, greatly speeding up the data collection process compared to sequential querying.

These insights reflect a blend of personal preferences and technological advancements in managing and collecting data, underscoring the importance of structure, organization, and efficient use of technology in data collection processes.

Data Storage

In their discussions, Subjects 6, 8, 3, 2, 4, and 9 share diverse approaches to data storage, highlighting a range of strategies and tools used.

Subject 6 primarily uses SharePoint for central data storage but also relies on email attachments stored in Outlook, especially for documents and email exchanges with clients. They also use a synchronized notes app for meeting notes and store workshop photos in a private photo library, indicating a blend of professional and personal storage solutions.

Subject 8 discusses maintaining mirrored project folders on both the server and their laptop, with an offline copy for datasets too large for OneDrive. This approach ensures data accessibility across Trello, OneDrive, and offline storage, all organized by projects.

Subject 8 also mentions using a dedicated server for storing large files, especially for data product development. In this case, the data is managed through a SQL database, accessible for work but not stored locally on devices.

Subject 3 emphasizes systematic and structured data storage, project-based, while also considering information sharing across projects. This approach sometimes necessitates searching for similar past projects to find relevant data.

Subject 2 speaks about not storing data due to its vastness, instead accessing it as needed via a good internet connection. They temporarily store needed data in Excel files on their laptop, which are deleted

after use to avoid data overload.

Subject 4 describes an automated data extraction process using a pipeline, where data is temporarily stored on a terminal server at Statista. This temporary storage is crucial for managing any interruptions or errors during data extraction.

Lastly, Subject 9 talks about managing large amounts of data received from various APIs. Their role involves managing storage to facilitate easy distribution and retrieval of this data.

These insights reflect a blend of personal preferences and professional requirements in data storage, emphasizing the importance of accessibility, organization, and efficient use of technology in managing data storage solutions.

Versioning

In discussing versioning, Subjects 7, 6, 8, 3, and 4 highlight their various approaches and tools used for managing different versions of data and documents.

Subject 7 talks about using branching in GitHub for code versioning. They create branches for specific processes or features, allowing experimentation before deciding whether to merge changes back into the main version. This approach is particularly useful for managing multiple functionalities or when awaiting additional information from clients.

Subject 6 mentions SharePoint's automatic versioning feature for documents stored within it. This system records every edit, facilitating the tracking of document evolution. The subject also describes a more manual approach for larger data sets with geographic references, organizing them into a tree structure mirroring their logical structure.

Subject 8 employs a sporadic and unstructured versioning method, naming files with the date at the beginning. This approach results in copies of files with different dates, essentially creating a version history. For projects with numerous files, they create an archive folder with different versions of documents, which are eventually deleted after the project's completion.

Subject 3 emphasizes the importance of versioning in services like SharePoint and Google Drive, where changes to documents are automatically tracked. In programming, version control is essential for managing source code changes, allowing developers to revert to previous versions if needed. For large datasets, making backups can also serve as a form of versioning, ensuring data recovery in case of system failures.

Subject 4 highlights the benefits of using GitHub for organized versioning, especially when collaborating on files. GitHub's version control system makes it easy to track changes, see who made

them, and understand the reasons behind each modification. This system is crucial for collaborative work, preventing the loss of information and ensuring smooth team coordination.

These insights showcase a range of methods for versioning, from automated systems in SharePoint and GitHub to more manual and unstructured approaches, reflecting the diversity in handling data and document versions across different projects and needs.

Backups

In discussing backups, Subjects 6, 3, and 4 provide insights into their strategies for ensuring data safety and recoverability.

Subject 6 focuses on centralizing data storage in SharePoint, complemented by email attachments stored in Outlook. This approach helps create a backup memory system, where they can recall and locate specific information based on past interactions. The subject also uses synchronized note-taking apps for meeting transcripts and stores workshop photos in a private photo library on their mobile device. These diverse storage solutions serve as separate backup pools for different types of data.

Subject 3 highlights the importance of backups for large data sets. They consider backups as a form of versioning, crucial for operational continuity, especially in live systems where a system failure could result in significant data loss. The ability to revert to older data versions or backups is essential in maintaining system stability and preventing data loss.

Additionally, Subject 3 notes that for web applications, regular backups of server-stored data are vital. They emphasize the importance of having a robust interface between the application and the data to facilitate regular and reliable backups.

Subject 4 discusses their approach in the context of data science, where handling vast amounts of data requires splitting them into batches for processing. They mention the use of multi-processing on servers equipped with numerous CPUs to process data points simultaneously. This process includes intermediate data storage and logging sessions to track progress and processing instances. This method acts as a backup mechanism, allowing them to identify up to which point data has been processed successfully, which is crucial in case of server or script malfunctions.

Together, these subjects illustrate various backup strategies, from centralized data storage and synchronized applications to robust server backups and logging systems, highlighting the importance of backups in ensuring data integrity and availability.

Validation

Subjects 9's discussions on validation reveal a comprehensive approach to ensuring data accuracy and relevance.

Subject 9 emphasizes the importance of validation in the context of data collected from various sources like Google or Amazon. The first level of validation involves verifying that the data is indeed from the expected source or API, such as Google in their examples. This step is crucial to confirm the authenticity and relevance of the data.

Another aspect of validation they discuss is contextual checking of the data. For instance, when searching for schools in a specific area, they might encounter data entries that, while technically fitting the 'school' category, may not be the type of educational institution they are looking for, such as a dance school. This level of validation ensures that the data makes sense in the context of the search query and project requirements.

Subject 9 also mentions issues that can arise at the storage level, such as incorrect annotation or data being saved in the wrong folder. To address this, they use a nested folder structure, where each file is categorized and stored based on specific criteria like location. This method allows them to go back and check each item's details, like its address, against the stored hierarchy to ensure accuracy.

They further explain the process of reverse validation, where they cross-check the hierarchical structure of the stored data against the actual details of the items. This step is vital to guarantee that the data has been stored correctly and corresponds accurately to the source.

Lastly, Subject 9 touches on the challenges posed by errors that can occur during the data's journey from the source to their system. These errors, often related to DevOps and data engineering, necessitate additional validation steps to ensure the data's integrity.

In summary, Subject 9's approach to validation is multi-layered, involving source verification, contextual relevance checking, storage accuracy, and reverse validation. This comprehensive process is crucial for maintaining the quality and usefulness of the data they collect and use.

9.7.3 Information Management Fundamentals

Tools

In their discussions on tools, Subjects 7, 8, 2, and 5 highlight the variety of software and applications they utilize for different aspects of their work, ranging from data analysis to project management and information tracking.

Subject 7 mentions using programming tools like Python or R for handling large datasets. These tools are preferred for their ability to manage and process significant amounts of data efficiently.

Subject 8 extensively uses Trello for organizing and tracking project-related information. Trello cards

are used to consolidate information from various sources like emails, team chats, and meetings. This method helps maintain a structured and accessible overview of projects and tasks. Additionally, Subject 8 integrates Trello with other tools like OneDrive, where files are stored and linked back to Trello for easy access. They also propose the idea of a unified search tool across Microsoft platforms, like Outlook and Teams, to streamline information retrieval.

Subject 2 discusses using specialized software for data categorization and analysis, emphasizing the role of technology in simplifying and automating these processes. They rely on these tools to "make the data talk," which suggests a high level of data interaction and interpretation facilitated by the software.

Subject 5 describes using Selenium, a Python library, for web scraping, illustrating a practical approach to data collection from websites. They detail how data is extracted and stored in data frames, and then saved as JSON files on SharePoint or departmental servers. The subject also mentions Power BI for data analysis, highlighting the use of different tools for various stages of data handling, from collection to analysis.

Lastly, Subject 5 notes that their colleagues often use GitHub for versioning, particularly in large projects involving substantial data processing and review management.

These insights reflect a multifaceted approach to tool usage in data-related tasks, showing how different software and applications are leveraged for efficient data management, analysis, and project organization.

Folder structures

Subjects 7, 6, 3, 5, 1, 4, and 9 share their strategies for organizing folder structures, highlighting the importance of systematic and logical organization for efficient data management.

Subject 7 talks about using a standardized folder structure, with folders like 'src' for raw code or assets, 'data' for data sources or outputs, and 'bin' for compiled elements. This standard helps in identifying the type of content in each folder, providing a clear and organized framework for storing different kinds of files.

Subject 6 details their method of sorting emails by individual projects and project phases, using a very structured approach. They emphasize the clarity and intuitiveness of their folder structure, adhering to the mutually exclusive, collectively exhaustive (MECE) principle. This approach ensures discrete categorization of folders based on project results, administrative documents, and other categories.

Subject 3 highlights the evolution of technology towards semantic search, which could potentially automate and enhance the folder organization process. However, they still maintain a consistent structure for each project, with folders like 'Project Documentation,' 'Results,' and 'Data Sets' for easy

retrieval of specific information.

Subject 5 describes using Selenium, a Python library, for web scraping, and how they store the scraped data in JSON format on SharePoint or departmental servers. Their storage method depends on the nature of the project, with web pages getting individual files containing product IDs and prices.

Subject 1 focuses on the importance of not having files scattered around, preferring a standardized folder structure that is adjusted to their team's workflow. This approach emphasizes findability and reproducibility of information.

Subject 4 discusses the necessity of structured data management, especially given the vast and varied nature of their datasets. They emphasize the importance of preliminary structuring and organization to prevent data loss and maintain criticality.

Finally, Subject 9 delves into the use of nested folder structures, especially for large-scale data collection projects. They describe organizing folders hierarchically by categories like POI, search terms, geographical locations, and postal codes. This structured approach allows for efficient data retrieval based on specific criteria.

Together, these subjects illustrate the crucial role of organized and logical folder structures in managing large volumes of data, ensuring efficient data retrieval, and maintaining project organization.

Predefined structure

The discussions by Subjects 8 and 5 on predefined structures focus on organizing and structuring data, especially in the context of web scraping and data collection.

Subject 8 describes the importance of sorting the scraped data in a meaningful way, which can be programmed into the scraping algorithm. They emphasize understanding the structure of the data at the outset, determining whether the data formats (like CSV, pickle, or other formats) and their content are what is needed before delving into folder structures. The goal is to ascertain whether the lowest level of information is relevant to avoid unnecessary sorting through folders that might only contain irrelevant files, like Word documents with a few bullet points.

In another context, Subject 8 talks about web scraping projects where the structure of the website dictates the organization of scraped data. They explain that sometimes the data needs to be sorted in an unstructured manner due to the variety of information on different websites. In such cases, sorting and organizing the data post-scraping becomes necessary, often aided by tools and algorithms.

Subject 5 discusses their approach to organizing information, particularly for web scraping projects. They explain that the method of storing data often depends on how the data is accessed. For example, if searching for certain types of professionals like doctors or dentists, it makes sense to store the data by

keywords (like "dentist") and then by postal codes. This approach ensures comprehensive coverage and helps in avoiding duplicates. For a project involving property taxes in the USA, they found it more efficient to download and store each variable separately, although the website allowed downloading complete data sets. They then created an Excel file to maintain the structure, categorizing the variables into personal (like age, marital status) and household (rent, house value, utility costs) categories. Both subjects highlight the importance of having a clear understanding of the data's structure and content before organizing it, and the necessity of tailoring the storage approach to the specific needs and characteristics of each project.

Meta information / Documentation / Logging

Subjects 7, 8, and 4 discuss the importance of meta-information, documentation, and logging in their workflows, emphasizing structured approaches for managing and tracking data and processes.

Subject 7 explains the use of folder structures as a form of meta-information. They detail how different types of content, such as data sources, raw code, or compiled items, are categorized into specific folders like 'data', 'src', and 'bin'. This system serves as a standard for organizing files and understanding their purposes at a glance. They also mention the practice of naming folders by dates or version numbers, which acts as additional metadata, indicating the timeline or the iteration of the datasets.

Subject 8 discusses using labels and color coding in Trello for project management. This method helps in quickly identifying and categorizing projects, such as paid projects or internal development tasks. By associating specific colors with project types, they can easily locate and reference relevant project information.

Subject 4 focuses on the process of handling large datasets in data science. They describe splitting massive datasets into smaller batches for processing, using multi-processing across multiple CPUs. To keep track of this complex process, they utilize logging sessions. These logs record which part of the data is being processed by which CPU, the progress made, and any instances of malfunction. This detailed logging is crucial for maintaining control over the data processing workflow and for troubleshooting in case of errors or server malfunctions.

Together, these subjects highlight the significance of organized data management practices. Whether through structured folder categorization, visual project tracking, or detailed logging of data processing, these methods are essential for efficient, accurate, and accountable handling of data and projects.

File/Folder Names

Subjects 3 and 9 discuss their approaches to naming files and folders, highlighting the differences in conventions and practices in various fields like IT, data science, and consulting.

Subject 3 points out the contrasts in how folders and files are named in the consulting field compared to

IT and data science. They observe that consultants often use a detailed and aesthetically organized naming system, including numbering, descriptive project names, and subfolders, often with spaces, mixed case, and special characters like Umlauts. However, from an IT and data science perspective, these naming conventions can cause problems. For instance, special characters or excessively long paths can lead to errors when scripts are used to read data. Subject 3 shares a personal experience where Umlauts in folder names caused their script to fail, illustrating the practical challenges that can arise from certain naming conventions.

Subject 9 describes a more systematic approach to naming files and folders, particularly focusing on incorporating key attributes into the names. They mention using timestamps as part of file names, indicating the exact time of creation or modification. This method provides a clear, chronological order and can be particularly helpful in managing version control and tracking the timeline of data or documents. The type of file is also considered in naming, providing immediate context about the content or format of the files.

These insights highlight the importance of adopting file and folder naming conventions that are not only clear and descriptive but also compatible with the technical requirements of the systems and software used. While aesthetic and detailed naming might be preferred in some fields, the practicality and functionality of names take precedence in IT and data science to ensure seamless data processing and management.

9.8 Part III: Challenges

9.8.1 Out of Control

Subject 3 discusses the challenge of a lack of knowledge with some clients, as they believe their data is unsafe on secure cloud servers (while they are safe). The Subject continues to speak about the challenge of working with folder structures from consultants within the company and external folder structures from clients, as these often include letters and signs that are not machine readable, or folder paths are too long which may also create issues.

Subject 8 mentions a similar issue, that a folder structure from a client was too complex to understand and comprehend, and required frequent communication with a responsible project manager, which delayed the project.

Subject 6 mentions in a similar vein, the intellectual challenge to understand folder structures presented by clients. It continues to state that there have been projects where the main challenge was to find the

right version of a file, rather than the sheer size of the collection. Subject 7 similarly complains about the challenge of understanding the logic behind a given structure. And Subject 4 introduces the challenge that sometimes the filetype or formatting is false when handed over.

9.8.2 Data Complexity and Source Management

Fragmentation

Subjects 3 and 8 discuss challenges related to data complexity and source management, specifically the difficulty of managing information from multiple sources and projects. The author notes that while there was a structure in place, finding files was a challenge and the project was complex with a tight deadline and large budgets at stake. The main problem was fragmentation of information, with many small files and notes from various sources that needed to be aggregated and incorporated into the data structure. The subjects note that working in a team exacerbates these challenges, as information is often spread across multiple platforms and servers.

Information Flood

Subject 4 is faced with the challenge of managing and structuring incredibly large and diverse datasets, including various file types. The primary concern is that without meticulous organization, the sheer volume could lead to significant information loss and inefficiency, making structured data management a critical necessity in their work.

9.8.3 Information Storage and Access Challenges

Storage

Subject 7 mentions the challenges of using Sharepoint (to ensure collaboration) for large information collections. It highlights that SharePoint easily reaches its limit and one needs to be careful when storing large data sets on SharePoint. Subjects 7 and 1 also mention that the main problem with storing large information sets is the costs. Servers might become affordable, but security control suffers.

Subject 3 mentions that the main challenge when working with large information collections is indeed the question where to store the information. It needs deep thought, otherwise one has to migrate from one solution to another on the go is a challenge.

Interestingly Subject 4 discusses the limitations they face with data storage, noting that Excel files can only store slightly more than 1 million rows and that their usual practice of storing data in JSON format

— while structured differently from Excel or CSV files—also has its limits, generally around one gigabyte in size. They acknowledge the existence of various other formats but emphasize that ultimately, each has its capacity limits.

Subject 5, similarly to Subject 7 mentions capacity issues they encountered with SharePoint.

Subject 1 states that large information collections produce larger challenges in the context of storage, the larger they are.

Storage / Access

Subject 6 and 3 mention additional challenges related to the storage and accessing of large information sets which include the lack of portability of data, as it is often stored on servers and requires SSH access to search for information. Additionally, the way data is stored and accessed can be complex, requiring knowledge of databases and file servers. Access and manipulation of data can also be limited by the skills of the individuals who can use the system. Efficient storage and access to data is crucial for systems that rely on it, as latency can cause delays and inefficiencies. Security measures can also add complexity to accessing data, requiring multiple SSH commands to access it through a secure tunnel.

Archiving

The challenge of archiving data arises when dealing with large amounts of information. Many people use external hard drives to store data, but this can lead to difficulties in accessing the information when needed. It is important to have a clear archiving strategy in place to ensure that data can be easily located and retrieved. However, even with a strategy in place, there may be instances where data is needed urgently, and the archiving system must be quickly navigated. Ownership of data can also be a challenge, as it may not always be clear who has access to certain files.

9.8.4 Organizational and collaborative challenges

Clarity

Subject 6 mentions: The first challenge in dealing with large amounts of data is having clarity and overview. It becomes impossible to manually view the file list when dealing with a large number of files. This means that even simple tasks like checking file titles, types, sizes, and dates require a script and someone who can evaluate the code.

Subject 4 states that the lack of overview and the complexity of data make it challenging to understand the information contained in the data. For example, OpenStreetMap's dataset was 144 GB, and it took a long time to understand the information contained within. The data in each row may also require further

processing, such as converting a word into a key that is then associated with a list of words.

Uncertainty and Unpredictability

Subject 8 states that it may not be easy to understand what file is the important one among many files- which one may I need in the future?

Subject 3 acknowledges the difficulty of anticipating all eventualities and the potential for hindsight to reveal better strategies. The Subject suggests that gaining new information or learning from colleagues can lead to changes in approach. They also note the importance of having a shared system for organizing information and collaborating but recognize that individual differences in approach can still lead to changes in strategy.

Data Protection Concerns

Subject 3 deals with sensitive and substantial data sets that, due to security concerns, sometimes require storage on encrypted external hard drives rather than on servers or in the cloud. They've had to use this method in a project where client data was so large that the safest solution was to physically transfer it with high security, such as in an armored vehicle.

Subject 1 mentions that handling large amounts of data with caution and consideration is important, as the impact of mishandling sensitive data can be significant.

Time-Constraints

Subject 2 discusses the challenge of transposing rows with columns in Excel would take one week without using Python scripts.

Subject 5 mentions that the processing is not the issue when working with large information sets, but rather the time it takes, given that they have deadlines to reach for their clients.

Subject 4 highlights that one needs time and patience when working with large information collections.

Collaboration

Subjects 7, 3, 1, and 4 highlight the complexities and challenges faced in collaborative data management:

Subject 7 points out the issues with syncing large files or many small files to SharePoint, noting that such practices can disrupt the platform's functionality. They recommend a strategy that involves sharing only essential data, like scripts, and keeping more extensive raw datasets local to prevent overloading shared systems.

Subject 3 discusses the challenges of aggregating and accessing project-related information dispersed across multiple channels and storage systems, such as SharePoint, Teams, and personal storage. This fragmentation creates difficulties in efficiently managing and accessing project data.

Subject 1 talks about the trade-off between local and shared storage, like SharePoint. They emphasize the need to balance speed and visibility, noting that while local storage is faster, it's less accessible to other team members. Deciding where to store data often depends on who needs access and their familiarity with the existing folder structure.

Subject 4 elaborates on the advantages of using platforms like GitHub for collaborative projects. GitHub's version control system is crucial for tracking who made changes to files, what those changes were, and the reasons behind them. This approach is key to preventing the loss of information when multiple team members work on the same file.

These insights collectively underscore the need for strategic planning and the use of appropriate tools in collaborative environments to manage data sharing, access, and version control effectively.

9.8.5 Technical and Processing Challenges

Special Skills needed

Subject 6 discusses the challenges of accessing and manipulating data, and the need for specialized skills to write scripts and work with complex data structures.

Subject 2 provides an example of using Python to automate data processing tasks, such as transposing rows into columns, which would be too time-consuming to do manually and requires Python knowledge.

The Subject 4 mentions the challenges of using certain filetypes commonly used when handling vast amounts of information. The challenge is that special tools are required to open data types like JSON or Parquet or Pickle, and one can't simply open the files and see what's inside.

Physical Challenges

Subject 2 describes the challenge that some excel files are too big to share them with clients. Subject 9 describes the challenge that a file needs to be stored on a special hard-drive and accessed via a VPN.

Data-Cleaning

Both Subject 2 and Subject 4 discuss the challenges of data quality and cleaning within large datasets, emphasizing the difficulty in spotting errors and dealing with incomplete or improperly formatted data,

especially when dealing with high volumes or third-party data sources.

Filesystem

Subject 4 highlights that filesystem hierarchy must align with how programs, like loops, access and process data, indicating that a change in the order can disrupt these processes. Subject 3 points out the challenge of organizing data for ease of access across multiple projects, suggesting that a project-based system might complicate retrieving information applicable to multiple contexts.

Tool Limitations

The Subjects discuss various technical and processing challenges in dealing with large amounts of data. Subject 2 mentions the limitations of Excel, which can struggle with large datasets and is limited to 1.04 million rows and require the use of other tools like Python or SQL databases.

Subject 5 highlights the SharePoint capacity limitations, while Subject 4 agrees on the Excel limitation when working with data sets beyond 1 million rows.

Another challenge mentioned by Subject 4 is the need to constantly find new ways to handle increasingly large amounts of data, which can require the use of different tools and approaches.

Time / Processing Challenges

Subject 5 describes a project that involved collecting data for a magazine that supports elderly people in the US. The data included information on evictions, unemployment, and utility costs. However, processing the large amount of data was a challenge, with over 300 variables for each state, county, and block level. It took a long time to process the data, but a library was found to help speed up the process. However, the data still needed to be combined and formatted correctly. Working with large datasets is always more difficult and time-consuming, and it can be costly to process and filter out unnecessary information.

Subject 4 mentions that processing large information collections is tenfold more challenging, compared to smaller information collections. And Subject 9 describes an instance where it took 12 hours just to load the information into the program.

9.9 Part IV: Strategies

9.9.1 Strategies to Address Organizational and Collaborative Challenges

Mental Models

In their discussions, Subjects 7, 6, 8, and 5 each describe unique mental models they employ as strategies for managing data and information, reflecting the varied challenges and requirements in their fields.

Subject 7 discusses a flexible model that adapts to the complexity of the project at hand. For straightforward tasks, a basic organization suffices, but as complexity increases with multiple iterations and various file types, the model evolves. This evolution involves using structured systems like GitHub for code management, while keeping data and presentations in separate, more suitable systems.

Subject 6 employs a mental model based on clear categorization and mutual exclusivity. This approach is designed to ensure that every piece of information has a specific, appropriate place within the system, making it intuitive and easy to navigate, especially for those new to the project.

Subjects 8 and 5 focus on condensing and structurally organizing large volumes of information. Their model prioritizes logical and contextual organization of data, ensuring that the structure aligns with the specific needs of the project. This method simplifies the management and retrieval of data by creating a logical and understandable framework.

Together, these subjects demonstrate the importance of adopting mental models as strategic tools in data management, with each model tailored to address specific project needs and complexities. These models serve as foundational approaches for effective and efficient information handling in diverse professional environments.

Information Hygiene

Subject 8 and Subject 1 discuss the concept of "information hygiene," emphasizing the importance of maintaining order and organization in their work processes to ensure efficiency and ease of access to important information.

Subject 8 likens the practice to daily routines like teeth brushing, suggesting it's a necessary habit for efficiency. They stress the value of dedicating a few extra minutes after each meeting or task to organize and sort through new information. This practice, although not always followed stringently, has proven crucial, especially when they need to quickly retrieve information. They also mention routinely sorting and transferring key information from emails and meetings, ensuring that important files, such as PowerPoint presentations, are saved in a central, easily accessible location.

Subject 1 focuses on the need for regular archiving of old files to avoid clutter in operational areas. They

draw a parallel between physical and virtual workspaces, emphasizing that just as one should not let their physical house become cluttered, the same principle applies to virtual workspaces. Keeping the virtual workspace uncluttered involves regular cleaning and organization, including the disposal or archiving of unnecessary files.

Both subjects highlight the importance of consistent and deliberate efforts to maintain order in information management. This "information hygiene" is key to preventing disorganization and ensuring that important data and documents are easily and promptly accessible when needed.

Communication and collaboration

Subjects 7, 6, 8, 3, 2, 1, 4, and 9 in their discussions emphasize the critical role of communication and collaboration as key strategies in managing information and working within teams.

Subject 7 highlights the importance of adhering to standard structures or best practices in data management and suggests directly consulting with involved parties for clarity. Subject 6 focuses on the significance of troubleshooting and the value of feedback from colleagues, pointing out the challenges in technical problem-solving. Subject 8 discusses the necessity of collaborating with clients for effective data structuring, to make sense of disorganized data.

Subject 3 points out the importance of documentation and clear communication to ensure that data organization methods are understandable to everyone involved. Subject 2 shares experiences with large datasets, emphasizing the need for constant communication with clients for data validation and troubleshooting.

Subject 1 talks about adapting to different collaborative strategies based on the team dynamics and project requirements. They advocate for flexibility and adapting to the methods chosen by the team or project lead. Subject 4 underscores the importance of logical structuring and naming of files from the start to avoid inefficiencies, especially when transferring work. Subject 9 discusses standardizing data formats within a team to ensure consistency and reduce time spent on data engineering.

Collectively, these subjects highlight the importance of clear communication, effective collaboration, and standardization in managing information and working efficiently in team environments.

Documentation

The critical role of documentation in data management is multifaceted, encompassing the importance of maintaining accurate records and the challenges of keeping documentation updated, alongside recommended best practices for effectiveness.

Subject 7 highlights the value of documentation in reflecting the accurate state of data, essential for mitigating confusion as data structures evolve. However, Subject 3 points out a real-world challenge: documentation often takes a backseat due to the demand for quick results, leading to difficulties in

comprehending complex structures and reusing information.

For effective documentation, Subject 7 suggests that newcomers document their learning process thoroughly, akin to creating detailed guides. This enhances understanding, similar to a novice documenting steps for internet use. Subject 6 observes that developers' thorough documentation methods, especially in well-commented code, contrast with the typically sparse documentation in business tools like Excel. This approach is invaluable for understanding the rationale behind coding decisions.

On practical aspects, Subject 3 emphasizes the importance of selecting appropriate data storage locations and using descriptive file names for efficient metadata management. This aids in swift comprehension and handling of datasets. Additionally, Subject 4 recommends writing readme files in data folders, a practical step that significantly aids in structuring information and guiding users to understand data collections more efficiently.

In sum, these insights underscore the significance of documentation as a key aspect of data management, highlighting challenges, best practices, and practical methods to maintain clear and useful records.

Learning from others

The subjects discuss strategies to address organizational and collaborative challenges, specifically in the context of working with large amounts of data. Speaker 1 suggests that when encountering problems, it is important to stop and search for best practices before trying to invent a solution. They recommend assuming that others have likely faced similar problems and have developed effective solutions over time. Subject 7 agrees, adding that it may be helpful to take courses to learn the basics and avoid developing bad habits.

One common challenge is the need to save large amounts of data after processing it through a pipeline. If this is not possible, valuable information may be lost and the process may need to be repeated. In this situation, it is important to quickly develop a strategy and research what others have done to solve similar problems. Subject 4 suggests looking to resources such as Towardsdatascience, Medium, Stack Overflow, and GitHub for articles and experiences related to the same issue.

Overall, the Subjects emphasize the importance of learning from others and not trying to reinvent the wheel when faced with challenges in data science and related fields.

9.9.2 *Strategies for technical and processing challenges*

Random Samples

Given the impracticality of reviewing entire datasets due to their size, random sampling is presented as a viable strategy. The approach involves examining various parts of the dataset, such as the beginning, middle, and end, and relying on quantitative data to validate the dataset's integrity. Key checks include verifying that all columns have the same number of rows and that data formats are consistent throughout the dataset. This technique acknowledges that while it is impossible to have a 100% overview of massive datasets as one might have with a small table of ten rows and three columns, random sampling can effectively highlight errors and ensure data quality on a broader scale.

Automatisation

One subject highlights the importance of automatisation practices when dealing with large amounts of information.

Data Prioritising

Subject 5 mentions that they have faced capacity constraints on SharePoint due to large datasets with many variables and observations. The subject suggests prioritizing data based on the research questions and variables of interest, rather than downloading all the data. Subject 9 mentions considering the costs and time involved in data processing. To filter out irrelevant data, they suggest defining thresholds based on price and quality (in an Amazon reviews example, to filter out irrelevant information before the scraping or download)

Batches

The strategy of "batching" involves segmenting large datasets into more manageable packets for processing. This approach is beneficial in several contexts:

- **Targeted Data Provision (Subject 6):** If a collaborator only needs a subset of the data, providing just that portion can simplify their work. This process involves selective data exporting and helps in reducing complexity for the end-user.
- **Working with Data Subsets (Subject 3):** In the initial conceptual and proof-of-concept phases, working with a portion of the data can mitigate the challenges posed by large datasets and streamline the development process.

- **Overcoming Software Limitations (Subject 2):** When dealing with data quantities that exceed software limitations (e.g., Excel's row limit), batching allows for the distribution of data across multiple files, which requires additional steps for cleansing and organizing but ensures all data is accommodated.
- **Handling Extensive Data (Subject 5):** For projects involving an immense number of variables, batch processing can be used to load and analyze data in chunks, improving efficiency. This method may necessitate additional steps to restore data formats and titles post-processing.
- **Individual Variable Files (Subject 5):** Storing each variable as a separate file and loading only those needed for current analysis can expedite processing, allowing for faster, more focused analysis.
- **Batching in Data Analysis (Subject 4):** When dealing with millions of data points, dividing the data into batches (e.g., every 2000 data points) makes it more feasible to handle and analyze the data sequentially.

In essence, batch processing is a strategy for dealing with the technical and processing challenges of large datasets by reducing their size into manageable pieces, enabling efficient analysis, transfer, and storage of data.

9.9.3 Using / Developing Tools

General advice regarding tools

Subject 2 discusses strategies for technical and processing challenges, specifically using and developing tools. It advises a hybrid approach between humans and tools, i.e. to double-checking scraped information on company websites or databases, as tools like Python may find but not always correct mistakes. For those new to dealing with large amounts of data, the subject recommends becoming proficient in Excel and learning coding languages like Python or MySQL. The subject cautions against underestimating the complexity of dealing with large amounts of data and emphasize the importance of knowing how to write scripts to address problems.

External Tools/Technologies

GitHub (Subject 7 & Subject 4)

- **Code Management Strategy:** Subject 7 uses GitHub for organizing large volumes of code, tracking issues, and maintaining structure, which simplifies the management of complex development projects. Subject 4 highlights its role in systematic file storage and providing clear documentation for project contents.

Trello (Subject 8)

- **Information Aggregation Strategy:** Subject 8 utilizes Trello for aggregating massive amounts of information from various sources into structured project cards. This strategic use of Trello maintains clarity and prevents the loss of critical details amidst the information overload.

Ray (Subject 9)

- **Data Processing Strategy:** Subject 9 applies Ray for efficient processing of extensive data collections. By using this tool, they can handle multiple data requests concurrently, significantly speeding up the time-consuming data analysis processes.

Tools that were developed internally

Customized Interfaces and Systems (Subject 6):

- Developed a specialized document management and workflow system tailored for data annotation tasks.
- Created user-friendly, clickable interfaces, akin to PowerBI, enabling non-developers to interact with and control data without coding.

Scripting for Data Transformation (Subject 2)

- Wrote a Python script to transpose rows into columns in databases, efficiently reformatting the data structure for easier analysis and handling massive datasets.

Variable-Specific Data Loading (Subject 5)

- Devised a method to save and load data variables individually, enhancing the speed and efficiency of data analyses by working with only the necessary segments of the dataset.

Custom Tools for Data Aggregation (Subject 9)

- Supervised the development of a 'Data Aggregator' tool, which aggregates data based on specific attributes across nested folders, such as searching for particular services in a given city.

In these strategies, internally developed tools are employed to customize data interaction, transform and manage data structures, and perform targeted data aggregation to cope with the challenges presented by large volumes of information. These tools enable the handling of data in a more efficient, user-friendly manner, reducing complexity and the need for manual intervention.

9.9.4 Strategies for Information Storage and Access Challenges

Search

The subjects discuss strategies for information storage and access challenges, specifically focusing on search. Subject 7 suggests using tools with search functions to find information based on keywords, file type, creation date, or other criteria. They note that folder structures may not always accurately reflect the context of the information in a file. Subject 3 mentions that semantic search technology, which recognizes the meaning behind words, is the future of search. Subject 9 emphasizes the importance of organizing information with a consistent folder structure to facilitate search and avoid chaos.

Access

Subject 6 suggests that one strategy for overcoming information storage and access challenges is to store data in the cloud, which allows for secure and location-independent access. Another strategy is to package data into smaller sets for easier handling and export. The subject's own data team helps with this process. To quickly find information, subject 8 uses Trello to avoid having to search through folders. Subject 4 emphasizes the importance of backing up data to ensure access in case of server failures or errors in data extraction. Subject 9 mentions the use of a distributed computing architecture has helped to significantly reduce the time needed to access and process data.

Version Control

The subjects discuss the importance of version control in managing large amounts of information and files. Subject 1 explains that version control allows for easy modification of files while maintaining a record of changes, but can lead to duplicate files and increased storage space. Subject 4 emphasizes the importance of including a date or version number in file names to track changes over time and avoid

deleting old files. Subject 5 mentions the use of GitHub for version control in large projects with multiple collaborators. Overall, version control is seen as a crucial strategy for managing information challenges.

Storage

- **Cloud-Based Solutions (Subject 6):** A foundational strategy is to utilize cloud storage, which not only provides similar security as traditional servers but also enhances accessibility by being location-independent, ensuring that data storage is not a limitation to access.
- **Centralized Data with Access Links (Subject 8):** Rather than copying and storing large data sets in multiple locations, which compounds storage needs and can slow down operations like searches, it's more efficient to keep data in a central location and use links to refer to the files needed for specific projects.
- **Sizing Up Storage Needs (Subject 8 & Subject 5):** When data sets become too large for standard solutions like SharePoint or local storage, strategies shift to server-based storage, where data can reside and be indexed or integrated with databases as needed.
- **Handling Overcapacity (Subject 5):** To deal with capacity issues, like those experienced on SharePoint, transitioning to server storage becomes necessary, especially when data scraping results in continuous file generation.
- **Balancing Cost and Access (Subject 1):** Storage is expensive and scarce, necessitating a balance between the likelihood of needing to access project data post-completion and the cost of storing large volumes indefinitely. Archiving rather than deleting data when it's no longer in active use is a preferred strategy.
- **Automated Data Handling and Backup (Subject 4):** An automated pipeline extracts data, which requires time and needs to be stored on a server like Statista's Terminal Server, with interim backups essential to prevent data loss.
- **Nested Folders for Organized Storage (Subject 9):** The strategy remains consistent across platforms, where data collected at the start of a project is stored in a localized place, typically on a hard drive, following a structured nested folder approach.
- **Local Server Advantage (Subject 9):** Despite the trend towards cloud computing, there is an advantage in using local servers that are directly connected to the hard drive,

offering faster data transfer rates compared to cloud migration, which is susceptible to slower internet connections and the complexities of VPN routing.

These strategies reflect the diverse approaches to storing large amounts of data, from embracing cloud solutions to optimizing local server capabilities, all with the aim of ensuring data is securely stored, efficiently organized, and remains readily accessible when needed.

Subject 1 describes a strategy to archive information from SharePoint to a local drive, because this is cheaper and provides more space than SharePoint, yet it is more difficult to access and to collaborate on.

9.9.5 Foundational Strategies

Structured Approach

The subjects discuss the challenges of managing information and the importance of having a structured folder system to save time and increase efficiency. Speaker 3 highlights the frustration of searching for information and the negative impact it has on motivation and productivity compared to having it in a structure. The subjects 4, 8 and 9 believe that having a clear folder structure and naming convention is crucial for maintaining organization and avoiding confusion. Subject 9 agrees that a structured system is necessary not only for automated aggregation but also for easy navigation and avoiding chaos when revisiting data.

- **Avoid Overcomplicating Systems (Subject 7):** Recommends not to create complex systems that do everything. As data handling methods change over time, it's better to use established solutions to problems and maintain a system that is easy to work with.
- **Learn to Organize Problems (Subject 6):** Emphasizes learning how to clearly define and organize problems, which is important when using different software and systems to find information or solve issues.
- **Start with a Clear System (Subject 8):** The importance of starting with a clear organizational system is stressed, like having a specific folder for each project. Consistency is key, but one should also be ready to tweak the system to make it better.
- **Consistent Naming and Structure (Subject 4 & Subject 1):** It's crucial from the beginning to structure files and name them in a consistent manner. This makes it easier to understand and work with the data, whether you're a person or a computer program.

- **Test Before Scaling (Subject 5):** Before using data on a larger scale, it's suggested to start small to ensure everything works correctly, especially when costs are involved.
- **Maintain Reproducible Structures (Subject 1):** The strategy highlights the need for structures that can be replicated, which is essential in managing data efficiently.

In simpler terms, the structured approach strategy involves starting with a simple and clear system for organizing data, learning how to ask the right questions to different systems, and being consistent in how you handle data so that both people and computers can understand it. It also means being able to adapt and improve the system over time and ensuring that the methods used can be repeated reliably.

Planning and preparation

- **Run Dry Tests Before Actual Execution (Subject 6):** Before performing significant operations like moving large folders on SharePoint or merging tables, it's recommended to do a dry run. This might involve writing down the steps or using database operations to preview results. It ensures that resource-intensive or irreversible actions are checked beforehand.
- **Thoughtful Systematic Structure (Subject 3):** It's important to define a systematic structure for folder organization considering the nature of the data. This might mean sorting by project, data type, or other relevant categories while incorporating necessary considerations like data anonymization and time components.
- **Excel and Scripting Knowledge (Subject 2):** Advises learning to use Excel efficiently, including VBA scripting, and gaining coding knowledge in Python or SQL before tackling large data sets. This foundational knowledge can help solve many problems that come with large amounts of data.
- **Hypothesis-Driven Analysis (Subject 5):** Emphasizes the need to form hypotheses and structured questions before delving into data analysis to ensure that the findings are meaningful and relevant, not just statistically significant.
- **Thorough Data Cleaning (Subject 4):** Stresses that with large data sets, strategic thinking is required from the start. It's crucial to clean data meticulously and have contingency plans for any issues that might stop the processing, allowing the workflow to continue despite errors.

- **Data Prioritization and Thresholds (Subject 9):** Contemplates the need to prioritize data based on the task at hand, and to always consider which data prioritization makes the most sense for the objectives of the analysis.

In simpler language, this strategy revolves around the idea that when working with large amounts of data, you should plan carefully and test processes before fully implementing them. Know how to use data tools effectively, make sure you understand the data you're working with, and be ready for errors so they don't stop your entire project. It's also about asking the right questions and cleaning your data thoroughly to ensure your analysis is reliable.

9.9.6 Strategies for Information Complexity and Source Management:

Context-dependent decision-making

Subject 3 discusses strategies for managing complex information and sources, specifically in the medical field. It emphasizes the importance of sorting data by entities and considering time components, while also ensuring proper anonymization. The subject stresses the need for systematic organization to easily locate information, while highlighting that the chosen folder structure depends on the Use-Case.

Subject 5 discusses different approaches to structuring data, such as organizing variables either horizontally or vertically. The speaker notes that the choice of structure depends on the intended use and the program being used. They also mention the importance of organizing data in a way that makes sense for the specific use case, such as grouping search terms by category or location. Ultimately, the best approach depends on the specific question being asked.

Data Zones / specific structure

Subject 8 discusses one strategy to create a specific folder structure, such as having a folder for each project and a Trello card for each task.

Subject 8 and 4 state it is important to have a specific structure for different types of data, such as raw data, processed data, and classified data. Data may be sorted by content or usage, such as reviews of restaurants or patents related to autonomous driving.

Subject 9 introduces the concept of data zones and mentions that there are also different zones for data, such as a raw data zone, a processed data zone, and a golden zone for high-quality data ready for use in databases.

Early on structure

Subject 3, 9 and 8 emphasize the importance of early on structuring data and creating a folder structure to easily locate important files. They also suggest defining formats and encouraging clients to deliver data in a specific way to avoid the need for extensive restructuring. The speakers stress the importance of having a good nomenclature and folder structure to automate the process of retrieving data early on. They conclude that having discipline and structure early on is key to managing large amounts of data effectively.

Personal Structure

Prefix-Based Filing System (Subject 3)

Subject 3 employs a prefix system for folder names to manage projects and tasks systematically. This structured approach extends to the creation of subfolders where files are meticulously organized, ensuring a clear and consistent retrieval system.

Mirrored Folder Structures Across Platforms (Subject 8)

Subject 8 adopts a strategy where personal project folders are mirrored across different storage platforms—from a server to OneDrive, and locally on a laptop. This redundancy ensures that files are accessible from multiple locations and are organized consistently across all platforms.

Administrative and Project Division (Subject 1)

Subject 1 outlines a standardized structure that categorizes files into administrative areas, data centers for storage and delivery, working environments for active processing, and final delivery folders for finished products. This approach creates a distinct workflow pathway, similar to a factory's production line.

Separate Coding and Data Files (Subject 4)

Subject 4 details an organized structure specifically for coding workflows, with separate files for variables, functions, and main execution. This separation is mirrored in the data organization, with a dedicated folder for finalized files intended for clients or internal project discussions.

In essence, these individual strategies reflect a common theme of creating a structured and reliable organization system tailored to each person's workflow, ensuring that data and code are managed in a way that enhances efficiency and clarity across all stages of project work.

Standards

Subject 7 discusses a folder structure that follows best practices and standards, such as having a data folder and a SAC or Bin folder. However, it mentions that there are no fixed standards for folder structures.

Subject 1 states that within his team, Project managers can decide on individualized file naming conventions, but the project structure cannot be changed. It is important to archive old files and maintain consistency in the folder structure to facilitate easy access and onboarding of new team members. Subject 1 describes the advantages of a standardized folder structure include easy access to files and the ability to onboard new team members more easily.

9.9.7 File/Folder Names

Machine Readability

Structured Naming for Automation (Subject 3)

Subject 3 outlines the importance of having a structured and consistent naming convention for files and folders. By using prefixes and underscores, a system is created that allows metadata to be integrated into the file names, facilitating automated scripts and machine interactions.

Standardization and Compatibility (Subject 1 & Subject 4)

Subjects 1 and 4 focus on the theme of standardizing file names to ensure machine readability. They discuss the necessity of avoiding special characters and spaces, using a uniform naming pattern that supports seamless processing by software, and ensuring compatibility between the file names and the automated systems that manage them.

Version control

Automated Versioning Systems (Subject 6)

Subject 6 discusses the shift from manual version numbering to relying on systems like SharePoint that automatically version files with each edit. This automation requires users to ensure that the final versions of files are correctly named, reflecting the stages of development from draft to completion.

Date-Prefix Sorting (Subject 8):

Subject 8 highlights the practice of starting every file name with a date, which aids in sorting and locating files within folder structures. This consistent inclusion of the creation or modification date at the beginning of file names serves as a simple yet effective versioning method.

Version Control for Data Files (Subject 4)

Subject 4 emphasizes the importance of including dates or version numbers in file names. This versioning practice is crucial for maintaining historical versions of files, allowing one to track changes over time and ensure that older versions are preserved for reference or in case of the need to revert to previous data points.

In summary, these themes reflect different approaches to versioning in file and folder names, from automated systems that handle versioning behind the scenes to user-defined practices like prefixing files with dates or including version numbers to maintain a clear history of document edits and updates.

9.9.8 Structure

Flexible adaption as collection grows

Subject 8 emphasizes the importance of flexible adaptation as collections grow, and the need to regularly restructure and optimize systems. The subject notes that as projects become more complex, the standard folder structure may no longer be sufficient and may require additional restructuring.

Technical structure

The subjects discuss strategies for managing complex information and sources. One strategy is to use a technical data structure, such as a hierarchical tree, to organize large amounts of data by geographic regions and locations. Another strategy is to carefully consider how data is stored and organized, as it can be difficult to find specific data within a large dataset if it is not systematically stored.

Subject 3 recommends working with clients to ensure that data is delivered in a specific format and developing a good folder structure and nomenclature to facilitate automated data retrieval. They emphasize that creating a good structure and defining formats are essential for achieving the best results in data science tasks.

9.10 Part V: Transferability of strategies

9.10.1 Not transferable (no)

Over-Engineering

Subject 8 mentions that using advanced folder structures for small information collections can be an "overkill". One should rather restructure the information collection as it grows and demands for it.

Subject 2 suggests that if you don't have a certain script to reuse it won't make much sense to write it for a small information collection, because you can simply do the task manually.

Subject 5 holds the opinion that complex versioning and folder structures may not be required and therefore over-engineered.

Subject 9 discusses the example of using Ray for distributed computing, which requires specific preparation and experience, and may not be worth the effort for smaller datasets.

Subject 1 states that the cost-benefit ration does not match, having duplicates of small files does not "hurt".

The subjects conclude, that the effectiveness of a strategy should be weighed against the time and cost required to implement it.

Threshold not reached to determine if a structure works

Subject 8 mentions that one can only evaluate if a structure works once a certain threshold is reached, wich may not be given when applied to small amounts of information.

9.10.2 Transferable (yes)

Importance of conscious data management

The subject 6 mentions that the conscious handling of information collections, known from larger information collections, would be beneficial for smaller collections. It highlights having a understanding of the storage location, the rules around deletion etc. would be beneficial when handling smaller information collections.

Search

Subject 6 believes that transferring strategies from large to small information media can be helpful because generative AI demonstrates that accessing vast datasets can be made simple and user-friendly, implying that similar intuitive search functions should be available for smaller data systems like Outlook or SharePoint.

Re-Use of existing set-ups

Subject 2 mentions the re-usability of scripts developed for larger information amounts for smaller ones. Subject 4 mentions that the strategies from a small information collection won't work on a large information collection, but the strategies from a large information collection will work on smaller information collections. It mentions that one can re-use data pipelines for analysis and processing (originally build for large collections) on smaller information collections to increase efficiency.

Use of structure

Two subjects discuss that using structure even for smaller information collections is beneficial for collaboration.

Subject 7 mentions collaborative work in the context of information collections, which originated from the tech scene and large information collections. One such strategy is the use of open spaces, such as Google Docs, for simultaneous access and tracking of changes. Another strategy is the linking of project management and file management, where milestones and subtasks are defined and referenced to specific files. It believes that these strategies, originally emerged from work with larger information collections will integrate more into the "normal World" in the future.

Subject 3 emphasizes the importance of having a systematic structure for data storage, regardless of the size of the data, to facilitate collaboration and understanding among team members. The use of semantic structures is recommended for easy navigation and comprehension.

Subject 5 believes that using the same structure, globally, even for smaller information collections can increase the speed of dealing with the information, since one recognizes the structures already.

Versioning

Subject 7 discusses the usefulness of versioning and the ability to compare differences between versions, which is particularly useful in software development. This feature could also be adapted for smaller information tasks, such as tracking changes in Outlook appointments. Git branching is also mentioned as a useful strategy for testing changes without risking the stability of the main project. The subject adds that creating secure backups and experimenting with different versions can be helpful in ensuring that changes can be easily reverted if necessary. These are strategies that are helpful even for smaller information collections.

Strategy that emerged from larger collections being adopted

Subject 7 discusses strategies that emerged from the handling of large information collections. It

mentions the automation of tasks that were previously done manually, such as uploading large files to iCloud instead of emailing them. Another strategy is the use of separate communication channels for sending files, which has been adopted by developers and is now being offered as a tool for the general public. Collaborative working, such as using Google Docs, is also mentioned as a strategy that originated in the tech industry. The integration of project management and file management is another strategy, where milestones and subtasks are defined and linked to specific files for better tracking and organization.

9.11 Full Code System (interim)

Code System	Count
Codesystem	486
Other	0
Knowledge sharing	1
Changes in information storage logic over time	1
Importance of avoiding obsolescence	1
Organizational responsibility for skill development	1
Need for continuous learning	1
Lack of data skills in traditional business education	1
Governance and Compliance	1
Increase of efficiency	1
Reduction of complexity	1
Self-Assessment	1
Brid Statements	53
1. Learning/Challenges from handling large amounts of information	10
Documentation	2
Importance of thoughtful consideration before analyzing data	1
Learning from others	1
Planning and preparation	1
Proactive approach and error prevention	1
Flexibility	1
Automation	1
Structured approach	4
Importance of structured problem-solving	1
Documentation and understanding of algorithms	1
Cultural impact on documentation practices	1
Communication and collaboration	2
Seeking feedback and collaboration	1
Troubleshooting skills and knowledge	1
Empowerment through self-documentation	1
Self-documentation and self-awareness	1
Importance of preparation	1
2. Challenges/Strategies dealing with large info collectors	8
Challenges	9
Challenges: Retrieval	4
Dynamic changes in strategy	0
Uncertainty and unpredictability	1
Data Protection Concerns	1
Fragmentation	1
Many Sources Challenges	2
Anschlierung	2
Time-Constraints	4
Filetype	1
Filesystem	2
Collaboration	4
Data-Cleaning	2
Information Flood	1
Special Skills needed	2
Largest / most complex projects	6
Challenges besides the volume of data	2
Storage	8
Access	2
Clarity	4
Out-of-control	3
External impact	3
Understanding data organization	1
Challenge: Prioritizing	2
Time / Processing Challenges	2
Physical challenges	2
Tools	3
external	6
hardlimits	5
Github als Filemanagement Strategie	1
challenges	1
own developed	1
Large vs. small info collections	13
Storage / Access	2
Data Safety	2
Search	1
Tool limitations	1
Dealing according to a plan	3
Planning and preparation	1
Strategies	21
anchoring	1
Hybrid	1
Search	2
Online-Research	2
Collaboration	5
Process Planning / Strategic Approach	2
Version Control	3
Documentation	2
Backups	4
Storage	4
Access	3
Increase in efficiency due to jim	1
Information Hygiene	4
Mental Models	5
Adaptation to overcome data challenges	1
Struktur	11
Folder Struktur	9
Context-dependent decision-making	2
Predefined structure	1
restrukturieren	1
File/Folder Names	2
Machine Readability	2
Data Prioritizing	2
Transferability of strategies	5
Transferability of strategies	3
not transferable large to small	2
No Other-Engineering	2
No	1
Speed	1
Versionierung	1
Diff	1
Info: Data-Cleaning-Pipelines / Automatisierung	0
Re-Use for smaller File collections	2
Linking project management and file management	1
Collaboration work	2
Comparison between accessing data in different interfaces	1
Importance of conscious data management	1
3. General handling of info	5
File/Folder names	1
Tools	4
Shared learning/Collaboration	1
Continued learning	1
Documentation/Logging	1
Tool design	2
Data Quality	6
Meta information	1
Folder structure	4
Archiving/Deletion	4
Data Collection	5
Data Storage	8
Versioning	5
Backups	4
Vollständigung	3
Safety	6
Organization	18
Folder structures	3
Management	1
Labels	1
Retrieval	9
Scraping	1
Information acquisition strategies	1
How did the info end up in the personal space?	12
Info Sources	14
Info Types	7
Main Task: focus on info	9
Main Task	10
sets	0

Figure 4 Full code system (interim)

9.12 Distribution of Codes Among Subjects

Figure 5 Distribution of codes among subjects (black colored codes have been excluded from the thesis)

9.13 Full Description of the Creation of the Interview Guide

As mentioned in section 3.6, "SPSS" represents four process steps in the creation of the interview guide: Collect, Review, Sort, and Summarize (in German, "Sammeln", "Prüfen", "Sortieren", "Subsummieren"). In "Collect," all relevant questions for the research interest are gathered. This can be considered a free collection and brainstorm-like approach. In "Review," the previously collected question list is evaluated and optimized based on specific criteria and questions: "The first test question eliminates all questions asking for facts", and the researcher is supposed to ask him-/herself: "Do questions lend themselves to generating open-ended responses or narratives at all?", or "What am I curious about, what *don't* I know yet?". Lastly, review questions that eliminate questions about abstract relationships are asked: "Can I even demand an answer to this from the narrators with their own subjective world?". In the next step, the remaining questions are grouped by topics or possibly by time-related aspects (for example, questions relating to something before an event and questions relating to something after an event). Lastly, in "Summarize," simple overarching prompts are crafted for each question group following this lead question: "Does the chosen wording lend itself to evoking a narrative in which as many of the aspects of interest as possible are addressed on their own?" (Helfferich, 2011).

9.14 Interview Guide

Intro:

Der Untersuchungsgegenstand der Studie: Umgang mit großen File Collections im persönlichen Arbeitsbereich (am liebsten Dateien in Ordnerstrukturen, aber auch Dateien in Datenbanken): persönliche Strategien, Praktiken, Aktivitäten und Verhaltensweisen, um diese Informationen zu erwerben, zu erstellen, zu speichern, zu organisieren, zu pflegen, abzurufen, zu nutzen und zu verbreiten.

- Soziodemographika des Experten (Alter, Geschlecht, Position, Hierarchielevel)

Warmup Fragen:

- Können Sie kurz beschreiben, was Ihre Arbeit als XXX beinhaltet?
- Können Sie Ihre Arbeit noch einmal beschreiben, aber jetzt auf die Rolle der für Ihre Arbeit benötigten Informationen eingehen?
- Welche Informationen haben und nutzen Sie in Ihrem persönlichen Arbeitsbereich?
- Was ist die Quelle dieser Informationen (woher stammen die Dokumente)?
- Wie sind die Dokumente in Ihrem persönlichen Arbeitsbereich gelandet?

Erzählaufforderung (Leitfrage)	Stichworte	Vorformulierte Frage	Aufrechterhaltungs- und Steuerungsfragen
<p>Teil 1: Wie gestalten Sie Ihren alltäglichen Umgang mit Informationen in Ihrem persönlichen Arbeitsbereich?</p>	<p>Suchen von Informationen, Speichern von Informationen, Organisationsmethoden, Versionierung, Tools, Sicherstellung von Informationsqualität (bspw. Data-Cleaning, Know your Data etc.), Kollaboration</p>	<p>Wie organisieren Sie Informationen in Ihrem persönlichen Arbeitsbereich?</p>	<p>Wie gehen Sie normalerweise vor, um Informationen in Ihrem Arbeitsbereich zu finden, wenn Sie sie brauchen?</p> <p>Organisieren Sie Ihre Dateien auf eine bestimmte Weise? Warum?</p> <p>Wie oft und unter welchen Umständen löschen Sie Informationen in Ihrem Arbeitsbereich?</p> <p>Wie oft werden die Informationen in Ihrem elektronischen Arbeitsbereich gesichert?</p> <p>Wer führt die Sicherungen durch?</p> <p>Welche Funktionen würden Sie sich wünschen, um Informationen in Ihrem Arbeitsbereich zu organisieren und abzurufen, die Sie noch nicht haben?</p> <p>Welche Werkzeuge haben sich als besonders hilfreich erwiesen?</p> <p>Sie haben gesagt, dass Sie (XXX) verwenden. Was gefällt Ihnen an diesem XXX besonders gut? Gibt es Funktionen oder Merkmale, die Sie besonders schätzen?</p>
<p>Teil 2: Denken Sie an einen Zeitpunkt, an dem Sie mit besonders vielen Informationen Umgehen mussten. Was waren die Herausforderungen?</p>	<p>Spezifische Herausforderungen, entwickelte Strategien zur Lösung</p>	<p>Welche Strategien haben Sie entwickelt, um spezifisch mit großen Informationsmengen zu arbeiten?</p>	<p>Wie unterscheiden sich die Herausforderungen bei großen Informationsmengen im Vergleich zu kleineren Mengen?</p>

			<p>Wie unterscheiden sich Ihre Ansätze für große Informationsmengen im Vergleich zu kleineren Mengen?</p> <p>Können Sie mehr zu Ihrem Vorgehen beim Speichern / Organisieren (Versionierung, Datenqualität, Validierung, Backups etc.) / Suchen von großen Informationsmengen sagen?</p> <p>Haben Sie Beispiele für besondere Herausforderungen?</p> <p>Sie haben erwähnt, dass Sie [eine bestimmte Strategie] verwenden. Können Sie mir einen konkreten Fall beschreiben, in dem diese Strategie besonders nützlich war?</p> <p>Welche anderen Ansätze haben Sie in der Vergangenheit ausprobiert und warum haben Sie sich letztlich für diese bestimmte Strategie entschieden?</p>
<p>Teil 3: Was wären Ratschläge oder Lektionen, die Sie teilen würden, basierend auf Ihren Erfahrungen im Umgang mit großen Informationsmengen, besonders für diejenigen, die neu in diesem Bereich sind?</p>	<p>Technologische Entwicklungen, Anpassung der Strategien, Größte Informationsprojekte, Einfluss von Werkzeugen und Strategien</p>	<p>Glauben Sie, dass die von Ihnen angewandten Strategien auch anderen Personen in unterschiedlichen Kontexten (zB mit weniger großen Info Mengen) helfen könnten?</p> <p>Warum? Warum nicht?</p>	<p>Welches war das anspruchsvollste Informationsprojekt, an dem Sie beteiligt waren?</p> <p>Welche Tools, Praktiken oder Strategien sind Ihnen dabei besonders in Erinnerung geblieben?</p>

9.15 Datenmanagementplan (DMP) für die Abschlussarbeit¹

Titel der Arbeit: *Strategies for dealing with large collections of information in the workplace: A case study in personal information management*

Art der Arbeit: Bachelorarbeit

Name: Jo Teichmann

Matrikelnummer: 577843

Kontakt: jo.f.teichmann@gmail.com

Datum Einreichung: 24.11.2023

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Generelle Anmerkungen:

- Wenn Sie keine Anmerkungen zu einer Frage haben oder diese nicht auf Ihre Abschlussarbeit zutrifft, vermerken Sie es bitte (z. B. „trifft nicht zu“).
- Wenn Sie mehrere Datensatztypen (z. B. Interviewaufnahmen und deren Transkriptionen) oder mehrere Datensammlungen aus z. B. unterschiedlichen Quellen haben, beschreiben Sie diese bitte einzeln in dem jeweiligen Kapitel, wo sinnvoll.
- Sie können dem DMP gerne Anhänge zufügen (bitte nummerieren und darauf dann verweisen) oder auf entsprechende Kapitel in Ihrer Abschlussarbeit verweisen.
- Bitte beachten Sie auch die jeweilige FDM-Policy, Richtlinien und/oder Handreichungen der Humboldt-Universität (HU).

¹ Dieses DMP Template wurde für den gemeinsamen Masterstudiengang Digitales Datenmanagement (DDM) des Instituts für Bibliotheks- und Informationswissenschaft der Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin und des Fachbereichs Informationswissenschaften der Fachhochschule Potsdam entwickelt. <https://www.ddm-master.de/>

1. Allgemein

1.1 Thema

1.1.1. Wie lautet die primäre Forschungsfrage der Abschlussarbeit?

"What strategies do individuals employ to manage and handle vast amounts of information in a workplace setting?" In this context, particular attention is given to the challenges of dealing with extensive information collections. Ultimately, the discussion will consider whether these identified strategies can benefit a broader audience.

1.1.2. Bitte geben Sie einige Schlagwörter² zur Forschungsfrage bzw. Fragestellung an.

GDN Schlagwörter: Informationsmanagement(4114012-6), Wissensmanagement(4561842-2), Wissensorganisation (4205605-6), Big Data (4802620-7), Data Science (1140936166)

1.1.3. Welchen Regeln oder Richtlinien (HU) zum Umgang mit den in der Abschlussarbeit erhobenen Forschungsdaten folgen Sie für den DMP? Bitte referenzieren Sie diese hier inklusive Version bzw. Veröffentlichungsjahr.

Leitlinien zum Umgang mit Forschungsdaten in Abschlussarbeiten vom 08. Dezember 2021 https://www.ibi.hu-berlin.de/de/studium/rundumdasstudium/fdm-fuer-studierende/leitlinie_forschungsdaten_finale_version_dez_21-1.pdf

2. Inhaltliche Einordnung

NB: Bitte beschreiben Sie jeden Datensatztyp oder Datensammlung einzeln in dem jeweiligen Kapitel, wo sinnvoll.

2.1. Datensatz

2.1.1 Um welche Arten von Daten handelt es sich? Bitte in wenigen Zeilen kurz beschreiben.

Für die Arbeit wurden 10 Interviews mit der Videokonferenz Software Zoom durchgeführt. Anschließend wurden die Transkripte mit Hilfe der Software für qualitative Datenanalyse MAXQDA erstellt, codiert und analysiert. Die Interview Notizen liegen auch vor.

2.2 Datenursprung

2.2.1 Werden die Daten selbst erzeugt oder nachgenutzt?

Die Daten wurden selbst erhoben.

2.2.2 Wenn die Daten nachgenutzt werden, wer hat die Daten erzeugt? Bitte mit Angabe des Identifiers, falls vorhanden, z.B. DOI³.

Trifft nicht zu, siehe oben.

2.3. Reproduzierbarkeit

2.3.1 Sind die Daten reproduzierbar, d. h. ließen sie sich, wenn sie verloren gingen, erneut erstellen oder erheben?

Die Daten sind nicht exakt reproduzierbar. Da es sich um Interviews handelt, würde es bestimmte Abweichungen zwischen den ersten und zweiten Interviews geben.

2.4 Nachnutzung

2.4.1 Für welche Personen, Gruppen oder Institutionen könnte dieser Datensatz (für die Nachnutzung) von Interesse sein? Für welche Szenarien ist dies denkbar?

Der Datensatz kann für Forscher:innen im PIM oder FM Bereich, Human Information Behavior sowie der IT-Entwicklung von Interesse sein.

² Hier gern auch ein anerkanntes (Fach)Vokabular nutzen, die Dewey Dezimalklassifikation (DDC deutsch, <https://deweysearchde.pansoft.de/webdeweysearch/mainClasses.html?catalogs=DNB>) oder Gemeinsame Normdatei (GND, https://gnd.network/Webs/gnd/DE/Home/home_node.html) bieten sich für fachübergreifende Terme an. Bitte angeben, ob und falls ja, welches Vokabular benutzt wurde bzw. ob freie Schlagwortvergabe angewendet wird.

³ DOI, <https://www.doi.org/>

3. Technische Einordnung

3.1 Datenerhebung

3.1.1 Wann erfolgt(e) die Erhebung bzw. Erstellung der Daten?

Die Interviews wurden im Oktober 2023 durchgeführt und im November 2023 transkribiert.

3.1.2 Wann erfolgt(e) die Datenbereinigung / -aufbereitung bzw. Datenanalyse?

Die Datenanalyse fand im November 2023 statt.

3.1 Datengröße

3.1.1 Was ist die tatsächliche oder erwartete Größe der Daten(typen)?

Die MAXQDA Dateigröße liegt bei 3,3 MB.

Die Word Dateien liegen bei ca. 25kb pro Datei.

3.2 Formate

3.2.1 In welchen Formaten⁴ liegen die Daten vor?

.mx22

.docx

3.3 Werkzeuge

3.3.1 Welche Instrumente, Software, Technologien oder Verfahren werden zur Erzeugung, Erfassung, Bereinigung, Analyse und/oder Visualisierung der Daten genutzt? Bitte (falls möglich) mit Versionsnummer und Referenz in Form einer Adresse jeweils angeben.

Die Aufnahmen wurden mit der Videokonferenz Software Microsoft Teams Classic (Version 1.6.00.29954) aufgenommen. Um die Transkripte zu erstellen, so wie die Codierung und Analyse dieser, wurde die Software MAXQDA2022 Version verwendet.

3.3.2 Welche Software, Verfahren oder Technologien sind notwendig, um die Daten zu nutzen?

MAXQDA

Microsoft Word

3.4 Versionierung

3.4.1 Werden verschiedene Versionen der Daten erzeugt (z. B. durch verschiedene Weiterbearbeitungsprozesse bzw. Bereinigung von Daten)?

Es liegen die Rohdaten in Form von Audio-/Video-Aufnahmen der Interviews vor, genauso wie die Abschriften davon. In MAXQDA werden die Daten dann codiert und analysiert.

4. Datennutzung

4.1 Datenorganisation

4.1.1 Gibt es eine Strategie zur Benennung der Daten? Wenn ja, bitte skizzieren Sie sie kurz.

Die Leitfaden Notizen sind im Format Leitfaden_JT_VornameSubject angelegt.

4.2 Datenspeicherung und -sicherheit

4.2.1 Wer darf (zukünftig) auf die Daten zugreifen?

Die Gutachter dürfen auf die Daten zugreifen.

4.2.2 Wie und wie oft werden Backups der Daten erstellt?

Es wird jede Woche ein Backup erstellt und die Daten werden auf einer externen Festplatte gespeichert. Außerdem liegen die Daten zusätzlich in der HU-Box und werden dort täglich aktualisiert.

⁴ Vgl. z. B. DROID zur Format-Erkennung, <http://digital-preservation.github.io/droid/>

4.3 Interoperabilität

4.3.1 Sind die Datenformate im Sinne der FAIR-Prinzipien interoperabel, d.h. geeignet für den Datenaustausch und die Nachnutzung zwischen bzw. von unterschiedlichen Forschenden, Institutionen, Organisationen und Ländern?

Für die vorliegende Untersuchung wurden teilweise proprietäre Datenformate verwendet, wie MAXQDA. Die Interview-Transkripte liegen allerdings im offenen Format .docx vor.

4.4 Weitergabe und Veröffentlichung

4.4.1 Ist es geplant, die Daten nach Abgabe der Abschlussarbeit zu veröffentlichen oder zu teilen?

Nein, bisher nicht.

4.4.2 Wenn nicht, skizzieren Sie kurz rechtliche und/oder vertragliche Gründe und freiwillige Einschränkungen.

Der Forscher ist sich noch nicht sicher, welche Teile der Daten und Arbeit veröffentlicht werden sollen.

4.4.3 Wenn ja, unter welchen Nutzungsbedingungen oder welcher Lizenz sollen die Daten veröffentlicht bzw. geteilt werden?

4.5 Qualitätssicherung

4.5.1 Welche Maßnahmen zur Qualitätssicherung (z. B. Plausibilitätsprüfung von Datenwerten) werden für die Daten ergriffen?

Da es sich bei dieser Arbeit um Daten aus Interviews handelt, ist es schwierig diese Datenwerte einer Plausibilitätsprüfung zu unterziehen. Die Interviews und deren Bearbeitung wurden nach bestem Wissen und Gewissen durchgeführt. Es wurde darauf geachtet die Regeln der guten wissenschaftlichen Praxis einzuhalten. Wie die Interviews genau vorbereitet, durchgeführt und anschließend bearbeitet wurden wird ausführlich im Methodenkapitel der Bachelorarbeit beschrieben.

4.6 Datenintegration

4.6.1 Falls Daten aus verschiedenen Quellen (z. B. Anpassung Skalierung, Zeiträume, Ortsangaben) integriert werden, wie wird dies gewährleistet?

Nicht zutreffend.

5. Metadaten und Referenzierung

5.1 Metadaten

5.1.1 Welche Informationen sind für Außenstehende notwendig, um die Daten zu verstehen (d. h. ihre Erhebung bzw. Entstehung, Analyse sowie die auf ihrer Basis gewonnenen Forschungsergebnisse nachvollziehen) und nachnutzen zu können?

Der Interview-Leitfaden, der den vorliegenden Daten zu Grunde liegt befindet sich im Anhang. Außerdem sind die Informationen im Methodenkapitel der Bachelorarbeit zu finden.

5.1.2 Welche Standards, Ontologien, Klassifikationen etc. werden zur Beschreibung der Daten und Kontextinformation genutzt?

Da es sich bei den vorliegenden Daten um Interviews handelt, werden keine Standards, Ontologien oder Klassifikationen genutzt. Es wurde ein ausführliches Codebuch für die codierten Interviews angelegt, dieses wurde induktiv aus den Daten heraus erstellt. Das Codebuch (kontrollierte Vokabularliste) befindet sich ebenfalls hier im Anhang.

6. Rechtliche und ethische Fragen

6.1 Personenbezogene Daten

Ja, es wurden personenbezogenen Informationen abgefragt. Informationen, wie zum Beispiel das Alter und der Name der interviewten Person.

6.1.1 Enthalten die Daten personenbezogene Informationen?

6.2.1 Sensible Daten

6.2.2 Enthalten die Forschungsdaten besondere Kategorien personenbezogener Daten nach Artikel 9 der DSGVO ("Angaben über die rassische und ethnische Herkunft, politische Meinungen, religiöse oder philosophische Überzeugungen, Gewerkschaftszugehörigkeit, Gesundheit oder Sexualeben")⁵?

Nein.

6.2.3 Werden die Daten anonymisiert oder pseudonymisiert?

Die Namen der interviewten Personen wurden in der Arbeit anonymisiert. In der schriftlichen Arbeit werden Begriffe wie Subjects verwendet.

6.2.4 Haben Sie eine "informierte Einwilligung" der Betroffenen eingeholt? Fügen Sie bitte ein Template der Einverständniserklärung als Anlage bei.

Die Einverständniserklärung befindet sich im Anhang. Die Einverständniserklärung besteht aus einem Informationsschreiben, Hinweis zum Datenschutz und der Einwilligungserklärung. Es wird festgelegt, dass die erhobenen Interview-Daten nur anonymisiert verwendet werden.

6.2.5 Wenn keine "informierte Einwilligung" eingeholt wird, begründen Sie dies bitte.

Nicht zutreffend.

6.2.6 Wo und wie sind die "informierten Einwilligungen" abgelegt?

Die Einverständniserklärungen befinden sich mit allen anderen erhobenen Daten auf einer externen Festplatte in den privaten Räumen des Autors und außerdem in der HUBox

6.2.7 Bis wann werden die (un-anonymisierten bzw. un-pseudonymisierten) Originaldaten spätestens sicher vernichtet?

Die Audio-/Video-Daten werden nach erfolgreichem Bestehen der Bachelorarbeit gelöscht. Gleiches gilt für die Interviewmitschriften.

6.2 Urheber- oder verwandte Schutzrechte

6.3.1 Werden Daten genutzt und/oder erstellt, die durch Urheber- oder verwandte Schutzrechte geschützt sind?

Nein.

7. Speicherung und Langzeitarchivierung

7.1 Wo werden die Daten (einschließlich Metadaten, Dokumentation und ggf. relevantem Code bzw. relevanter Software) während Phase der Erarbeitung der Abschlussarbeit gespeichert?

Die Daten werden zum einen in der HU-Box des Autors gespeichert und zum anderen auf einer externen Festplatte, die sich in der Wohnung des Autors befindet.

7.2 Wo werden die Daten (einschließlich Metadaten, Dokumentation und ggf. relevantem Code bzw. relevanter Software) nach dem Ende der Abschlussarbeit gespeichert bzw. archiviert?

Auf der externen Festplatte des Autors.

7.3 Handelt es sich dabei um ein zertifiziertes Repository oder Datenzentrum (z.B. durch das CoreTrustSeal⁷, nestor-Siegel⁸ oder ISO 16363⁹)? (Wurden mehrere Langzeitarchivierungsoptionen ausgewählt, kann die Frage bejaht werden, wenn dies auf mindestens eine der Optionen zutrifft).

Nicht zutreffend.

⁵ <https://dsgvo-gesetz.de/art-9-dsgvo/>

⁶ Vgl. z. B. Registry of Research Data Repositories, <https://www.re3data.org/>

⁷ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/about/>

⁸ https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/DE/Zertifizierung/nestor_Siegel/nestor_siegel_node.html;jsessionid=766FAA5089CB1958F7EAEB00D2BA51F3.internet542

⁹ http://ikeep.com/ISO_16363_ISO_16919_DIN_31644